

**TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE (TPACK) OF
B.ED TRAINEES**

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2019

CHAPTER - I

INTRODUCTION AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The teaching landscape is rapidly changing, the technological rise of the 21st century and widespread integration of those technologies into our society, combined with access to the internet has integrally changed teaching in just a few years. Our children, and their following generations are already and will continue to grow up in a world that's a stark reminder of how rapidly the human civilization has changed, a society and world where smart phones and tablets are widespread, affordable, and replacing most computers and laptops. The rapidly changing landscapes should be a marker to show that teaching methods need to evolve to keep up with the times and incorporate integrated technologies into the learning modal, these technologies aren't going to go away, they'll continue to be integrated into our society and it's time to embrace them for the advantages they bring.

The modern age of science and technology demands creative and dynamic as well as multi-dimensional and multi-media approach. It is broadly termed as "Information and Communication Technology (ICT)." A teacher should be able to incorporate the facilities of ICT in the classroom as much as possible by changing the stimulation and sustaining the attention of the students. But the use of technology and giving facts alone are not part of good teaching. Good teaching is to be kind and sympathetic. Love for teaching and students are essential. Justice and impartiality are virtues which must be cultivated for successful teaching. Teaching is a co-operative affair between the teacher and the taught. Successful teaching must create a congenial atmosphere in the classroom for mutual interaction. It may be possible through the actions, behaviour and personality of the teacher.

Educational technology implies a behavioural science approach to teaching and learning in that it makes use of pertinent scientific and technological methods and concepts developed in psychology, sociology, communications, linguistics and other related fields. It also attempts to incorporate the management principles of cost effectiveness and the efficient deployment and use of available resources in men and materials. Educational technology as a concept does not necessarily imply the use of machines and other items of hardware. Experience has shown that more often than not they involve such media, equipment and resources.

In short educational technology, in its wide sense as understood today, includes the development, application and evaluation of systems, techniques and aids in the field of learning. As such its scope encompasses educational objectives, media and their

characteristics, criteria of selection of media and resources, management of resources, as well as their evaluation.

The growing use of educational technology in today's schools has helped to release the teacher from the routine role of information giving so that he/she can devote his/her time and effort to the more important tasks of planning, arranging and evaluating learning experiences and outcomes and of encouraging, enthusing, guiding and counseling pupils. The various technological media are used to communicate the needed factual information to pupils and they are capable of doing this perhaps more accurately and efficiently than the teacher. So today pupils acquire knowledge through the various media and behavioural changes via the teacher. Another noticeable trend is the creation of multimedia learning environments in the classroom which involve the use of variety of interrelated learning experiences.

Educational Technology has to be taken up as a comprehensive and continuous programme. It has, of course, to be used as a remedy for inherent deficiencies in the system, in one place to offset the teachers' lack of qualifications by regular broadcast demonstrations or by programmed documents for the pupils; in another to speed up the introduction of new subjects or new methods of teaching, to take over activities on which schools have fallen down, and so on. Teacher-training programmes can thus be improved by radio and television broadcasts.

Educational Technology can promote a certain amount of flexibility into the functioning of the school system which has been in a rut for decades. For imparting in-service training to teachers and improving their professional growth, educational technology provides ample opportunities. It also works as a means of rapid dissemination of education on a massive scale and of increasing the effectiveness of education by making learning a more individual process. Moreover, educational technology implies new methods for the production of teaching materials and a division of talent in their uses.

The development of educational technology would open up the prospect of creating and recreating new types of educational institutions in future radically different in structure and function from those of the traditional ones. It would help in reducing wastage to a minimum, which is a great drainage of resources both physical and human. Since the society of tomorrow is to be founded on lifelong education, the self-teaching or self-study centers would grow-up, which can possess various educational technologies. Even the formal teaching would no longer mean a matter of forcing information upon inert pupils in an

authoritarian method, but one of exposing self-motivated youth to the practices of self-teaching or self-learning.

1.1.1 OBJECTIVES OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY

Technology is opium of intellectuals and for grading against super egoism; the responsible technology is much more required. The Education Commission (1964-66) has recommended that the fundamental objectives in the curriculum should be improved so that teachers can be prepared for various responsibilities towards education. Educational objectives should be enumerated and following major objectives of educational technology should be improved in all teaching learning process.

- a. To determine the goals and formulate the objectives in behavioural terms.
- b. To analyses the characteristics of learner.
- c. To organize the content in logical or psychological sequences.
- d. To mediate between content and resources of presentation.
- e. To provide the feedback among other components for the modification of learners.

Thus the objectives of educational technology are formulated for the purpose of communication and through this communication all the teaching and learning can easily be achieved. Educational technology always carries fresh looks into classroom situations. Therefore, in the light of educational objectives, it can be said that educational technology has a very vital importance in the field of education.

1.1.2 SCOPE OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY

Educational technology is process oriented technique. Educational technology is not limited to teaching and learning process and theories still teaching learning process is influenced much more by educational technology. Theories have been shifted from learning to teaching only due to educational technology. If the educational technology is limited to audio-visual aids, mechanical and electronic gadgets the scope of educational technology becomes limited, but educational technology is not limited to all these things rather, it pervades all the over.

1.1.3 IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY

As far as the educational system is concerned, it is absolutely revolutionized by educational technology. Educational process cannot go systematically without the help of educational technology. Every aspect of educational system is fully enlightened with educational technology. It has great importance in educational field. The importance of educational technology in the area of education is as following:

- a. Educational technology improves the teaching learning process and makes it more effective and process oriented.
- b. Educational technology has not only maintained the standard of education but also improved the ways of teaching by giving teaching aids and programmed instructional materials.
- c. Students appearing in the higher examination or competitive examinations may be benefited by organizing educational programme on television and radio.
- d. New innovation of system analysis in the field of educational technology can help in solving educational administrative problems.
- e. Educational technology opens new field for educational researches which throw light on the new dimensions in the field of examination process, classroom teaching and training problems.
- f. Educational technology provides practices and strategies for reducing individual differences or strategies and practices which help teachers to teach according to individual differences of the learners.

1.2 TEACHER EDUCATION

Teachers are a section of community sharply segregated from the rest, preparing themselves for their life's work in institutions for developing human attributes. The teacher education system as it exists today lacks in educating human beings. The trained teacher is too often an untrained human being. The aim must be the education of the right human beings for work in our schools. The only means of strengthening one's intellect is to let the mind be a thoroughfare for all thoughts, not selected party. From this open-mindedness, sympathy, tolerance, intellectual adaptability and width of interest will develop the attributes essential for successful living and dealing with children. But all this requires a comprehensive philosophy of life and education, a map by which the future teacher may observe himself in relation to other teachers as well as other activities of human beings. During his training course, he must be given time and opportunity to think about education, because the trainee will have little time for it after completing his training as he will be engaged in the all absorbing tasks of the classroom and the common life.

Therefore, a prospective teacher must be offered opportunities to associate with the best minds and to develop a disciplined intellect as well as the quality of appreciation of culture in its various forms. He will have the emotional life developed to a fine sensitivity but held in strict control.

Competence and professional skills are the very heart of the programme of teacher education. Professional education should focus on the person as an individual who is in practice and seeks to broaden his mental, moral and emotional capacities. The person should have a sound philosophy of education, knowledge of adequate functioning of psychology along with a dynamic sociological perspective. Only such teachers will be able to relate theoretical insight to practice and to improve preparation programme. They will be effective practitioners in their profession. Teacher education seeks to develop such competencies in the prospective teachers which will make him/her a successful teacher. It tends to increase the ability of a teacher to deal with a range of individual differences.

The teacher of tomorrow would design a teaching situation conducive to the growth of pupils' mental health. It would develop certain skills and competencies. The teacher requires a new type of knowledge and attitude, atmosphere and facility to make his task easy, fruitful and confirming to the demands of the students. Therefore, the teacher education should be according to the necessities of the time and needs of the society. It should develop the following:

- (i) To relate learning with the individual diagnosis instruction.
- (ii) To analyses group development interaction and to perform a leadership role in a group.
- (iii) To communicate with the individual as well as the group.
- (iv) To acquire knowledge and skill in a disciplined manner.
- (v) To structure the acquired knowledge, to choose from his specialization, the type of knowledge that is important for a particular individual or group.

1.2.1 NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF TEACHER EDUCATION

A teacher has been given great regards, since ancient times, not only in India, but also in the world. Manu, the ancient law giver has said, "A teacher is the image of Brahma (the creator of the universe)". An old Indian Prayer says, "Gurur Brahma, Gurur Vishnu, Gurur Devo Maheshwara, Guru Sakshat Par Brahma, Tasmai Shri Guruve Namah" i.e. "The teacher is God Brahma; he is God Maheshwara. He is the whole universe, obeisance to the teacher". According to Indian Culture, a child receives his physical birth from the parents and second birth at the hands of the teacher. The teacher is given a higher position than parents, because he opens the pupil's eyes of knowledge and moulds his character. As it is said that God created man after His own image, so also the teacher fashions his student after his own image. In the Western world also, the teacher is given great regards, Adams said, "A teacher affects eternity, he can never tell where his influence stops". In other words, his work does not confine to a particular state or a country; it transcends all the boundaries. His

contributions do not confine to a particular period of time. His influence can cover the entire span of life. Henry van Dyke once said, "I sing the praise of the unknown teacher, king of himself and leader of mankind".

The role of the teacher and his/her education is the foundations on which the superstructure of the education of a country is based. Besides the initial preparation of teachers, the teacher education also includes the programmes for further education of teachers already engaged in the teaching profession and with the assumption that the teaching activity can be definitely improved after undergoing such programmes. Professor Humanyun Kabir rightly stated, "Without good teachers even the best system is bound to fail. With good teachers even the defects of a system can be largely overcome". To meet the national needs especially those of 21st century teachers have to decide on and construe the curriculum, aids to instruction and persuade boys and girls with their demeanor and deeds.

Teachers have a great responsibility at a time when the society is undergoing transformation in re-orienting education. Their task will not be confined to preserve, interpret and transmit the culture to the coming generation, but also to bring about social change. They have to work as active agents in ushering forth-new social order based on equality, liberty and justice. Indeed, teachers have an astounding task to perform.

1.3 TECHNOLOGICAL, PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE (TPACK)

Technology's impact on the teaching and learning environment has changed not only the way our students process new concepts and achieve learning objectives, but it has also modified the way in which instruction is delivered. Students' needs are diverse, and the forms of technology that they encounter in their learning environment may not fit those needs of every student or subject (Halverson, 2003). The educational technologies that a teacher may use in the teaching and learning environment may not adapt to every diverse need; rather, it is the job of the teacher to creatively apply these tools to meet the needs of the student.

Teachers in the 21st century must not only be familiar with the operation of instructional technologies but also with their application within the curriculum and their classroom (Eisenberg & Johnson, 1996). The technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge (TPACK) framework is a conceptual model designed to rethink how a teacher might approach the integration of technology. Topper (2004) suggests that "for teachers to use technology in support of their teaching, and see it as a pedagogically useful tool, they must be confident and competent with the technology they are planning to use". Similarly, to the recommendations by Greenhow, Dexter and Hughes (2008), the TPACK framework

helps the teacher to connect what is being taught to the way in which it is taught, with the technology used to enhance these connections. TPACK emphasizes "the connections among technologies, curriculum content, and specific pedagogical approaches, demonstrating a teachers' understanding of technology, pedagogy, and content that can interact with one another to produce effective discipline-based teaching with educational technologies" (Koehler & Mishra, 2008). By considering the impact that technology could have on the content and its delivery, a teacher might be able to overcome different factors faced and embrace new approaches to academic success.

Today's technology advancements, educational contexts should take advantage of innovative pedagogy and digital rich tools for deeper content exploration, ease of classroom management, engagement and motivation of students in learning contexts, and generally revolutionizing the learning spaces of old to meet the learning needs of today's students. It is logical to think that classrooms equipped with chalk and erasers, fixed rows of desks, and behavioral pedagogy would have yielded to changes caused by the technological advancements; however, despite the addition of digital tools, educational practices have changed little in the global context of educating youth.

TPACK will "emphasize the connections among technologies, curriculum content, and specific pedagogical approaches, demonstrating how teachers' understandings of technology, pedagogy, and content can interact with one another to produce effective discipline-based teaching with educational technologies" (Koehler & Mishra, 2008, p.1025).

Incorporating technology into the classroom is a complicated task. There are a multitude of barriers that can prevent technology integration from happening. Understanding the existing technologies and potential barriers, as well as how teachers experience those barriers, is critical to successful integration and adaptation over time. The TPACK framework offers a lens into the integration of technology in classrooms. Use of this framework, along with analysis of lesson plans and open-ended surveys, will inform this study to examine the range of ways that teachers implement technology and experience barriers. Further, this study will look to explore patterns in these experiences along dimensions of teachers' years of experience, subject area and other emergent relevant characteristics.

1.4 COMPONENTS OF TPACK MODEL

1.4.1 TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE (TK)

Technological Knowledge (TK) is related to different innovations and their utilization (Koehler and Mishra, 2005; Mishra and Koehler, 2006; Koehler et al. 2007; Koehler and Mishra, 2008; Mishra and Koehler, 2008; Harris et al., 2009; Koehler and Mishra, 2009;

Schmidt et al., 2009). Innovation is utilized to help the teacher while giving the content to the learner, to help the discourse between the educator and the understudy, or for introducing the content to the learners to direct their exploration on the content. (Hammond and Manfra, 2009). Technological Knowledge (TK) is more fluctuating than Content Knowledge and Pedagogical Knowledge. It is the trouble confronted amid characterizing it. The upcoming Knowledge of innovative progressions can without much of a stretch give advantage to time hungry educators. It can be additionally suggested that technological knowledge is at the danger of getting to be plainly obsolete till it end up noticeably congenial to ordinary citizens. (Koehler and Mishra, 2005).

The Technological Knowledge, in this way, required by an educator requests inside and out learning and understanding of advances for data preparing and critical thinking as opposed to the conventional meanings of PC as it were. The possibility of TK does not imagine an "end state," but rather it is thought to be dynamic, growing over a lifetime of generative communications with different advances. Technological Knowledge (TK) is the Knowledge about certain methods for considering, and working with technological instruments and different resources of innovation. In this manner the understanding of innovation includes utilizing it adequately and productively at work place and everyday life too. Likewise having the capacity to recognize when innovation can increment or back off the achievement of student, and being capable to adjust your-self as per changes set aside a few minutes to time (Koehler and Mishra, 2009). The idea of technology coordination in schools most generally alludes to the utilization of advanced technologies, for example, portable PCs, Internet, and programming applications. TK however goes a remote place than computerized education as it were. Its motivation is to utilize existing technologies in classroom condition for upgraded teaching and learning (Harris, 2008).

1.4.2 PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE (PK)

Pedagogical knowledge is teacher's profound information that incorporates the systems, procedures, practices and standards of teaching learning, classroom administration and association in Education (Shulman, 1987). It is the knowledge of teaching-learning procedures, applications or techniques. The knowledge is situated to general classroom administration aptitudes, lesson arranging, understudy's evaluation and knowing the learning styles of learners and the act of teaching likewise (Koehler and Mishra, 2005; Mishra and Koehler, 2006; Koehler et al., 2007; Koehler and Mishra, 2008; Mishra and Koehler, 2008; Harris et al., 2009; Koehler and Mishra, 2009; Schmidt et al., 2009). Teacher use extra strategies to draw out the coveted results from learners practices and to help learners. Fitting

the 21 adequate innovations in the classroom relies upon the academic motivations of the educator. Instructional method should lead the innovation; the turnaround circumstance ought not to be legitimate (Hammond and Manfra, 2009).

It incorporates knowledge about procedures or techniques utilized as a part of the classroom, the nature of the students' needs and inclinations, and methodologies for surveying learners' understanding. An educator with profound Pedagogical Knowledge sees how learners build learning and secure aptitudes in separated routes, and additionally how they create propensities for brain and demeanors toward learning. All things required for Pedagogical Knowledge are understanding of psychological, social, and developmental theories of learning and how they apply to learners in the classroom. This learning is vital however not adequate for teaching purposes. An educator requires content learning notwithstanding this too. (Harris et al., 2009)

1.4.3 CONTENT KNOWLEDGE (CK)

Content Knowledge (CK) is the information about the topic. As Shulman (1986) noted, content incorporates information of ideas, hypotheses, thoughts, authoritative systems, techniques for confirmation and verification, and in addition built up theories and methodologies toward growing such learning in a specific area. For instance, For the situation of art appreciation, such information would incorporate learning of craftsmanship history, popular canvases, forms, the impact of craftsmen's recorded and social settings, and in addition information of tasteful and mental speculations for comprehension and assessing workmanship. The cost of educators having a deficient content related knowledge base can be very restrictive; learners can create and hold epistemologically erroneous conceptions about and inside the content region (Bransford, Brown, and Cocking, 1999; Pfundt, and Duit, 2000, National Research Council, 2000).

Content Knowledge (CK) is the information about the topic that will be taught or learned for instance, middle school science, secondary school history, undergraduate art history, or graduate-level astronomy. Learning and the nature of inquiry contrast enormously among content regions and it is fundamentally imperative that educators understand the disciplinary "propensities for mind" appropriate to the topic that they instruct (Koehler and Mishra, 2009). Content Knowledge is tied in with understanding the topic profoundly and making inquiries from various areas (Koehler and Mishra, 2005; Mishra and Koehler, 2006; Koehler et al., 2007; 22 Koehler and Mishra, 2008; Mishra and Koehler, 2008; Harris et al., 2009; Koehler and Mishra, 2009; Schmidt et al., 2009).

1.4.4 TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE (TPK)

Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK) is an understanding of how teaching and learning change when specific innovations are utilized. This incorporates knowing the instructive affordances and limitations of a scope of technological devices and assets. Technological Pedagogical Knowledge requires building an understanding of the potential advantages and confinements of specific advancements as they can be connected inside specific sort of learning exercises, and additionally in the teaching-learning settings inside which these technological bolstered exercises works best. An imperative part of Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK) is the creative adaptability with accessible instruments important in planning to utilize them for particular pedagogical purposes. The flexible utilization of apparatuses turns out to be especially critical on the grounds that most mainstream software programs are not intended for educational purposes. Programming, for example, the Microsoft Office Suite (Word, PowerPoint, Excel, Entourage, and MSN Messenger) is intended for use in business conditions. Online advances, for example, writes (blogs) and podcasts are intended for entertainment, correspondence, and interpersonal interaction. Educators, hence, must have the knowledge and aptitude that enable them to utilize appropriate technologies for educational purposes, so they can utilize Excel, for instance, to help youngsters in sorting out and examining the data, and they can make use of podcasts as approaches to share developed information with others (Koehler and Mishra, 2009). Consequently, TPK must incorporate a forward looking, innovative, and liberal mindedness for technological application, not for its own particular purpose, but rather for headway in learning and comprehension. A vast extent of innovation based learning exercises that have been produced in the past to delineate innovation reconciliation, through their absence of accentuation upon content and teaching method, additionally represent a fragmented and relatively shallow type of TPK.

1.4.5 TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE (TCK)

Technological Content Knowledge (TCK) is the learning of both Technology and content to be instructed. This knowledge requests adaptability with the utilization of innovation in technology as demanded by the content (Koehler and Mishra, 2005; 23 Mishra and Koehler, 2006; Koehler et al., 2007). Technological Content Knowledge (TCK) incorporates an understanding of the way in which innovation and content impact and compels each other. In anticipating teaching, content and innovation are frequently considered independently. Effective teaching requires building up an understanding of the ways in which topic can be changed by the utilization of various advances. Educators must

understand which advancements are most appropriate for which sort of topic and how content shapes the use of particular innovation and the other way around. We distinguish three ways in which innovation and content are identified with each other.

To begin with, the appearance of new innovation has regularly changed a very basic level of what we consider to be disciplinary content. Consider how, the creation of Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) and other Internet conventions significantly changed the courses in which we work and convey. Content shapes new innovations and offers new uses for existing advancements, while in the meantime the affordances and constraints of advances in technology shape how this content is represented, controlled, and connected. Second, innovations in technologies are not nonpartisan as for its effects upon cognizance. Different advancements (or media) induce diverse mentalities or methods for considering. Each new innovation from the phone to the camera to the advanced PC has had its impacts on human cognition. For instance, the appearance of moveable sort and printing in the fifteenth century was trailed by a progression of emotional changes in all parts of social, cultural political and logical life. Finally, technological changes offer us new representations and dialects for contemplating human perception and our places on the planet. Viewing the heart as a pump or the cerebrum as a data handling machine is only one of the ways advances have given new viewpoints to understand wonders. These illustrative and figurative associations are not shallow. Considering the mind as much the same as a mud tablet, for instance, offers an altogether different perspective of perception and learning than thinking of it as like a data preparing machine. Having these similitudes and analogies as a major aspect of a general social cognizance impacts how advancements are appropriated for instructing and learning (Latour, 1990; Koehler, Yadav, Philips & Cavazos-Kottke, 2005; Mishra, Spiro & Feltovich, 1996).

1.4.6 PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE (PCK)

Shulman included that PCK is specific type of learning for showing which alludes to the transformation of topic information in to the relevant information for encouraging learners' understanding. This kind of information can be effortlessly utilized by the teacher to structure the content of the lesson, pick or create particular portrayals or analogies, to comprehend and suspect specific previously established inclinations or learning troubles of their students and so forth. It is the incorporation of educators' content learning and the appropriate method for showing that specific content in various settings. As it were, it is a blend of teaching method, learners, topic and the educational programs. Pedagogical Content Knowledge is seriously implanted in teacher's day by day schedule. Be that as it may,

Theoretical Knowledge is not its inverse by importance and nature. It envelops both hypothesis got the hang of amid teacher readiness and encounters picked up from progressing tutoring exercises. The principle issue with respect to PCK is its tendency or nature. The primary component incorporated into Shulman's unique idea of PCK incorporates information of topic, from one viewpoint, and comprehension of particular learning challenges and learners originations, on the other. He also supported that the more techniques educators have at their hand inside a positive subject area the better is the comprehension of learners in that space and thus more powerful will be the instructing learning condition. PCK manages Teacher Education all in all and Content information specifically (Shulman, 1986). Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) speaks to the mixing of content and teaching method into a comprehension of how specific parts of topic are sorted out, adjusted and spoken to for direction. Shulman contended that knowing about topic and general teaching procedures, however essential, yet were not adequate for catching the knowledge of good teachers. To portray the intricate courses in which the educator considers how specific content ought to be taught, he bolstered the "Pedagogical Content Knowledge" as the base that arrangements with the showing procedure, including the ways speaking to and figuring the subject that make it conceivable to others. In the event that teachers need to be fruitful, they would need to stand up to themselves with the two issues all the while, i.e. by exemplifying the 15 part of content most fitting to its showing capacity (Shulman, 1986). It is esteemed as an epistemological idea (Ball, 1996; Cochran, King and DeRuiter, 1993; Grossman, 1990; Ma, 1999; Shulman, 1987; Wilson, Shulman, and Richert, 1987). PCK gave a stage to teachers to consider the necessities and prerequisites in the range of educator training in a smaller manner. That basic information (PCK) is not only blend of two particular bodies-content and teaching method. It is, rather, those two groups of learning in addition to a third assortment of information which is made through the association of content and teaching method together. There are accordingly three collections of learning and they are not disengaged from each other. They associate and impact each other in ways that require an educator to consider them together, not independently.

Pedagogical Content Knowledge is a type of functional learning that is utilized by educators to direct their activities in exceptionally contextualized classroom settings. This type information involves, in addition to other things: (a) Knowledge of how to structure and speak to academic content for direct instructions to learners; (b) learning of the regular conceptions, misguided judgments, and challenges that learners experience when learning

specific content; and (c) information of the particular teaching methods that can be utilized to address learners' adapting needs specifically in classroom conditions.

With the progression of technology it is very hard to teach learners according to their standards. Keeping in mind the end goal to meet these objective, educators ought to have authority over the topic. The imaginative thoughts of learners ought to be associated over the fields and everyday life by the educators. These are the establishment stones of Pedagogical Content Knowledge. It is basic, nonetheless, that Pedagogical Content Knowledge be subject particular. It is the work of Mishra and Koehler (2006) on growing PCK to incorporate another area the utilization of technology to help instructing learning. The subsequent model, Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) adds promote intricacy to the way we consider teaching, learning and technology. It does that by including another information area (Technological Knowledge or TK) to the essential model and furthermore including extra intelligent connections between the distinctive core areas.

Shulman defined pedagogical content knowledge as teachers' interpretations and transformations of subject-matter knowledge in the context of facilitating student learning. He further proposed several key elements of pedagogical content knowledge:

- (i) Knowledge of representations of subject matter (content knowledge)
- (ii) Understanding of students' conceptions of the subject and the learning and teaching implications that were associated with the specific subject matter
- (iii) General pedagogical knowledge (or teaching strategies).

To complete what he called the knowledge base for teaching, he included other elements:

- (i) Curriculum knowledge
- (ii) Knowledge of educational contexts
- (iii) Knowledge of the purposes of education (Shulman, 1987).

The following paradigm clearly indicates the relationship and play between content knowledge and pedagogical knowledge.

Fig. -1.1 Pedagogical Content Knowledge

(Source: <http://www.tpck.org/tpck/index.php>)

Pedagogical content knowledge is deeply rooted in a teacher's everyday work. However, it is not opposite to theoretical knowledge. It encompasses both theory learned during teacher preparation as well as experiences gained from ongoing schooling activities. The development of pedagogical content knowledge is influenced by factors related to the teacher's personal background and by the context in which the teacher works. Pedagogical content knowledge is deeply rooted in the experiences and assets of students, their families and communities.

When teaching subject matter, teachers' actions will be determined to a large extent by the depth of their pedagogical content knowledge, making this an essential component of their ongoing learning. Pedagogical content knowledge research links knowledge on teaching with knowledge about learning, a powerful knowledge base on which to build teaching expertise.

1.4.7 TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE (TPACK)

As Shulman (1986) contended that teachers' knowledge for effective teaching requires the change of content into educational structures. What has been disregarded much of the time is the basic part that innovation or technology can play. For instance, Shulman composes that creating PCK expects educators to locate the most helpful types of portrayal of [the subject area's] thoughts, the most capable analogies, delineations, cases, clarifications, and demonstrates in a word, the methods for representing and planning the subject that make it understandable to others. It is fascinating to note here that each of the parts depicted by Shulman portrayals, analogies, cases, clarifications, and exhibitions are obliged, developed and characterized in basic courses by the affordances and limitations of the advanced technologies and non-computerized technologies used to detail and represent the educational programs based content. In one sense, there is no such thing as unadulterated content,

immaculate teaching method or unadulterated innovation. It is essential for teachers to understand the mind boggling way in which every one of the three of these areas and the settings in which they are consistently shaped exists together, co-constrain and co-create each other.

Each instructional circumstances in which teacher get them is unique. It is the after effect of inter weaving of these associated factors. In like manner, there is no single innovative technological arrangement that will work similarly well for each educator, each course or each teaching approach. Or maybe, an answer's prosperity lies in an educator's capacity to flexibly explore the spaces delimited by content, teaching method and innovation, and the mind boggling interactions among these components as they play out in particular instructional circumstances and settings. Educators need to create fluency in these three spaces as well as in the way in which they can be utilized intuitively with the goal that they can give the best and appropriate learning condition as could reasonably be expected (Shulman, 1987).

Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) is certainly a fruitful and skillful teaching with the assistance of innovation in technology. It is not quite the same as the knowledge of its individual components and their interactions. It rises up out of various associations among content, instructional method, innovation and contextual knowledge.

Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) is the knowledge of the utilization of innovation in different subjects and working on teaching strategies. This knowledge makes the learning of the subject for the understudy less demanding with proper instructional method and innovation (Koehler and Mishra, 2009; Schmidt et al., 2009). It is expected to go past techno anti-extremism to help educators in creative thinking. It will be conceivable with the act of TPACK and supportive in conveying another measurement to innovation for instructive purposes (Mishra, Koehler, Zellner and Kereluik, 2012).

TPACK is the base for effective teaching with innovation which incorporates an understanding of how to give ideas with innovation, how to utilize pedagogical procedures that utilize innovation in instructing the content in not a direct way, the knowledge of the concepts which make learning less demanding or harder, the learning of how the innovation will be useful for taking in, the learning of the learners' past information and the information of epistemological hypotheses, the knowledge of how to utilize innovation in building new information onto existing information and which likewise incorporates the advancement of new epistemologies, or reinforcing the old ones (Mishra and Koehler, 2006; Koehler et al., 2007; Koehler and Mishra, 2008; Mishra and Koehler, 2008; Harris et al., 2009; Koehler and

Mishra, 2009). The casing of the TPACK model requires that educators ought to build up a point by point, perplexing, familiar and adaptable learning of the considerable components, and educators should locate the suitable innovation and should know how and why to utilize this innovation in the teaching procedure and that they should hone the innovation (Koehler et al., 2011).

TPACK and the selection of educators influence in-class practices and understudy execution (Bos, 27 2011). Thus, TPACK is required information to empower educators to incorporate innovation in training (Kereluik et al., 2010). Keeping in mind the end goal to move from teaching innovation to utilizing innovation to improve teaching, educators ought to be set up to consider innovation to be an integral part of their day by day classroom exercises. The way prospective educators are set to interact with innovation can help to change their thinking about innovation and have the capacity to utilize it to help learners' learning. Beyerbach et al. (2001) and UNESCO (2008b) proposed diverse doses required by pre-service educators at the school with a specific end goal to build up the suitable skills for incorporating innovation, instructional method and content. On the off chance that these exercises are appropriately embraced in the educators training colleges, pre-service educators are probably going to build up the required Technological, Pedagogical & Content Knowledge and in this manner have the capacity to apply TPACK in their teaching. It is imperative for technological courses to be connected to methodological courses and field encounters to give the forthcoming educators a chance to witness firsthand how innovation can be successfully incorporated in their teaching (Polly, Mims, Shepherd and Inan, 2009).

1.5 NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Today's technology advancements, educational contexts should take advantage of innovative pedagogy and digital rich tools for deeper content exploration, ease of classroom management, engagement and motivation of students in learning contexts, and generally revolutionizing the learning spaces of old to meet the learning needs of today's students. It is logical to think that classrooms equipped with chalk and erasers, fixed rows of desks, and behavioral pedagogy would have yielded to changes caused by the technological advancements; however, despite the addition of digital tools, educational practices have changed little in the global context of educating youth.

Teachers in the 21st century must not only be familiar with the operation of instructional technologies but also with their application within the curriculum and their classroom (Eisenberg & Johnson, 1996). Technology's impact on the teaching and learning environment has changed not only the way our students process new concepts and achieve

learning objectives, but it has also modified the way in which instruction is delivered. Students' needs are diverse, and the forms of technology that they encounter in their learning environment may not fit those needs of every student or subject (Halverson, 2003). The educational technologies that a teacher may use in the teaching and learning environment may not adapt to every diverse need; rather, it is the job of the teacher to creatively apply these tools to meet the needs of the student.

The technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge (TPACK) framework is a conceptual model designed to rethink how a teacher might approach the integration of technology. Topper (2004) suggests that "for teachers to use technology in support of their teaching, and see it as a pedagogically useful tool, they must be confident and competent with the technology they are planning to use". Similarly, to the recommendations by Greenhow, Dexter and Hughes (2008), the TPACK framework helps the teacher to connect what is being taught to the way in which it is taught, with the technology used to enhance these connections. TPACK emphasizes "the connections among technologies, curriculum content, and specific pedagogical approaches, demonstrating a teachers' understanding of technology, pedagogy, and content that can interact with one another to produce effective discipline-based teaching with educational technologies" (Koehler & Mishra, 2008). By considering the impact that technology could have on the content and its delivery, a teacher might be able to overcome different factors faced and embrace new approaches to academic success.

So through this study, the investigator wants to find out the technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) among student teachers in Trichy district.

1.6 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Technology's impact on the teaching and learning environment has changed not only the way our students process new concepts and achieve learning objectives, but it has also modified the way in which instruction is delivered. Students' needs are diverse, and the forms of technology that they encounter in their learning environment may not fit those needs of every student or subject (Halverson, 2003). The educational technologies that a teacher may use in the teaching and learning environment may not adapt to every diverse need rather, it is the job of the teacher to creatively apply these tools to meet the needs of the student. Since the study deals with the effect of the selected demographic variables of student teachers and their technological pedagogical content knowledge, so the study is entitled as *Technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) among student teachers in Trichy District*.

1.7 OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS AND THE TERMS

1.7.1 Technological Knowledge (TK)

According to this study, Technological knowledge, not only referring to the use of a computer, server, or network, but it also refers to the technical equipment used in one's profession of study. This knowledge will come to mean the correct operation of computers, tablets, video recording devices, projectors, speakers, and other electronic devices that aid in the processing of information (Sahin, et al., 2013).

1.7.2 Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)

According to this study, Pedagogical knowledge means the frame of reference from which the instructor chooses to deliver the content knowledge in a variety of different ways. A skilled instructor will effectively choose which method of delivery is best suited for the students that they are instructing.

1.7.3 Content Knowledge (CK)

According to this study, Content knowledge will represent the depth of discipline specific knowledge, measured by the teacher's ability to pass a state certification exam.

1.7.4 Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK)

According to this study, Technological pedagogical knowledge as the ability to determine which technology would best fit the method of instruction. Possessing this type of knowledge will allow for the proper choice of technology to coincide with the selected instructional technique (Mishra & Koehler, 2006).

1.7.5 Technological Content Knowledge (TCK)

According to this study, technological content knowledge defined as the knowledge of technologies relative to specific content. For example, a science teacher would need to know how to operate a microscope or a centrifuge, while a math teacher would require the technical operation of a graphing calculator, protractor, or compass. The science or math teacher would possess the technical knowledge to operate a complex technology specific to their discipline (Mishra & Koehler, 2006).

1.7.6 Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK)

According to this study, Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) incorporates the understanding that gives the learning of both tough and simple subjects. It is the information of various teaching methods for various subjects (Koehler and Mishra, 2005).

1.7.7 Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK)

According to this study, Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) are a type of organizational framework for knowledge consisting of three major domains that support content-based technology integration.

1.7.8 Student Teachers

According to this study, Student teachers are the students who undergo pre-service training to teach in the secondary and higher secondary levels.

1.8 GENERAL OBJECTIVES

1. To find out the level of male and female student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.
2. To find out the level of married and unmarried student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.
3. To find out the level of undergraduate and postgraduate studied student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.
4. To find out the level of Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.
5. To find out the level of I year and II year studying student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.
6. To find out the level of rural and urban student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

1.9 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1. To find out whether there is any significant difference between male and female student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
2. To find out whether there is any significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
3. To find out whether there is any significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

4. To find out whether there is any significant difference between Tamil and English medium student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
5. To find out whether there is any significant difference between I year and II year studying student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
6. To find out whether there is any significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
7. To find out whether there is any significant difference between student teachers age group among 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
8. To find out whether there is any significant difference between student teachers studying among languages, arts and science subjects in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
9. To find out whether there is any significant association among student teachers parental education with regard to school education, undergraduate and postgraduates in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
10. To find out whether there is any significant association among student teachers parental occupation with regard to daily wages, private and government in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

1.10 NULL HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
2. There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
3. There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
4. There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
5. There is no significant difference between I year and II year studying student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
6. There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
7. There is no significant difference between student teachers age group among 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
8. There is no significant difference between student teachers studying among languages, arts and science subjects in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

9. There is no significant association among student teachers parental education with regard to school education, undergraduate and postgraduates in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
10. There is no significant association among student teachers parental occupation with regard to daily wages, private and government in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

1.11 DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The study is restricted to the student teachers in colleges of education affiliated to Tamil Nadu Teachers Education University in Tiruchirappalli district only.
2. Technological, pedagogical and content knowledge has been measured in terms of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological, pedagogical and content knowledge among student teachers.
3. Studies were not found related to technological, pedagogical and content knowledge among student teachers.
4. This study was limited to the teacher trainees of secondary education only.
5. Data were collected only from the teacher trainees of colleges of education.
6. The survey method was employed and the questionnaires were used to collect the data from the teacher trainees of seven education colleges.

1.12 CONCLUSION

This Chapter introduced the topic for the present study and explained the conceptual framework of the topic, “*Technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) among student teachers in Trichy District.*”

CHAPTER - II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1. INTRODUCTION

In this chapter, studies which are related to the problems are abstracted and their contribution to the field is presented. Significant writings of authorities in the area of the study are also reviewed. An attempt is made to show how the present investigation arose from contradictions or inadequacies of earlier investigations. Related literature is the foundation on which any future study can be found, which provides ideas, theories, explanations, hypotheses, method of research and other valuable information regarding the problem in hand.

J.C. Aggarwal (1966) says “study of related literature implies locations, reading and evaluating reports of research as well as reports of causal observation and opinion that are related to the individual’s planned research project.” Review of related studies helps the researcher to understand what is already known, what others have attempted to find out and what one can add to it. Thus it is a complete picture of the background of one’s study which is put together in step by step.

2.2. THE PURPOSES OF REVIEW

The reasons for review of related literature are:

1. To gain a background knowledge of the research topic.
2. To identify the concepts relating to it, potential relationships between them and to formulate researchable hypotheses.
3. To identify appropriate methodology, research design, methods of measuring concepts and techniques of analysis.
4. To identify data sources used by other researchers, and
5. To learn how others structured their reports.

2.3 STUDIES ON TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE

Ayla Cetin-Dindar et al., (2018) Development of pre-service chemistry teachers’ technological pedagogical content knowledge. The purpose of this study was to learn how to integrate simulations, animations, instructional games, data-logging, virtual labs and virtual field trips into chemistry instruction considering factors such as chemistry subjects and students’ possible alternative conceptions or their previous chemistry knowledge. A survey and interviews were used to gather data on the pre-service chemistry teachers’ TPACK framework both before and after the semester. A mixed between-within subject’s analysis of variance was conducted to

examine the differences in the pre-service teachers' TPACK at two time periods considering also the gender factor. For the qualitative data, deductive analysis based on existing codes and categories was applied. The quantitative and qualitative findings of this study revealed that the pre-service chemistry teachers' TPACK improved partially on some components. In addition, based on these findings, gender was not found to be a significant variable in technology integration. For further development in the TPACK framework, more context related technology applications in learning and teaching environment are needed.

Sumera Irum et al., (2018) University Teachers knowledge about technological devices and their use: An Analytical study. This study focused on the existing status of technology integration in universities through the lens of TPACK. The main objectives of the study were; to analyze the current status of technology used by Teacher Educators, in terms of frequently used devices and purpose to use technology. And explore the perceptions of Teacher Educators about the Technological Knowledge (TK) domains of TPACK in Teacher Education Institutions in the province of Sindh, Pakistan. The study was Survey. The questionnaire was used for data collection. The questions are adopted through literature. Thirty-Three (33) Teacher Educators were selected through census sampling technique. Data was analyzed through SPSS, percentage, mean, standard deviation and chi-square. The findings of the study revealed that most of the teacher educators were using a Laptop and Smart phone. Mostly Teacher Educators used technology for research, teaching-learning process, and communication. Majority of Teacher educators rated themselves low in Technological Knowledge. Only those teachers were possessed high Technological Knowledge those had degrees in technology related disciplines.

Somin Kim (2018) Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) and Beliefs of Preservice Secondary Mathematics Teachers: Examining the Relationships. The findings of this study suggest that preservice teachers with constructivist-oriented or student centered beliefs about the nature of mathematics, learning mathematics, and technology use displayed higher levels of mathematical knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge, and technological content knowledge, respectively, than preservice teachers with traditional or teacher-centered beliefs about mathematics, learning, and technology use.

Bas and Senturk (2018) an evaluation of technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) of in-service teachers: A study in Turkish public schools. In the current study, the technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) perceptions of Turkish in-service teachers working in public schools were investigated. The survey method was employed to investigate the in-service teachers' perceptions of TPACK in terms of some

demographic variables. The participants of the study consisted of volunteering in-service teachers (n = 200) from different public elementary and high schools. The results of the study indicated that the in-service teachers' TPACK perceptions were affected by their gender, occupational experience, educational level, teaching level, and taking educational computer and Internet use seminar variables. The results also revealed that the in-service teachers' perceptions of TPACK were at a moderate level. The results suggested that further efforts are required to develop the in-service teachers' TPACK perceptions in order to integrate ICTs into teaching and learning process effectively in the classroom.

Alhababi and Hamzah Hassan (2017) Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) Effectiveness on English Teachers and Students in Saudi Arabia. The purpose of this study was to integrate technology into technology-rich, English language learning classrooms in Saudi Arabia. Technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge (TPACK) framework was used to design activities of technology integration for teachers' and students' achievement and effectiveness. This study used a mixed-method of quantitative and qualitative to collect data. All participants were male teachers who taught English language courses in public Saudi Arabian schools. Participants were gender specific because the school system in Saudi Arabia separates males and females. The researcher, who was also male, had access to the male portion of the education system and, thus, interviewed and observed only teachers and students. Two research-developed pre- and post-surveys were administered to participants digitally. The researcher conducted observations and in-depth, recorded interviews with each teacher (n = 2). Also, an in-depth recorded interview was conducted with students (n = 2) for data analysis to provide depth to the student perspective collected. The results showed that TPACK framework is an effective tool for both teachers and students to enhance teaching and learning if it is well implemented and used. Teachers in this study showed interest for a better future of education with technology being well integrated and used in the curriculum. Implications of this study are clear that teachers will be more ready and productive with technology integration once technology is part of education laws and policy.

Lilla Adulyasas (2017) Measuring and factors influence mathematics teachers' technological pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK) in three southernmost provinces, Thailand. This study aimed to measure mathematics teachers' TPACK in three southernmost provinces, Thailand and to study on factors influencing their TPACK. A quantitative study was carried out with 210 secondary level mathematics teachers in the three southernmost

provinces, Thailand which was random by two stage sampling technique. Data were collected by using a questionnaire to identify the level of mathematics teachers' TPACK and the factors influencing their TPACK. Descriptive statistics, Pearson product moment correlation and multiple regression analysis were used for analyzing data. Findings reveal that the mean score of mathematics teachers' TPACK is 3.33 which are in the medium level and the three factors which have positive correlation at .05 level of significant with the level of TPACK are teaching experience factor, individual specialization factor and personal & organization factor. However, there are only two factors influencing mathematics teachers' TPACK. The two factors are individual specialization factor and personal & organization factors. These give better understanding on mathematics teachers' knowledge in integrating technology with the pedagogy and content which will be the important information for improving mathematics teachers' TPACK.

Fatih Saltan and Kursat Arslan (2017) A comparison of in-service and pre-service teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge self-confidence. This study aimed to investigate and compare in-service and pre-service teachers' self-confidence on technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) in relation to their teaching experience, expertise, technology usage, and gender. To achieve this goal, survey method was conducted as part of a quantitative method design. Participants of the study consisted of 388 pre-service and 211 in-service teachers from four different concentrations: science, mathematics, information, and communications technology (ICT) and classroom teachers. The data were analyzed using paired Sample T-test and MANOVA statistical analysis. Results showed that both pre-service and in-service participants exhibit the highest self-confidence level in the technological content knowledge domain. While pre-service teachers had the lowest score in TPACK, in-service teachers had the lowest score in the technological knowledge domain. While pre-service mathematics teachers have significantly lower TPACK than pre-service science teachers, in-service ICT teachers' TPACK level is significantly higher than science, math, and classroom teachers' levels considering TPACK, pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) and technology knowledge (TK) domains.

Can, B., Erokten, S., and Bahtiyar, A. (2017) An Investigation of Pre-Service Science Teachers' Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge. This study aimed to investigate the teacher training programmes related to pre-service science teachers' TPACK. This study was designed as a cross-sectional study. As a data collection tool, 7 subscales of "Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Scale of Pre-Service Teachers"; namely,

technology knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge, and technological pedagogical content knowledge were used. According to the results, as the class level of pre-service teacher increases, their level of technological pedagogical content knowledge increases as well. Moreover, there is a significant difference on behalf of pre-service teachers at the 1st grade in all dimensions of technological pedagogical content knowledge scale.

Ilhan Karatas et al., (2017) An Investigation of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge, Self-Confidence, and Perception of Pre-Service Middle School Mathematics Teachers towards Instructional Technologies. The purpose of this study is to investigate the technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK), TPACK related self-confidence, and perception of pre-service middle school mathematics teachers in terms of instructional technologies. In this study, TPACK Survey, TPACK Self-Confidence Survey, and TPACK Perception Survey were administered to 427 pre-service middle school mathematics teachers in elementary mathematics education program. The data were analyzed quantitatively. The data analysis revealed that there was a significant relationship between gender and perception towards technology. Moreover, it might be concluded that pre-service teachers improve their knowledge and self-confidence to use technology in elementary mathematics education programs. Lastly, considering the finding that there was a relationship between the use of technology and self-confidence towards the use of technology, it might be inferred that self-confidence of pre-service teachers towards the use of educational technologies increases with the use instructional tools.

Kwakye Apau and Stephen (2016) Technological pedagogical content knowledge preparedness of student teachers of the department of arts and social sciences education of University of Cape Coast. This study assesses the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) preparedness of student-teachers in the Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education (DASSE) of University of Cape Coast (UCC), Ghana. It uses the descriptive survey design. The stratified simple random sampling technique was used to sample 370 student-teachers of DASSE for the study. Questionnaire was adapted for the data collection. Descriptive (frequencies and percentages, mean of means and standard deviations) and inferential statistics (independent t-test) were used to analyses the data. The study reveals that the student-teachers in DASSE, UCC have Technological Knowledge. The study also found that the student-teachers of DASSE, UCC lack Technological Pedagogical Knowledge. In addition, the study has found that the student-teachers of DASSE, UCC lack Technological

Content Knowledge. Moreover, the study establishes that the student-teachers of DASSE, UCC lacked Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge. Lastly, there is no statistically significant difference between the gender of the student-teachers of DASSE, UCC and their TPACK preparedness.

Jang and Tsai (2016) highlighted the connection between self-control and academic performances. The reason for this paper was to look at pre-service educators' improvement of TPACK with fitting Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) utilizing Content Specific Technologies (CST). Pre-service educator's self-appraised their ICT-TPACK at two time focuses, and the empirical investigation showed critical distinction. The investigation of content knowledge demonstrated that pre-service educators utilized psychological control methodologies to build up 65 their comprehension and application abilities on ICT-TPACK and could utilize intelligent practices to show their understanding of TPACK toward the finish of the semester.

Anuar et al., (2016) led among the Art and Design Education students at Faculty of Education, University Technology MARA (UITM) to discover their availability to utilize e-Learning in Visual Art Education (VAE). The information was accumulated from 27 last year learners in the Art and Design Education program. The survey measured their Technological Knowledge (TK), Content Knowledge (CK) and Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK). The general discoveries on TK demonstrated that the learners can learn with innovation or technology effectively and have specialized aptitudes expected to utilize innovation in the teaching and learning of VAE. Lion's share of the educators concurred that they have adequate CK and could consider different methods for utilizing innovation to create comprehension of VAE. The discoveries in this examination plainly uncovered that TPACK is a decent stage to quantify educators' availability towards utilizing innovation in the teaching and learning of VAE.

Baran, Bilici and Uygun (2016) underscored on utilizing innovations or technology in science training, the need has developed to get ready science educators with powerful innovation or technology coordination abilities. To address this need, a TPACK-based PD program was planned and actualized as a component of preservice teacher preparing venture in Turkey. The investigation also uncovered that because of going to the PD, educators' TPACK expanded and supported over a time of one year. Research and viable ramifications for planning pre-service science educator preparing programs are shared.

Agyei and Voogt (2015) investigated the effect of techniques connected in a science teaching innovation course to develop innovation or technology mix capabilities, specifically

in the utilization of spreadsheets, in pre-service educators. In this regard, 104 pre-service arithmetic educators from an educator preparing program in Ghana selected in the science instructional innovation course for one semester. The preservice educators' innovation combination abilities were evaluated through examination of lesson designs and lesson perceptions, their self-detailed technological pedagogical content knowledge and mentalities towards innovation. Discoveries demonstrate that pre-service educators' innovation reconciliation skills enhanced after investment in the course. All procedures were viewed as vital, yet specifically, platform true innovation or technology encounters including input from showing attempt out made huge commitments to the pre-service educators' produced innovation joining skills.

Chien (2015) broke down 30 Taiwanese students' development and advancement of technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPCK) in English guideline in a dialect educator training program in a north-western college in Taiwan. Information included class extends, overviews, and meetings. This investigation has these discoveries. To begin with, the members ended up noticeably mindful of various sorts of media devices through the educator's exhibit and demonstrating and their own hands-on encounters and control. Their TPCK was produced and built through the assessment of sight and sound instruments, lesson designs and movement plans, gathering and class discourses, and individual reflections. Proposals with respect to course configuration on building up students' TPCK are given.

Hutchison and Colwell (2015) inspected preservice educators' utilization of the Technology Integration Planning Cycle (TIPC) to incorporate i-Pads into proficiency guideline. Investigation uncovered two discoveries identified with utilizing the TIPC to design direction: (a) Though the TIPC gives an organized way to deal with arranging that aides educators in utilizing their Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK), the preservice educators still utilized a techno-driven way to deal with arranging guideline and did not completely participate in all components of the arranging cycle; (2) even with the organized arranging approach, preservice educators experienced issues adjusting their lesson content with the instructional objectives of the lesson; and (3) preservice educators depend on suggestions from their college classes while choosing applications to use in direction, instead of freely searching out resources.

Juniu et al., (2015) inspected pre-service Physical Education educators' convictions about and execution of innovation or technology in their classes with an end goal to evaluate which techniques for direction about innovation may give the best learning. The information examinations uncovered that there is a critical

relationship between the measure of TPACK pre-service educators saw having, and the innovation that physical PETE staff demonstrated including different strategies for execution.

Yelken et al., (2015) proposed blend strategy plan for the investigation. The subjective and quantitative information were acquired through technological pedagogical content knowledge and open-ended figurative inquiry as pre-and post-tests. In quantitative and subjective information investigation, t-test for the needy specimens and inductive substance examination were directed. The discoveries exhibited the planned pre-teachers' computerized story readiness expanded their self-assurance on TPACK. Information investigation comes about showed computerized story readiness had beneficial outcome on the forthcoming pre-service teachers' TPACK.

Alqallaf and Williams (2015) understood the significance of innovation or technology to advance the improvement in exchanging content learning. Hence, the motivation behind this investigation is to analyze educators' recognition about their capacity to viably incorporate advanced white board innovation in basic classroom in state funded school under the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK). The members of this investigation were 71 educators from government funded schools in Colorado. The investigation outcomes shown that there was no connections between educators' socioeconomics (i.e., sexual orientation, age, and showing background) with educators' TPACK recognitions.

Abdulaziz Ali Alzahrani (2014) The Effects of Instructors' Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (Tpack) on Online Courses. This study examined the current status of instructors' technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge (TPACK) in online courses at King Abdulaziz University in order to provide practical suggestions to improve the quality of online education in Saudi Arabia. Examining the relationship between instructors' TPACK and students' TPACK perceptions is important for getting a clear view of both of these important aspects of the educational process. The participants of this study were 46 online instructors and 618 students at King Abdulaziz University. This research is quantitative and an online survey was used to collect the data. The results of this study revealed that there was a significant negative correlation between the seven components of the instructors' TPACK and their ages in TPK and TPACK. Additionally, it was also found that there was no significant correlation between the seven components of the instructors' TPACK and their online teaching experience, nor any significant differences between the seven components of the instructors' TPACK and their colleges. It was also seen from the results that PCK was the only significant contributor to the instructors' TPACK. No

significant correlations were found between the seven components of instructors' TPACK and students' TPACK perceptions and their attitudes.

Blackburn (2014) utilized blended strategy for examine on internet learning is an investigation into the online instructional personnel's information of coordinated Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK). A subjective strategy took after with one-on-one meetings of nine chose teachers showing high TPACK parts. Empirical researches of the investigation show that there is high innovation, content, teaching method, and technological content knowledge among the school level showing staff inside the xi school contemplated. Subjective discoveries of the investigation show that the school level showing workforce educators are occupied with high effect hones with their online learners that exhibit their TPACK abilities and that the school level showing personnel utilize their TPK to evaluate consideration of new advancements devices in the online classroom.

Cengiz (2014) utilized a pre-/post-test plan without a control amasses in the examination. Members were third-year learners ($n = 42$) who have finished the Turkish adaptation of TPACK, TISE, and ITOE previously, then after the fact this 12-week mediation. The data were fundamentally investigated through unmistakable and combined specimen t-test measurements ($p < .05$). Graphic results demonstrated an expansion in all subscales of TPACK, TISE, and ITOE scores. The matched example t tests uncovered a critical distinction in scores for content learning instructive information, innovative educational learning, general TPACK and ITOE. In any case, no critical contrast in Technological Knowledge, TPACK, and TISE scores was watched. Taking everything into account, the mediation was compelling for deciding and creating TPACK factors and ITOE in preservice physical instruction educators.

Chang, Tsai and Jang (2014) utilized ICT and their TPACK in science instructing. Eight hundred and six optional science educators from Taiwan and 164 educators from Shaanxi took an interest in the investigation. The investigative outcomes demonstrated that media was the most utilized ICT in Taiwan, trailed by PowerPoint (PPT), Internet stages, and intelligent whiteboards (IWBs). In Shaanxi, PPT was the most utilized ICT announced by science educators, trailed by multimedia, IWBs, and Internet stages. The discoveries showed that in Taiwan, science educators' TPACK was measurably critical in connection to various sorts of ICT, though in Shaanxi, science educators' TPACK did not exhibit huge distinction. In Taiwan, science educators who announced their most utilized ICT to be multimedia were found to demonstrate critical contrasts in TPACK as indicated by sexual orientation and educating background. In Shaanxi, science educators who revealed their most utilized ICT to

be PPT did not demonstrate any huge contrast on TPACK by sex; in any case, they indicated critical contrasts on TPACK with respect to educating knowledge.

Chai et al., (2014) studied three hundred and ninety pre-administration and three hundred and ninety four in-service teacher educators as to the seven components of technological pedagogical content knowledge, their convictions about constructivist oriented teaching (CB) and design disposition (DD). Both exploratory and corroborative factor examinations demonstrated that the review in view of the nine-factor model had high reliability and validity. Critical contrasts between pre-service and in-service educators in the TPACK components and CB and DD were found and the distinctions uncover that the pre-service educators are less learned and less certain with respect to every one of the variables. With a specific end goal to recognize indicators of TPACK, the exploration additionally investigates the connections among TPACK components, CB and DD through auxiliary condition models. The discoveries uncover that DD reliably predicts both pre-service and in-service educators' TPACK and this offers help about the significance of plan attitude for TPACK headway. In any case, CB does not foresee the pre-benefit educators' TPACK. Also, CB is an essentially negative indicator for the in-benefit educators' TPACK.

Fanni (2014) enlightened the pretended by years of showing knowledge, proficient improvement with innovation, age, sexual orientation, ethnicity, and school level in the advancement of educator self-viability for TPACK. On one hand, experienced educators answered to have less trust in innovation or technology utilize. Then again, educators who got broad/direct proficient improvement with innovation revealed larger amounts of viability for TPACK. The part of educator preparing in innovation utilize rose to be fundamental in expanding their TPACK. No huge contrasts were recognized in TPACK as capacity of sexual orientation, ethnicity, and school level. At last, this exploration affirms the part of TPACK in anticipating educators' utilization of innovation. Results demonstrate that TPACK emphatically predicts educators' innovation or technology utilization. These discoveries shed all the more light on the pretended by educators' TPACK in the innovation incorporation prepare, as one of the critical markers of educators' innovation utilize.

Gravel (2014) utilized blended strategies for information gathering study that investigated the impacts of an expert advancement course lined up with the TPACK system on pre-kindergarten through twelfth grade in-service employees. This investigation used a pre/present overview organization on measure the development of employees' innovation incorporation information, upheld by criticism from the employees gathered in amid a concentration amass reflection meeting. Units of study were characterized inside the courses

syllabus, and were supplemented as important to help the necessities of the employees. The discoveries showed that there was a huge distinction between the mean pre-test and post-test scores for the TK, CK, TCK, TPK, and TPACK regions, recognizing that the employee's innovation reconciliation learning expanded because of their cooperation in the course. The proof additionally demonstrated that the structure of the course, advancement of an expert learning group, and improvement of a profound comprehension of innovation devices prompted the development of learners.

Kaalberg (2014) offered the chance to connect with members with computerized media, i.e., iPads, as a piece of perusing and composing guideline. This different contextual analysis highlights the encounters of those included with the course: two educators, 18 educator competitors, and the 18 rudimentary tutees who got proficiency mentoring. Information gathering included numerous contextual investigation philosophies and comprised of meetings, communitarian talks, perception and field notes, relics, and studies. Data based research included open coding and pivotal coding, using extra logical devices, and drawing from a TPACK content investigation. Classifications were built and assembled together to shape develops. The discoveries demonstrate course educators and educator hopefully coordinating technological, educational, and content information as they found out about and with i-Pads in a strong domain that empowered their learning. Educator hopefuls used advanced media with their proficiency direction as they gave tutees chances to draw in with an assortment of education.

Koh et al., (2014) explored 201 Singaporean educators' impression of their technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK), lesson configuration practices, and plan auras through a review instrument. Examination of these develops uncover critical factors impacting educators' view of TPACK which have not yet been investigated. The after effects of this examination demonstrate that to upgrade educators' TPACK recognitions, educator educators need to enable educators to create lesson configuration rehearses that help innovation ideation and cycle. Going past TPACK, understandings of educators' lesson configuration practices and plan airs are imperative for teachers to better outline proficient improvement for mix of data and interchanges innovation.

Koh, Chai and Tay (2014) portrayed TPACK in real life, a structure that can be utilized to envision the transaction amongst TPACK and four relevant elements that impact educators' plan of ICT lessons. This was utilized to investigate the lesson outline discourses of 24 teachers from a Singapore elementary school who were instructing the levels of Primary 1, 4, and 5. Content investigation and Chi-square examination was utilized. The

group encouraged by an accomplished instructive technologist additionally showed higher events of TPACK. These outcomes recommend that for ICT development to be viable, the synthesis of configuration groups should be painstakingly considered. Educators additionally need to create capabilities to encourage and talk about plan with the end goal that logical concerns can be transformed into chances to help academic change.

Kopcha and Leftwich (2014) inspected the TPACK information and execution of 27 early adolescence and basic instruction preservice educators in the wake of participating in a semester-long course on innovation incorporation or technology incorporation. TPACK learning and execution was measured as their execution on circumstance particular lesson designs. The course was novel in that a key instructional procedure was to present utilization of defense based figuring out how to connect with preservice educators in basic leadership about innovation mix under classroom-particular contemplations and requirements. Analyzing preservice educators' TPACK under case-based learning can illuminate the way in which innovation combination courses are created to upgrade TPACK and preservice educators figure out how to incorporate innovation into their lessons.

Lee and Kim (2014) utilized a TPACK-based instructional model with fifteen members from various majors. Information included individual members' composed materials and TPACK overview reactions, gather lesson designs, and the analysts' field notes. The information examination uncovered that: (1) the experienced members have issues in understanding Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), which impeded their learning of incorporated learning of TPACK and (2) their learning of TPACK was the blend instead of the combination of Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), Technological Knowledge (TK), and Content Knowledge (CK).

Lu (2014) discovered Learning by Design for Preservice Teacher Technology Preparation: How Effective Is It and in What Ways, the specialist inspected whether a LBD situation is powerful in helping preservice educators creates TPACK. The members for the most part concurred that LBD was useful for them to find out about educating with innovation or technology. They felt more alright with and positive about utilizing innovation in their teaching. Additionally utilizing Live Dual Modeling to Help Preservice Teachers Develop TPACK, the specialist explored whether a Live Dual Modeling system in the LBD condition was successful in helping preservice educators to create TPACK and what conditions impacted the utilization of this methodology. The discoveries demonstrated that preservice educators showed the underlying capacity to exchange what they realized in the displaying to true classroom educating. At the point when Live Dual Modeling is utilized,

consideration ought to be paid to the conditions that impact the efficacy of the procedure because of preservice educators' restrictions in their general information base, functional experience, and capacity to exchange figuring out how to different settings.

Magen-Nagar and Ungar (2014) looked at ICT educators who teach at both the areas and the school level and inspect the Program Information Communication Technology Knowledge (PICTK) and Technology Pedagogy and Content Knowledge (TPACK) intensity on the ICT educators' feeling of strengthening for encouraging the usage of ICT in the schools. One hundred and twenty one ICT educators took part in the exploration. The primary outcomes demonstrate that PICTK learning has a critical constructive outcome on TPACK information among the "region ICT educators", though there was no change among the "locale school ICT teachers". The outcomes also demonstrate that PICTK and TPACK information does not really advance the educational ICT learning of the ICT educator, yet is basic for his or her feeling of strengthening. It is consequently prescribed to proceed with the help for all ICT educators, and to grow their own insight about the developing ICT program.

Matas (2014) distinguished how educators can change teaching and learning by incorporating 21st century computerized innovation. Educator activity examine was utilized to research the effect of advanced training on teaching and learning. The investigation was directed in a rural Jewish day school in the Northeast, in the educator specialist's seventh and eighth grade sociology classes. Two studies and one meeting were led to triangulate the information gathered from looking at understudy work and the educator's reflexive diary. The discoveries from the investigation propose: (an) understudy inspiration can prompt further understudy engagement; (b) advanced activities can speak to a 'high water stamp' of understudy learning; (c) the educator's Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) is fundamentally imperative and impacted by innovation and (d) innovation can possibly add to constructivist learning condition.

Owusu (2014) uncovered that New Zealand's secondary school science educators as a rule had a high impression of their understanding of TPACK and its related develops. Science educators had high mean scores on every one of the develops on a five-point Likert scale with the exception of technological knowledge. There is therefore a sign that science educators in New Zealand saw themselves as having the capacity to instruct with innovation adequately. Correlation researches uncovered that each of the six builds related fundamentally with TPACK (likewise alluded to as TPCK). Numerous and stepwise relapse investigations uncovered that Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK) and Technological Content

Knowledge (TCK) made measurably huge novel commitments to Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK).

Pirttimaa et al., (2014) introduced a contextual analysis about utilizing a blog as an apparatus supporting and reflecting educators work on concerning the advancement of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) of educator in-service course members. The individual sites served a media for the course members to help, reflect, and share their work and learning. As indicated by the examination, utilizing instructive blogging turns out to be more important and more target-orientated amid habituation of utilizing the blog. Blogging turned out to be a helpful strategy for portraying make forms, observing the procedures of others, and creating thoughts for make items.

Rahmany, Sadeghi, and Chegini, (2014) examined the impact of innovation reconciliation all in all and standardization of CALL specifically on Iranian educators' technological, pedagogical and content learning (TPACK). It additionally looks at educators' difficulties with standardization of CALL. In such manner, 16 educators instructed a course with the objective to incorporate PC innovation completely. The specialists executed a TPACK poll prior and then afterward the course and a semi-organized meeting after the course. Perceptions likewise helped the researchers to pick up a correlative comprehension of the procedure of CALL standardization and how educators manage their new parts. The outcomes uncovered that innovation or technology related information areas of TPACK grew altogether. The outcomes additionally demonstrated that Iranian instructive society is exceedingly delicate to instructional innovation and its utilization in training.

Yasar Kazu et al., (2014). Teachers' Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Self-Efficacies. The aim of this study was to determine teachers' views on technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK), their self-efficacy, and whether these views changed according to sex, age, period of service, faculty graduated from, branch, access to the internet, the use of technology level, and access to in-service training which is oriented to the use of technology. Teachers' self-efficacies which are oriented to TPACK and its sub-dimensions known as technological knowledge (TK), content knowledge (CK), pedagogical knowledge (PK), pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), technological content knowledge (TCK) and technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK) were determined to be at a high level. According to this study, teachers' self-efficacy perceptions on TK, CK, PCK, TCK and TPACK did not change according to sex while the self-efficacy perceptions on PK and TPK changed according to sex. It was concluded that the self-efficacy perceptions of female teachers in these dimensions were higher when compared to those of male teachers.

According to the present study, teachers' self-efficacy at TK and PCK changed according to age and the period of service, while self-efficacy at CK, PK, TCK, TPK and TPACK did not change according to these variables. In addition, a significant difference was determined between teachers' self-efficacy perceptions on TK and TPK according to the faculty graduated from. It was detected that the self-efficacy levels of classroom teachers on CK, TPACK, PCK and TCK were higher when compared with those of branch teachers. It was also concluded from this study that teachers' self-efficacy perception of TPACK did not change according to the situation of access to internet in the school in which they held office and that their efficacy was adequate. Teachers who thought that their self-efficacy in the use of internet was sufficient had higher levels of self-efficacies in TK, TCK, TPK and TPACK compared with other teachers. According to the present study, the in-service training that teachers receive on how to use the internet has more positive effects on CK and PCK compared with their self-efficacy in other dimensions.

Kristi Nicole Garrett (2014) A Quantitative study of Higher Education Faculty Self-Assessments of Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (Tpack) and Technology Training. This study assessed the perception of the technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge (TPACK) of faculty at a southeastern research university using the researcher developed HE-TPACK instrument (n = 128). HE-TPACK is a valid and reliable revision of the original TPACK instrument that allows the measurement of higher education faculty TPACK. The research described faculty perceptions on each of the eight HE-TPACK domains and determined whether there was a difference in HE-TPACK based on discipline type, gender and academic ranking of the faculty. Descriptive statistics revealed that a majority of all participating faculty agreed with the statements in six domains (technology training, pedagogy knowledge (PK), pedagogy content knowledge (PCK), technological pedagogical knowledge iii (TPK), technological content knowledge (TCK), and technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge (TPACK)) and strongly agreed with statements in two domains (technology knowledge (TK) and content knowledge domains (CK)). This finding indicates that faculty perceive they are knowledgeable in seven HE-TPACK domains and that they believe technology training is important. A multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to identify differences in HETPACK due to educational discipline types, gender and academic rank. Based on academic rank, results revealed significant differences in the pedagogical knowledge (PK), content knowledge (CK), pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), and the technological, pedagogical, content

knowledge (TPACK) domains. There were no differences based on gender and educational discipline types.

Wetzel et al., (2014) depicted the execution of a program to inject innovation when all is said in done strategies courses as a necessity of an educator arrangement program. Results uncovered victories and situations of implanting innovation into the courses. Competitors capably depicted forthcoming utilization of components of the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) display (Mishra and Koehler, 2006), however were less sure of their capacity to create and execute content-based lessons to meet substance and innovation guidelines.

Campbell and Dobozy (2013) examined two regions that are developing as pioneers in the field; in particular Learning Design and Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge, which is additionally alluded to as TPACK. By investigating these two zones it is conceivable to translate where the two territories cross and to advance the writing on the two regions. Learning Design is a sub-field of eLearning, while TPACK has picked up a lot of cash subsequent to being created by Mishra and Koehler (2006) prior this century. This paper exhibits that by utilizing these two systems together it takes into account a more grounded epistemological establishment and better plan for teaching.

Iryanti, Hindersah, and Priyana (2013) decided the fusion of components of teaching method, content and innovation structure that joins such components called TPACK system which is then spoken to in a visual intelligent video innovation that likewise utilizes the idea of advanced narrating. The assessment demonstrates that the evaluators enjoyed the intuitive signal video execution, assessment of a few criteria; the base rate is 61% and greatest 97%. Visual portrayal of a client can be seen more video than simply utilizing content/picture which achieved 97%, while for the change is should have been done on the utilization of innovation integration (61%) and conveyance of the message sent in the video (69%).

Sancar-Tokmak, Yelken and Konokman (2013) researched an improvement of pre-service educators in their Instructional Material Design (IMD) abilities through the course Instructional Technology and Material Design, which depends on a technological, pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK) system. A sum of 22 Elementary Education pre-service educators took an interest in the investigation. Five exercises in view of TPACK were composed by the educators to furnish learners with particular instructing background. Activity explore technique was taken after amid the investigation. The investigation uncovered that pre-service educator increased basic abilities in instructional material outline.

In addition, the outcomes demonstrated that they encountered fusing TPACK into their future educating rehearses.

Blonder, R (2013) gave an innovative stage to clients' substance: making and sharing transferred content by the clients themselves. Web 2.0 gives an abnormal state of action and advances participation among its clients. This adds to making new social associations, sharing human encounters, and making new information. As it were, educators need adequate Technological, Pedagogical & Content Knowledge (TPACK) and technological teaching self-efficacy. They investigated the adjustment in the aptitudes, educators' TPACK, and self-efficacy convictions of science educators in regards to video altering and utilizing YouTube recordings in secondary school science lessons, because of an expert advancement program that concentrated on altering YouTube recordings and the going with instructing teaching method.

Govender and Govender (2013) investigated a conceivable connection between educators' self-efficacy convictions relating to their own level of capability and their states of mind towards innovation appropriation. Surveys were utilized to decide educators' view of their ability and elements that identify with their dispositions. Their reactions were examined utilizing a measurable bundle (SPSS) and social intellectual hypothesis was utilized as a system to clarify human learning regarding inspiration, behavioural and natural elements. A few ramifications for proficient improvement programs are then recommended. This paper decided the view of educators as for mentality towards ICT, characteristics of PCs and their competency levels of utilizing PCs. These observations were appeared to relate emphatically to teacher's self-efficacy convictions. They recommended that the projects for educators and pre-service educators need to change so as to fuse ICT into the teaching, since educators' view of the relative preferred standpoint and similarity of ICT were emphatically connected to teachers' demeanors and efficacy convictions towards PCs. This could be utilized as a spring board to build their self-efficacy about ICT and subsequently embrace ICT in teaching and learning.

Mishne (2012) analyzed whether educator self-efficacy, educator learning, and showing background impact levels of innovation incorporation in the classroom. In view of the current writing on the subject of educator combination of technology into classroom direction, the examination guessed that these variables would assume a huge part in anticipating innovation utilize. The information were broke down utilizing clear measurements, a correlational framework, and progressive relapse. There were 44 usable reviews (N=44). This investigation yielded blended outcomes. While innovation learning was

turned out to be a noteworthy indicator of general innovation using capability, educator self-efficacy and educating background. Technological, Pedagogical & Content Knowledge (TPACK) factors were reliably a measurably critical indicator of each of the three ward factors. The higher the educators' TPACK scores, the more innovation they utilize and they were accounted for to have more educator self-viability.

Tantrarungroj and Suwannatthachote (2012) explored pre-service educators' self-efficacy in planning advanced media and their Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPCK) for outlining computerized media utilizing distinctive types of self-managed learning instructional help for online venture based learning. The investigation utilized a 2×2 factorial research outline. The specimen comprised of 232 pre-service educators from a foundation arranged in Bangkok, Thailand. The four unique types of self-managed learning instructional help for online venture based learning were PB + SQ + PA, PB + SQ just, PB + PA just, and PB as it were. Two-way Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) was utilized for information examination. The outcomes demonstrated critical contrasts in preservice educators' self-efficacy and TPCK post-test scores. No principle impact was found between two diverse self-controlled learning techniques (SQ and PA) upon the methods for self-efficacy in planning advanced media scores and TPCK scores. The self-controlled learning systems (SQ and PA) had a measurably critical association upon the methods for self-efficacy in outlining computerized media scores while the self-directed learning methodologies (SQ and PA) had no cooperation upon the methods for the TPCK scores.

William I. Bauer (2012) Acquisition of Musical Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge. The purposes of this study were to (a) develop and administer an instrument to measure music educators' TPACK, (b) examine how music teachers acquire their TPACK, and (c) determine if a relationship existed between those teachers' TPACK and their reported integration of technology. Participants (N = 284) were music teachers who completed two questionnaires, one designed to measure their TPACK (Musical TPACK Questionnaire [MTPACK-Q]) and another to describe the level of technology integration in their classroom (Concerns-Based Adoption Model–Levels of Use [CBAM-LoU] instrument). Scores on the technology-related domains of the TPACK model were lower than content, pedagogical, or pedagogical content domains. A moderate, significant, positive correlation ($r = .51, p \leq .01$) was found between the participants' MTPACK-Q score and the level of technology integration in their classroom as reported by the CBAM-LoU.

Haley-Mize (2012) utilized a semi exploratory, pre/present test configuration on assess three diverse course encounters on preservice teachers' level of TPACK. Results demonstrated that applicants who took an interest in course plan that expressly displayed innovation mix, made a computerized space to broaden the group of training, tested members to make cooperative arrangements utilizing Web 2.0 stages, and incorporated substance on Universal Design for Learning indicated critical increments in Pedagogical Knowledge, Pedagogical Content Knowledge, Technological Content Knowledge, Pedagogical Technological Knowledge, and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge when post-test scores were contrasted to pre-test scores. Multivariate investigation of fluctuation between bunches on each of the six TPACK subscales explored in this examination demonstrated that this gathering additionally indicated altogether higher picks up in TPACK when contrasted with a completely online gathering and personal without innovation upgraded learning on Pedagogical Content Knowledge, Technological Content Knowledge, and Technological Pedagogical Knowledge.

Ya-Huei Wang et al., (2011) conducted a study on post structural feminist pedagogy in English instruction of vocational-and-technical education. The research results showed that the post structural feminist pedagogy had a positive effect upon the participants in the experimental group. First, in the English language achievement post-test, the participants receiving the post structural feminist instruction significantly outperformed those receiving the traditional banking instruction in terms of listening, vocabulary, grammar, and reading. Second, in the critical thinking ability post-test, the participants significantly outperformed those receiving the traditional banking instruction in terms of length, focus, content, organization, and style. Third, in regard to the students' satisfaction, it was clearly shown that the students who received the instruction informed by post structural feminist pedagogy expressed significantly greater satisfaction than those who had received traditional banking instruction in terms of instructional objective, teaching method/materials, teacher quality, class environment, and assessment.

Liaw H. (2010) involved a subjective contextual investigation on the conversion of innovation and social examinations in cultivating a constructivist training. Through the examination of pre-service social investigations educators' understanding of the online primary source & resources (OPSR), three subjects developed. Suggestions show that initially, foundational academic speculations are basic as to innovation incorporation in instruction and in that capacity educator readiness programs must not expect what is instructed is what is found out; second, occasions of more profound comprehension among

pre-service educators just showed up amid the use of their hypothetical understandings; third, setting is basic in how OPSR would be utilized as a part of classrooms and such relevant issues must not be disregarded by educator planning projects; and fourth, educators' technological pedagogical content knowledge (PCK/TPCK) is basic in the joining of innovation in training.

Asli Ozgun-koca et al., (2010) conducted a study on preservice teachers' emerging TPACK in a technology-rich methods class. The results indicated that the participants' understanding of technology shifted from viewing technology as a tool for reinforcement into viewing technology as a tool for developing student understanding. The preservice teacher TPACK development was closely related to a shift in identity from learners of mathematics to teachers of mathematics. In a class where advanced digital technologies were used extensively as a catalyst for promoting inquiry-based learning, preservice teachers retained a great deal of skepticism about the appropriateness of using technology in concept development roles, despite their confidence that they can incorporate technology into their future teaching.

Athanassios Jimoyiannis (2010) conducted a study on designing and implementing an integrated technological pedagogical science knowledge framework for science teachers' professional development. The result showed the need to expand TPACK by incorporating a fourth dimension, the Educational Context within Pedagogy, Content and Technology mutually interact, in order to address future policy models concerning teacher preparation to integrate ICT in education.

Bracha Kramarski and Tova Michalsky (2010) conducted a study on preparing preservice teachers for self-regulated learning in the context of Technological Pedagogical Content knowledge. The results showed that exposure to metacognitive support using the self-questioning method might enhanced preservice teachers' ability to reflect on and regulate their learning processes. This, in turn, could develop their TPCK, both as learners (comprehension skills) and as teachers (design skills). Further analysis indicated high correlations within SRL measures (self-reports, online reflections) and between SRL and TPCK tasks. Implications were discussed for teacher training in SRL-integrated TPCK contexts.

David Kanter and Spyros Konstantopoulos (2010) conducted a study on the impact of a project-based science curriculum on Minority Student Achievement, Attitudes, and Careers: The Effects of Teacher Content and Pedagogical Content Knowledge and inquiry-based Practices. The study found in sum, the extent of the success of a Project Based Science

(PBS) curriculum with students from groups underrepresented in science careers appeared to be dependent on elements of both teacher knowledge (CK and PCK) and teachers' frequency of use of inquiry-based activities that were consistent with culturally relevant pedagogical practices.

Fred Korthagen (2010) conducted a study on how teacher education can make a difference. The study led to significant conclusions about the need for careful programme design based on: (i) an elaborated view of the intended process of teacher learning; (ii) specific pedagogical approaches and (iii) an investment in the quality of staff members. The conclusions and implications were put into an international perspective.

Jurgen Baumert et al. (2010) conducted a study on teachers' mathematical knowledge, cognitive activation in the classroom, and student progress. Teachers' pedagogical content knowledge was theoretically and empirically distinguishable from their content knowledge. Multilevel structural equation models revealed a substantial positive effect of pedagogical content knowledge on students' learning gains that was mediated by the provision of cognitive activation and individual learning support.

Nance Wilson and Haiyan Bai (2010) conducted a study on the relationships and impact of teachers' metacognitive knowledge and pedagogical understandings of metacognition. The data analysis results using mixed research method suggested that the participant's metacognitive knowledge had a significant impact on his/her pedagogical understanding of metacognition. The results revealed that teachers who had a rich understanding of metacognition report that teaching students to be metacognitive required a complex understanding of both the concept of metacognition and metacognitive thinking strategies.

Syh-Jong Jang and Kuan-Chung Chen (2010) conducted a study on developing a transformative model for pre-service science teachers: From PCK to TPACK. This study expanded four views, namely, the comprehensive, imitative, transformative and integrative views to explore the impact of TPACK. The model could help pre-service teachers develop technological pedagogical methods and strategies of integrating subject-matter knowledge into science lessons, and further enhanced their TPACK.

Arif Yilmaz et al., (2010) conducted a study on comparing Mathematical Pedagogical Content Knowledge of In-Service and Pre-Service Early Childhood Education Teachers. The result of the study revealed that the first year pre-service teachers had higher level of mathematical Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) in comparison to first year pre-service and experienced in-service teachers. The results of the study provided valuable

feedback for developing and improving undergraduate level courses and professional development programs for teaching mathematics to young children.

Roberta Hunter (2010) conducted a study on changing roles and identities in the construction of a community of mathematical inquiry. The findings illustrated the interconnections between the teacher's beliefs, past experiences, and current, and future expectations for her diverse students. Explanations were provided of how different, often conflicting, voices emerged including one that drew on the teacher's cultural knowledge. This provided many learning opportunities for the researcher as the teacher developed her students' voices in culturally appropriate ways.

Muammer Calik, Ali Kolomuc and Zafer Karagolge (2010) conducted a study on the effect of conceptual change pedagogy on students' conceptions of rate of reaction. The results suggested that the teaching intervention helped the students to overcome their alternative conceptions and to store their newly structured knowledge in their long-term memories. It was suggested that combining different conceptual change methods such conceptual change text/refutation text, argumentation with the intervention used here might be more effective in reducing student alternative conceptions.

Leanna Archambault and Joshua Barnett (2010) conducted a study on Revisiting Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge: Exploring the TPACK. This study examined the nature of technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) through the use of a factor analysis. Three major factors became evident, but rather than being comprised of pedagogy, content, and technology, the only clear domain that distinguished itself was that of technology. This research suggested that measuring each of these domains was complicated and convoluted, potentially due to the notion that they were not separate.

William S. Davidson et al., (2010) conducted a study on student experiences of the adolescent diversion project: A community-based exemplar in the pedagogy of service-learning. This study highlighted that why service-learning opportunities for students were not just one way to teach students, they were opportunities to bridge relationships within communities, bring life to theoretical concepts, and build the foundations necessary for educated citizens that would one day take lead roles in our society.

Anat Oster-levinz and Aviva Klieger (2010) conducted a study on indicator for Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) evaluation of online tasks. It was found that teachers could use this indicator for evaluating the quality of the tasks that were developed as well as to test the improvement that took place in their tasks over time.

Yanping Fang (2010) conducted a study on the cultural pedagogy of errors: Teacher Wang's homework practice in teaching Geometric proofs. The findings of the study raised important questions about what teaching entailed, and how to organize teachers' work so that teacher learning occurred in the process of fostering student learning. This required a reconceptualization of homework to capitalize on its pedagogical potentials.

Singaravelu (2010) conducted a study on multimedia assisted teaching in pedagogical technique. The findings of the study revealed that the multimedia assisted teaching in the pedagogy enhanced the achievement. It was proved by the gain scores.

Min-Hsien Lee and Chin-Chung Tsai (2010) conducted a study on exploring teachers' perceived self-efficacy and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge with respect to educational use of the World Wide Web. The results indicated a lack of general knowledge about Web-related pedagogy amongst the teachers surveyed. Correlations were found between self-efficacy and positive attitudes to web-based instruction. Older and more experienced teachers were found to have lower levels of self-efficacy with respect to TPCK-W, though teachers with more experience of using the web (including for instruction) had higher levels of self-efficacy with respect to TPCK-W.

Visvanathan Naicker (2010) conducted a study on educator's pedagogy influencing the effective use of computers for teaching purposes in classrooms. The analyses of the data indicated that educator pedagogies were the highest predictors on the use of computers in the classroom. Although the quantitative analyses for educator support, training and attitude were the lowest predictors on the use of computers, the qualitative analysis, nevertheless, found sufficient support for it. Educationists and policy-makers must include all principals and educators when technological innovations were introduced into schools. All these role-players need to be cognizant of the implications if innovations were not appropriately implemented. Including the use of computers in educator training programs was important so that pre-service educators could see the benefits of using the computer in their own teaching. Educator pedagogy, theories and beliefs and access to computers were the highest predictors of using computers, hence a model was developed. The model aimed to strengthen the educators' initiatives to increase the likelihood that would result in enhanced teaching and learning when using computers.

Sarah Howie and Seugnet Blignaut (2009) conducted a study on South Africa's readiness to integrate ICT into mathematics and science pedagogy in secondary schools. The findings revealed that whilst South Africa had made some progress since 1998 in terms of the implementation of ICT in education, that the majority of schools were still in their infancy

regarding the acquisition of ICT and most of those who had access still in the process of trying to integrate the ICT into their teaching and learning. It would appear that more fundamental needs in South Africa's education system had dominated its priorities.

Charoula Angeli and Nicos Valanides (2009) conducted a study on epistemological and methodological issues for the Conceptualization, Development, and Assessment of ICT–TPCK: Advances in Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK) in Cyprus.

Hsin-Mei and Huang (2009) conducted a study on investigating of teachers' mathematical conceptions and Pedagogical Content Knowledge in Mathematics. The teacher's mathematical knowledge did not significantly affect their cognition of children's learning difficulties and knowledge of instructional practice.

Richardson (2009) conducted a study on mathematics teachers' development, exploration, and advancement of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge in the teaching and learning of Algebra. Results revealed the need to provide teachers with opportunities to develop and explore an integration of technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge in the teaching and learning of algebra.

Aida Suraya Md et al., (2008) conducted a study on Mathematics Teachers' Preparation Program: Determining the Balance between Contents in Mathematics and Pedagogy. Based on the types of mathematics education programs offered, students' preparedness to become teachers were revealed based on their confidence to teach, pedagogical content knowledge, views of mathematics, aspects that need be emphasised in teaching and their perceived importance of aspects to be incorporated in teaching.

Pernilla Nilsson (2008) conducted a study on teaching for understanding: The complex nature of Pedagogical Content Knowledge in Pre-service Education. This study emphasised the role of teaching experience and reflection in science teacher education as a way of better understanding the complex entities that constituted a knowledge base for teaching. The result revealed that the value of student-teachers participating in experiences contributed to the development of their PCK and supported a view of PCK development as a process of transformation.

Soonhye Park and Steve Oliver (2008) conducted a study on revisiting the conceptualization of Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK): PCK as a conceptual tool to understand teachers as professionals. The results indicated that (a) PCK was developed through reflection-in-action and reflection-on-action within given instructional contexts, (b) teacher efficacy emerged as an affective affiliate of PCK, (c) students had an important

impact on PCK development, (d) students' misconceptions played a significant role in shaping PCK, and (e) PCK was idiosyncratic in some aspects of its enactment.

Yih-Ruey Juang et al., (2008) conducted a study on Computer-Supported Teacher Development of Pedagogical Content Knowledge through Developing School-Based Curriculum. This study proposed a development model for PCK known as the 3C-model and implements a support system for it, known as EDUPLAN. Through the process of school-based curriculum development, the model was found to increase teacher PCK and collaboration. The supporting system was found to be capable of enhancing performance in lesson plan construction and revision.

Beula Johns and Annaraja (2008) conducted a study on the impact of information technology and self-esteem on teaching competency and pedagogical content knowledge of the B.Ed students. The findings showed that there was a significant relationship in the ICT awareness, self-esteem, teaching competency and pedagogical content knowledge of B.Ed students.

Ramganesh (2008) conducted a study on the effect of metacognitive strategy on enhancing teaching competency in mathematics among prospective teachers. The findings showed that B.Ed trainees should strengthened their teaching competency through metacognitive control.

Thangarajathi (2008) conducted a study on effectiveness of mind mapping technique in teaching mathematics. The findings of the study revealed that the mind mapping technique was more effective than the conventional method in terms of achievement.

Erika Lfstrm and Anne Nevgi (2008) conducted a study on university teaching staffs' pedagogical awareness displayed through ICT-facilitated teaching. The results of the present study indicated that while conceptuality and the transfer of knowledge were not well elaborated, the teachers particularly emphasised collaboration as a pedagogical means to facilitate learning. Furthermore, teacher reflection was an emerging theme in a few accounts, but this reflection appeared to facilitate student learning in a slightly different manner than the elements of meaningful learning, which directly impact the learning situation. This increased understanding of how the new media were adopted into teaching can be used to design ICT training schemes for university teaching staff.

Tsung Juang Wang (2008) conducted a study on using ICT to enhance academic learning: pedagogy and practice. The results revealed that the information and communication technologies (ICTs) had greater influence on the academic leaning. By

learning the new ICT tools effectively, the teachers became comfortable with existing new technologies, but more importantly, with the innovations that appear with increasing rapidity.

Bjorn Stensaker et al., (2007) conducted a study on use, updating and integration of ICT in higher education: Linking purpose, people and pedagogy. The analysis disclosed that Norwegian higher education institutions often had adequate economic resources and a rather well developed technical infrastructure and supported structure related to the use of ICT. In the conclusion it was argued that pedagogical issues and organizational and human development aspects must be better linked if ICT was to play a more effective role in teaching and learning in Norwegian higher education.

Sivakumar and Jahitha Begum (2007) conducted a study on teaching competency of mathematics teachers at higher secondary school. The finding of the study showed that mathematics teachers had to be trained for better teaching competency.

SuatKhoh Lim-Teo et al., (2007) conducted a study on the Development of Diploma in Education Student Teachers' Mathematics Pedagogical Content Knowledge. The Findings indicated that student teachers at the beginning of their programmes were generally quite weak in their Mathematics Pedagogical Content Knowledge, as might be expected. There was significant improvement in some aspects of their MPCK on completion of their mathematics pedagogy course.

Anisha V. Gopalakrishnan (2006) conducted a study on relationship between multiple intelligence and knowledge of content pedagogy of natural science secondary teacher education students. The findings of the study were: (i) 9.5% of male and 16.3% of female had high level of multiple intelligence. (ii) there were no significant difference in multiple intelligence by gender, locality, level of study and type of college. (iii) there was no association in their multiple intelligence by family income, but there was an association between birth order and multiple intelligence.

Nirmala, et al., (2006) conducted a study on optimization of academic achievement in mathematics: A linear programme approach. The findings of the study revealed that mathematics information skills, decision making skills and attitude towards mathematics had made a significant contribution towards the academic achievement. All the four factors confidence, usefulness, success and teacher of attitude to mathematics had made a significant contribution towards the maximization of the aggregate performance in mathematics.

Subir Nag (2006) conducted study on integral pedagogy process: A challenge for innovative teachers. The findings guided the teachers to develop various positive values and attitude among the learners. The ultimate aim was to produce real human being.

Crocco, Thornton and Chandler (2006) conducted a study on the influence of computer use on pre-service teachers' pedagogical content knowledge in social studies. The results of the study revealed that the use of computers had significant influence on the pedagogical content knowledge of pre-service teachers in social studies.

Vaille Dawson, Patricia Forster and Doug Reid (2006) conducted a study on Information Communication Technology (ICT) integration in a science education unit for preservice science teachers; Students' Perceptions of their ICT Skills, Knowledge and Pedagogy. The findings of this research suggested that some skills warranted greater attention in the unit, but students' pedagogical knowledge and knowledge and critique of ICT resources were enhanced over the duration of the unit.

Alex Morgan and Steve Kennewell (2005) conducted a study on the role of play in the pedagogy of ICT. In the study, several children reflected that they were learning in the same way as they had learned to use mobile phones, although there was no evidence for transfer of specific techniques. This indicated that the role of higher order learning skills was important, and evidence emerged that the influence of self-efficacy might be more important in gaining success than previous experience with PC technology.

Niess (2005) conducted a study on preparing teachers to teach science and mathematics with technology: Developing a technology Pedagogical Content Knowledge. Student teachers viewed the integration of technology and the nature of the discipline was identified as an important aspect of the development of TPCK.

Insung Jung (2005) conducted a study on ICT-Pedagogy integration in teacher training: Application cases. This paper analysed and organised a variety of approaches found in ICT uses in teacher training into a four-cell matrix. Based on the analysis of those approaches, it discussed new possibilities and challenges that ICT had brought to teacher training and professional development. It concluded with discussion of emerging research issues with respect to ICT integration into teacher training and networking.

Mary Webb (2005) conducted a study on affordances of ICT in science learning: Implications for an integrated pedagogy. The affordances that the author had identified support learning through four main effects: promoting cognitive acceleration; enabling a wider range of experience so that students can relate science to their own and other real-world experiences; increasing students' self-management; and facilitating data collection and presentation. ICT environments already provided a range of affordances that had been shown to enable learning of science but integrating these affordances with other pedagogical innovations provided even greater potential for enhancement of students' learning.

Chaurasia (2005) conducted a study on analysis of classroom teaching behaviour of Shikshamitras. The findings of the study were: (i) the Shikshamitras, BTC condense trained teachers and BTC trained teachers were found to be homogenous with regard to teacher-student interaction and teaching activities. (ii) the Shikshamitras, BTC condense trained teachers and BTC trained teachers differed significantly in teacher involvement in instruction, methods of giving introduction, use of textbook and overall effect of teaching. (iii) the classroom behaviour pattern with regard to interaction was found homogenous in the three groups, i.e., Shikshamitras, BTC trained teachers, and BTC condense trained teachers. (iv) the classroom behaviour pattern with regard to method of giving introduction and use of textbook differed in Shikshamitras, BTC condense teachers and BTC teachers.

Nate McCaughtry (2005) conducted a study on *Elaborating Pedagogical Content Knowledge: What it Means to Know Students and Think about Teaching*. Findings indicated that this teacher possessed a broad repertoire of knowledge about students that she used to think and make decisions about content, curriculum and pedagogy. The connections between knowing students and thinking about teaching were more sophisticated and interconnected than is typically recognized or articulated in teacher knowledge literature. Three themes were used to explain how this teacher understood her students' emotional and social lives in and out of her classroom, and ways it influenced her thinking and teaching.

Onno De Jong et al., (2005) conducted a study on *Preservice Teachers' Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Using Particle Models in Teaching Chemistry*. The outcome of the study revealed that, initially, all participants were able to describe specific learning difficulties, such as problems secondary school students had in relating the properties of substances to characteristics of the constituent particles. After teaching, all preservice teachers demonstrated a deeper understanding of their students' problems with the use of particle models. In addition, about half of the participants had become more aware of the possibilities and limitations of using particle models in specific teaching situations. Through learning from teaching, the preservice teachers further developed their PCK of using particle models, although this development varied among preservice teachers studied.

Alister Jones and Judy Moreland (2004) conducted a study on enhancing practicing primary school teachers' Pedagogical Content Knowledge in Technology. The increased PCK practice enhanced teacher knowledge about technology including the nature of technology, areas of technology and specific technological knowledge, changed pedagogical approaches, enhanced teacher student interaction, refinement of appropriate learning

outcomes, critical decision making, improved teacher confidence, and enhanced student learning.

Nate McCaughtry (2004) conducted a study on the Emotional Dimensions of a Teacher's Pedagogical Content Knowledge: Influences on Content, Curriculum, and Pedagogy. The findings showed that the teacher's interpretations of student emotion influenced her selecting, ordering, and formulating of curriculum units, her pedagogical maneuvering during lessons to facilitate learning, and her interactions with individual students and groups of students. The discussion centered on the need to expand current conceptions of teachers' pedagogical content knowledge, and the importance of emotional understanding in teaching. Future directions for research into emotion and teaching were suggested.

Peter John and Rosamund Sutherland (2004) conducted a study on teaching and learning with ICT: New technology and new pedagogy. The findings suggested that the use of ICT by subject teachers was being embraced but not imposed. This study ended with the suggestion for taking the ICT and learning venture forward within the current curriculum context.

Chandrakanthi (2003) conducted a study on socio-pedagogical factors affecting language skills among engineering college students. The findings of the study were: (i) socioeconomic status, family environment and personality traits were identified as significant factors affecting the language skills among the selected engineering students. (ii) the influence of pedagogical factors such as study habits, locus of control, learning approaches, learning styles and learners' effectiveness significantly influenced the language skills of the students.

Lilia Halim and Subahan Mohammad Meerah (2002) conducted a study on science trainee teachers' Pedagogical Content Knowledge and its influence on physics teaching. The findings showed that trainee teachers' PCK for promoting conceptual understanding was limited. They lacked the ability to transform their understanding of basic concepts in physics required to teach lower secondary school science pupils. The trainees' level of content knowledge affected their awareness of pupils' likely misconceptions. Consequently, the trainees were unable to employ the appropriate teaching strategies required to explain the scientific ideas.

CRITICAL REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The investigator has reviewed one hundred and two studies from India and abroad. In the same way the investigator could find more related literatures on technological pedagogical content knowledge which is another important area in the information era and

that provides numerous information especially for the B.Ed. trainees. In addition to that it helps B.Ed. trainees to improve their teaching. But it was noticed that there was a few Indian studies related to pedagogical content knowledge. Hence the investigator was able to find a lot of related literatures related to technological pedagogical content knowledge.

CHAPTER – III

METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Research methodology is a way to solve the research problems systematically. It may be understood as a science of studying how research is done. It studies about the various steps employed by the researcher, to study the research problem along with the logic of why a particular research study has been undertaken, how the research problem has been defined, in what way the hypothesis has been formulated, what data have been collected, what particular method has been adopted, why a particular technique of analysing data has been used and a host of similar other questions are usually answered. According to John W. Best (2003), “Research is considered to be the formal, systematic and extensive process of carrying on a scientific method of analysis. It involves a systematic structure of investigation usually resulting in some sort of formal record of procedures and a report of results or conclusions”. Here, the Investigator discusses the method used, population for the study, description of the study area, description of the sample, tools and statistical techniques used in the present study.

3.2 EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH

Robert M. W. Travers (1980) defined educational research as, “that activity which is directed towards the development of a science of behaviour in educational situations”. The ultimate aim of such science is to provide knowledge that will permit the educator to achieve his goals by the most effective methods. Educational research refers to a systematic attempt to gain a better understanding of educational process with a view of improving its efficiency. Educational research is nothing but an application of scientific method to the study of educational problems or educational thoughts. In other words, its scope is limited to educational practices or issues. Since education is a behavioural science, the major concern of educational research is to understand, explain and to some degree, predict and control the human behaviour. It is an activity directed towards the development of an organized body of scientific knowledge about the events with which educators are concerned.

3.3 METHOD FOR THE STUDY

The investigator has used survey method to study the technological pedagogical content knowledge among B.Ed student teachers in Tiruchirappalli district. The survey method gathers data from a relatively large number of cases at particular time. It attempts to describe and interpret what exists at present conditions, processes, trends, attitudes and belief for which the survey type of research would be more relevant and useful. It is concerned not

with the characteristics of individuals but with the generalized statistics of the population and statistics.

3.4 AREA OF THE STUDY

The area of the study consists of eleven colleges of education to conduct the classes of bachelor of education programme affiliated to Tamilnadu Teachers Education University and located from Tiruchirappalli district of Tamilnadu State.

3.5 POPULATION FOR THE STUDY

The population for the study includes the Bachelor of Education students who have taken in the self-financed colleges of education located in Tiruchirappalli district and affiliated to the Tamilnadu Teachers Education University, Chennai.

3.6 SAMPLE FOR THE STUDY

The investigator used stratified random sampling technique for selecting the sample. The investigator randomly selected eleven colleges of education from the total thirty two colleges of education at Tiruchirappalli district. The selection was done on the basis of locality of the college. From these colleges of education, 716 student teachers were selected by the stratification on the basis of sex, marital status, age, educational qualification, subject of studying, medium of instruction, years of study, locality, parental education and parental occupation.

TABLE 3.1
LIST OF COLLEGES SELECTED FOR THE STUDY

S. No.	Name of the Colleges	Number	Percentage (%)
1	Oxford College of Education, Pirattiyur, Trichy.	102	14.25%
2	Jamal Mohamed College of Education, TVS Tollgate, Trichy.	69	9.63%
3	Indira Ganesan College of Education, Manikandam, Trichy.	58	8.10%
4	Kongunadu College of Education, Thottiyam, Trichy.	88	12.30%
5	Jeevan College of Education, Manapparai, Trichy.	53	7.40%
6	J.J. College of Education, Ammapettai, Trichy.	67	9.35%
7	Amman College of Education, Pothavoor, Trichy.	47	6.57%
8	Divine College of Education, Ariyavur, Trichy.	51	7.12%
9	Siva College of Education, Thuraiyur, Trichy.	68	9.50%
10	Sri Saraswathi College of Education, Pallividai, Trichy.	57	7.97%
11	S.B.G Sanskrit Mission College of Education, Perugamani, Trichy.	56	7.82%
Total		716	100%

3.7 DISTRIBUTION OF THE SAMPLE

The following tables show the distribution of the sample with respect to the background variables.

TABLE 3.2
GENDER WISE DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE

Gender	Number	Percentage
Male	269	37.6%
Female	447	62.4%
Total	716	100%

It is inferred from the table that the sample consists of 37.6% of male and 62.4% of female student teachers and it is shown in the figure 3.1

FIG. 3.1 GENDER WISE DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE

TABLE 3.3

DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO MARITAL STATUS

Marital Status	Number	Percentage
Married	233	32.5%
Unmarried	483	67.5%
Total	716	100%

It is inferred from the table that the sample consists of 32.5% of married and 67.5% of unmarried student teachers and it is shown in the figure 3.2

FIG. 3.2 DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO MARITAL STATUS

TABLE 3.4

DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO AGE

Age	Number	Percentage
25 Years and below	436	60.9%
26-30	207	28.9%
31 Years and above	73	10.2%
Total	716	100%

It is inferred from the table that the sample consists of 60.9% of 25 years and below, 28.9% of 26-30 years and 10.2% of 31 years and above age group of student teachers and it is shown in the figure 3.3

FIG. 3.3 DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO AGE

TABLE 3.5

**DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO EDUCATIONAL
QUALIFICATION**

Educational Qualification	Number	Percentage
Undergraduate	537	75%
Postgraduate	179	25%
Total	716	100%

It is inferred from the table that the sample consists of 75% of undergraduate and 25% of postgraduate student teachers and it is shown in the figure 3.4

FIG. 3.4 DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION

TABLE 3.6

DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO SUBJECT OF STUDYING

Subject of Studying	Number	Percentage
Language	251	35.1%
Arts	179	25%
Humanities	286	39.9%
Total	716	100%

It is inferred from the table that the sample consists of 35.1% of student teachers studying languages, 25% of arts and 39.9% of humanities subjects and it is shown in the figure 3.5

FIG. 3.5 DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO SUBJECT OF STUDYING

TABLE 3.7

DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION

Medium of Instruction	Number	Percentage
Tamil	369	51.5%
English	347	48.5%
Total	716	100%

It is inferred from the table that the sample consists of 51.5% of Tamil and 48.5% of English medium studying student teachers and it is shown in the figure 3.6

FIG. 3.6 DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION

TABLE 3.8

DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO YEAR OF STUDY

Year of Study	Number	Percentage
I Year	392	54.7%
II Year	324	45.3%
Total	716	100%

It is inferred from the table that the sample consists of 54.7% of I Year and 45.3% of II Year student teachers and it is shown in the figure 3.7

FIG. 3.7 DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO YEAR OF STUDY

TABLE 3.9

DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO LOCALITY

Locality	Number	Percentage
Rural	450	62.8%
Urban	266	37.2%
Total	716	100%

It is inferred from the table that the sample consists of 62.8% of rural and 37.2% of urban locale of student teachers and it is shown in the figure 3.8

FIG. 3.8 DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO LOCALITY

TABLE 3.10

DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO PARENTAL EDUCATION

Parental Education	Number	Percentage
School Education	443	61.9%
Undergraduate	197	27.5%
Postgraduate	76	10.6%
Total	716	100%

It is inferred from the table that the sample consists of student teachers parental education of 61.9% of school education, 27.5% of undergraduates and 10.6% of postgraduate and it is shown in the figure 3.9

FIG. 3.9 DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO PARENTAL EDUCATION

TABLE 3.11

DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO PARENTAL OCCUPATION

Parental Occupation	Number	Percentage
Daily Wages	404	56.4%
Private	169	23.6%
Government	143	20%
Total	716	100%

It is inferred from the table that the sample consists of parental occupation of student teachers of 56.4% of daily wages, 23.6% of private and 20% of government employed and it is shown in the figure 3.10

FIG. 3.10 DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE WITH RESPECT TO PARENTAL OCCUPATION

3.8 TOOL USED IN THE PRESENT STUDY

The following tool were used for data collection

1. Technological pedagogical content knowledge scale developed and validated by the investigator.

3.9 TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE SCLAE (TPACK)

3.9.1 Description of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Scale (TPACK)

Measuring the technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) of student teachers, the investigator developed a technological pedagogical content knowledge scale (TPACK). To ensure the suitability, this tool was validated by the investigator.

3.9.2 Preparation of the Draft tool

As the first step towards the preparation of technological pedagogical content knowledge scale (TPACK), the investigator has gone through teacher education books and journals. In addition to that, the investigator has gone through the educational technology books and the journals related to educational technology. As no tool was directly available to assess the different sub scales of technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) B.Ed. students, the investigator constructed and validated the tool to assess the technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) B.Ed. students. The investigator prepared 74 statements. These items were given to the educational experts and the experts in Educational Technology. They scrutinized the items. Based on the suggestions given by the experts, some of the items were deleted and some of the items were modified. The modified draft of the technological pedagogical content knowledge scale (TPACK) had 63 items. Thus the investigator developed a rough draft of technological pedagogical content knowledge scale (TPACK) and it is appended. (Appendix-I)

3.9.3 Item Analysis

For the purpose of item analysis, the items were given to sixty student teachers of Oxford College of Education, Tiruchirappalli. Their responses were collected and scored by the investigator. Then item-total correlation for each item was calculated. The items, which were having value above 0.35 (for df 58, the table value of correlation is 0.35), were retained and

other items were eliminated. Finally the tool consisted only fifty one items. The correlation values of the items were appended. (Appendix-II)

3.9.4 Establishing Validity

The validity of the tool has been found in different methods. For the present study, the investigator established content validity.

3.9.5 Content Validity

To establish content validity of the technological pedagogical content knowledge scale (TPACK), the scale was given to the experts of Bharathidasan University, Trichy. Technological pedagogical content knowledge scale (TPACK) was well scrutinized and checked by the experts in educational technology. A few modifications were carried out based on their comments, regarding the language, suitability and relevance. Thus the content validity of the scale was established.

3.9.6 Establishing Reliability

In the present study, the reliability of the technological pedagogical content knowledge scale (TPACK) was established by applying the Split-Half method. This method shows the inter-correlation of the items in the test and the correlation of the items as a whole. A sample of 60 B.Ed., students was selected for the administration of the technological pedagogical content knowledge scale (TPACK). The items in the tools were classified as odd and even number items. Then Karl Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient was computed between the scores of odd number and even number items. The correlation coefficients computed were further corrected by applying the Cronbach's Alpha Formula. The Table 3.12 shows the coefficients of Cronbach's Alpha computed for the various sub scales of the technological pedagogical content knowledge scale (TPACK).

TABLE 3.12

**SPLIT-HALF RELIABILITY COEFFICIENT OF TECHNOLOGICAL
PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE SCLAE**

TPACK Questionnaire and its Sub Scales	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items
Technological Knowledge (TK)	0.740
Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)	0.674
Content Knowledge (CK)	0.686
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK)	0.721
Technological Content Knowledge (TCK)	0.636
Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK)	0.779
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK)	0.780

The above table shows the sub scales wise reliability value of technological pedagogical content knowledge.

3.9.7 Description of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Scale

The following table shows that the sub scales wise distribution of items in the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Scale.

TABLE 3.13

**ITEM DESCRIPTION OF TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT
KNOWLEDGE INVENTORY**

TPACK Questionnaire and its Sub Scales	Items Distribution
Technological Knowledge (TK)	1-7
Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)	8-15
Content Knowledge (CK)	16-21
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK)	22-29

Technological Content Knowledge (TCK)	30-35
Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK)	36-43
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK)	44-51

3.9.8 Scoring

The scoring was done with the key which was prepared by the investigator for technological pedagogical content knowledge scale. In the technological pedagogical content knowledge scale, there are only positive statements. The choices given to the respondents are “Strongly Agree”, “Agree”, “Sometimes”, “Disagree” and “Strongly Disagree”. An individual may get a lowest score of 51 and the possibility of the highest score of 255. The scoring procedure is given in the following table.

TABLE 3.14

SCORING OF TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE

Response	Scoring
Strongly Agree	5
Agree	4
Sometimes	3
Disagree	2
Strongly Disagree	1

3.10 PROCEDURE FOR DATA COLLECTION

A planned schedule by the investigator helped him to collect the data in an orderly manner, with the prior permission of head of the institution. The investigator visited selected colleges of education in Tiruchirappalli district. After giving a brief introduction about the investigator, the investigator established a rapport with the B.Ed. students and explained the purpose of research and encouraged them to be free and frank in giving the responses.

Then investigator distributed the booklets of research tool to the respondents and they were asked to read all the items carefully after filling the personal profile form given in first page about the details of the college of education. Then they were asked to put the tick mark in the consecutive scale. In administration of tool, the B.Ed. students have taken 45 minutes to

complete the research tool by reading carefully and answering the statements. After their answer the investigator collected the filled questionnaire. Thus the investigator collected the data.

TABLE 3.15

TIME FOR ADMINISTRATION OF TOOLS

Research Tools	Time (in min)
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Scale	45
Total	45

3.11 STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED FOR THE STUDY

Statistics is the science of making effective use of numerical data relating to groups of individuals or experiments. It deals with all aspects of this, including not only the collection, analysis and interpretation of such data, but also the planning of the collection of data, in terms of the design of surveys and experiments.

3.11.1 Levels

After calculating the mean and standard deviation, the scores were corrected into T scores

$$T = 50 + 10 Z$$

Where

$$Z = \text{Raw Score} - \text{Mean} / \text{Standard Deviation}$$

The levels are fixed as follows

TABLE 3.15

LEVELS OF SCORE

Score	Levels
Above Mean + 1 S.D	High
Between Mean +/-1 S.D	Average
Below Mean -1 S.D	Low

3.11.2 ‘t’ test

‘t’ test or test of significance of the difference between means for large independent samples (Garret, 1969) is used to compare the means between any two groups on any of the variables. If the ‘t’ value is below a cut-off point at 5% level, the differences in means is considered as not significant and the null hypothesis is accepted. When ‘t’ value exceeds a cut-

off point at 5% level, then the difference side is considered to be significant and null hypothesis is rejected.

3.11.3 ANOVA

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is an extremely useful technique for testing the difference between the means of multiple independent samples. The basic principle for ANOVA is to test the difference among the means of samples by examining the amount of variation between the samples relative to the amount of variation among samples. The value of ANOVA is compared in the 'F' limit for given degrees of freedom at 5% level. If the 'F' value worked out is equal or exceeds the 'F' limit value from the table indicated, then there are significant differences among the samples between the means.

3.11.3.1 Post ANOVA test - Waller-Duncan test

Duncan's multiple comparison procedure based on the Standardized range test. For tests that are used for detecting homogeneity subsets of means, non-empty group means are sorted in ascending order. Means that are not significantly different are included together to form a homogeneity subset. The significance for each homogeneity subset of means is displayed. For unequal sample sizes, the harmonic mean n_h is used instead of n .

The Waller-Duncan t test is given as follows

$$v_i, j = |x_i - x_j| \geq tB(w, F, q, f) S \sqrt{2/n}$$

Where

$tB(w, F, q, f)$ is the Bayesian t value that depends on w

$$F = \frac{MS_{\text{treat}}}{MS_{\text{error}}} \quad \text{and } S^2 = MS_{\text{error}}$$

Here

$f = k(n-1)$ and $q = k-1$. MS_{error} and MS_{treat} are the usual mean squares in the ANOVA table.

3.11.4 Pearson Product Moment Correlation

Pearson ' γ ' is used for estimating the extent of relation existing among different variables taken in pairs for all the different groups. Garret (1969) presents the following classification for interpreting the various values of ' γ ', which is adopted for the study.

γ from 0.00 to +/- 0.20 denotes negligible correlation.

- γ from +/-0.20 to +/- 0.40 denotes low correlation.
 γ from +/-0.40 to +/- 0.70 denotes substantial correlation.
 γ from +/-0.70 to +/- 1 denotes high correlation.

The correlation is interpreted only after the statistical significance of co-efficient correlation is considered from the tables. In the present study it's found that ' γ ' exceeds 0.062, it is significant at 5% level and if it's below 0.062, it is not significant at 5% level.

3.11.5 Chi-Square test

Chi-square distribution (χ^2 -distribution) with k degrees of freedom is the distribution of a sum of the squares of k independent standard normal random variables. It is one of the most widely used inferential statistics. It is used for goodness of fit on an observed distribution to a theoretical one of qualitative data. The value of χ^2 is compared in the ' χ^2 ' limit for given degrees of freedom at 5% level. If the ' χ^2 ' value worked out is equal or exceeds out the ' χ^2 ' limit value from the table indicated; then there are significant association between the samples.

3.12 TABULATION OF RESPONSES

The data collected were scored as per the norms established and the responded items were scored on the basis of scoring key in the form of matrix table. The scored data were fed into the computer and analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics v21. The tabulation of analysed data is given in the following chapter.

CHAPTER IV

ANALYSIS OF DATA

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Statistical analysis is the process of collection, analyzing and interpreting the numerical data and it is one of the basic steps of research process. In this Chapter, the Researcher discusses the results of mean, standard deviation, 't'-test, One-Way ANOVA, Chi-Square analysis, Karl Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Multiple regression analysis.

Analysis of data means studying the tabulated material in order to determine the inherent facts or meanings and it involves the application of deductive and inductive logic to the research process. Kothari (1990) stated that analysis of data is essential for any scientific study and for ensuring that one has all relevant data for making contemplated comparisons and analysis. The term analysis refers to the computation of certain measures along with searching for pattern of relationship that exists among data groups.

According to Krishnaswamy (1993), "analysis means a critical examination of the assembled and grouped data for studying the characteristics of the object under the study and for determining the patterns of influence and relationship among the variables relating it".

So the collected data are studied in many possible ways to explore the facts and it is done by the investigator under the following headings.

1. Technological pedagogical content knowledge of male and female student teachers.
2. Technological pedagogical content knowledge of married and unmarried student teachers.
3. Technological pedagogical content knowledge of undergraduate and postgraduate studied student teachers.
4. Technological pedagogical content knowledge of Tamil and English medium studying student teachers.
5. Technological pedagogical content knowledge of rural and urban student teachers.
6. Technological pedagogical content knowledge of student teachers with regard age.
7. Technological pedagogical content knowledge of student teachers with regard subject of studying.
8. Technological pedagogical content knowledge of student teachers with regard parental education.

9. Technological pedagogical content knowledge of student teachers with regard parental occupation.

4.2 DIFFERENTIAL ANALYSIS

4.2.1 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student Teachers

The Table 4.2.1.1 gives a clear picture of the level of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of male and female student teachers.

Table 4.2.1.1
LEVEL OF TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF MALE AND FEMALE STUDENT TEACHERS

Variables	Gender	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Technological Knowledge	Male	48	17.8	151	56.1	70	26.1
	Female	80	17.9	244	54.6	123	27.5
Pedagogical Knowledge	Male	40	14.9	189	70.2	40	14.9
	Female	85	19	227	50.8	135	30.2
Content Knowledge	Male	53	19.7	136	50.5	80	29.8
	Female	79	17.7	277	62	91	20.3
Technological pedagogical knowledge	Male	41	15.2	143	53.2	85	31.6
	Female	80	17.9	240	53.7	127	28.4
Technological content knowledge	Male	32	11.9	175	65.1	62	23
	Female	72	16.1	284	63.5	91	20.4
Pedagogical content knowledge	Male	41	15.2	163	60.6	65	24.2
	Female	98	21.9	240	53.7	109	24.4
Technological pedagogical content knowledge	Male	49	18.2	146	54.3	74	27.5
	Female	60	13.4	274	61.3	113	25.3

It is inferred from the Table 4.2.1.1 that 17.8% of male student teachers reported low, 56.1% of them moderate and 26.1% of them high level of technological knowledge. Whereas 17.9% of female student teachers reported low, 54.6% of them moderate and 27.5% of them high level of technological knowledge.

It is understood that 14.9% of male student teachers reported low, 70.2% of them moderate and 14.9% of them high level of pedagogical knowledge. Whereas 19% of female student teachers reported low, 50.8% of them moderate and 30.2% of them high level of pedagogical knowledge.

It is clear that 19.7% of male student teachers reported low, 50.5% of them moderate and 29.8% of them high level of content knowledge. Whereas 17.7% of female student teachers reported low, 62% of them moderate and 20.3% of them high level of content knowledge.

The Table indicates that 15.2% of male student teachers reported low, 53.2% of them moderate and 31.6% of them high level of technological pedagogical knowledge. Whereas 17.9% of female student teachers reported low, 53.7% of them moderate and 28.4% of them high level of technological pedagogical knowledge.

It is shown that 11.9% of male student teachers reported low, 65.1% of them moderate and 23% of them high level of technological content knowledge. Whereas 16.1% of female student teachers reported low, 63.5% of them moderate and 20.4% of them high level of technological content knowledge.

The Table displays that 15.2% of male student teachers reported low, 60.6% of them moderate and 24.2% of them high level of pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas 21.9% of female student teachers reported low, 53.7% of them moderate and 24.4% of them high level of pedagogical content knowledge.

It is inferred from the Table that 18.2% of male student teachers reported low, 54.3% of them moderate and 27.5% of them high level of technological pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas 13.4% of female student teachers reported low, 61.3% of them moderate and 25.3% of them high level of technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 1

There is no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological

pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical and content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 1.1a

There is no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their technological knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 1.1b

There is no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 1.1c

There is no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 1.1d

There is no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 1.1e

There is no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 1.1f

There is no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 1.1g

There is no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.2.1.2
DIFFERENCE BETWEEN MALE AND FEMALE STUDENT TEACHERS IN THEIR TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE

Variable	Gender	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Remarks at 5% level
Technological Knowledge	Male	26.457	4.786	0.143	NS
	Female	26.405	4.738		
Pedagogical Knowledge	Male	31.446	4.615	3.034	S
	Female	32.503	4.456		
Content Knowledge	Male	23.673	3.487	3.463	S
	Female	24.658	3.799		
Technological pedagogical knowledge	Male	30.896	4.681	1.566	NS
	Female	31.477	4.879		
Technological content knowledge	Male	23.673	4.038	2.015	S
	Female	24.306	4.097		
Pedagogical content knowledge	Male	30.740	5.081	3.522	S
	Female	32.081	4.841		
Technological pedagogical content knowledge	Male	31.227	4.900	3.361	S
	Female	32.409	4.341		

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the Table 4.2.1.2 that there was significant difference between male and female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge, as the calculated 't' values of 3.034, 3.463, 2.015, 3.522 and 3.361 was greater than the table value of 1.96 at 5% level of significance. **Hence the null hypothesis 1.1b, 1.1c, 1.1e, 1.1f and 1.1g was rejected.**

Further, there was no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, as the calculated ‘t’ values of 0.143 and 1.566 was less than the table value of 1.96 at 5% level of significance. *Hence the null hypothesis 1.1a and 1.1d was accepted.*

4.2.2 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Married and Unmarried Student Teachers

The Table 4.2.2.1 gives a clear picture of the level of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical and content knowledge of married and unmarried student teachers.

Table 4.2.2.1
LEVEL OF TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF MARRIED AND UNMARRIED STUDENT TEACHERS

Variables	Marital Status	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Technological Knowledge	Married	45	19.3	142	60.9	46	19.8
	Unmarried	83	17.2	271	56.1	129	26.7
Pedagogical Knowledge	Married	30	12.9	136	58.4	67	28.7
	Unmarried	95	19.7	269	55.7	119	24.6
Content Knowledge	Married	44	18.9	123	52.8	66	28.3
	Unmarried	77	15.9	326	67.5	80	16.6
Technological pedagogical knowledge	Married	43	18.5	131	56.2	59	25.3
	Unmarried	92	19	261	54	130	27
Technological content knowledge	Married	32	13.7	158	67.8	43	18.5
	Unmarried	88	18.2	301	62.3	94	19.5
Pedagogical content knowledge	Married	52	22.3	106	45.5	75	32.2
	Unmarried	86	17.8	255	52.8	142	29.4
Technological pedagogical	Married	37	15.9	121	51.9	75	32.2

content knowledge	Unmarried	100	20.7	277	57.4	106	21.9
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It is inferred from the Table 4.2.2.1 that 19.3% of married student teachers reported low, 60.9% of them moderate and 19.8% of them high level of technological knowledge. Whereas 17.2% of unmarried student teachers reported low, 56.1% of them moderate and 26.7% of them high level of technological knowledge.

It is understood that 12.9% of married student teachers reported low, 58.4% of them moderate and 28.7% of them high level of pedagogical knowledge. Whereas 19.7% of unmarried student teachers reported low, 55.7% of them moderate and 24.6% of them high level of pedagogical knowledge.

It is clear that 18.9% of married student teachers reported low, 52.8% of them moderate and 28.3% of them high level of content knowledge. Whereas 15.9% of unmarried student teachers reported low, 67.5% of them moderate and 16.6% of them high level of content knowledge.

The Table indicates that 18.5% of married student teachers reported low, 56.2% of them moderate and 25.3% of them high level of technological pedagogical knowledge. Whereas 19% of unmarried student teachers reported low, 54% of them moderate and 27% of them high level of technological pedagogical knowledge.

It is shown that 13.7% of married student teachers reported low, 67.8% of them moderate and 18.5% of them high level of technological content knowledge. Whereas 18.2% of unmarried student teachers reported low, 62.3% of them moderate and 19.5% of them high level of technological content knowledge.

The Table displays that 22.3% of married student teachers reported low, 45.5% of them moderate and 32.2% of them high level of pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas 17.8% of unmarried student teachers reported low, 52.8% of them moderate and 29.4% of them high level of pedagogical content knowledge.

It is inferred from the Table that 15.9% of married student teachers reported low, 51.9% of them moderate and 32.2% of them high level of technological pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas 20.7% of unmarried student teachers reported low, 57.4% of them moderate and 21.9% of them high level of technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 2

There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical and content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 2.1a

There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their technological knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 2.1b

There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 2.1c

There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 2.1d

There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 2.1e

There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 2.1f

There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 2.1g

There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.2.2.2
DIFFERENCE BETWEEN MARRIED AND UNMARRIED STUDENT TEACHERS IN THEIR TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE

Variable	Marital Status	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Remarks at 5% level
Technological Knowledge	Married	26.296	4.734	0.502	NS
	Unmarried	26.487	4.766		
Pedagogical Knowledge	Married	31.824	4.532	1.155	NS
	Unmarried	32.242	4.545		
Content Knowledge	Married	24.391	3.815	0.514	NS
	Unmarried	24.238	3.666		
Technological pedagogical knowledge	Married	31.099	4.827	0.617	NS
	Unmarried	31.335	4.805		
Technological content knowledge	Married	24.155	4.0548	0.391	NS
	Unmarried	24.027	4.102		
Pedagogical content knowledge	Married	31.464	4.935	0.423	NS
	Unmarried	31.631	4.993		
Technological pedagogical content knowledge	Married	31.717	4.685	1.005	NS
	Unmarried	32.085	4.546		

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the Table 4.2.2.2 that there was no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical and content knowledge, as the calculated 't' values of 0.502, 1.155, 0.514, 0.617, 0.391, 0.423 and 1.005 was less than the table value of 1.96 at 5% level of significance. *Hence the null hypothesis 2.1a, 2.1b, 2.1c, 2.1d, 2.1e, 2.1f and 2.1g was accepted.*

4.2.3 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Undergraduate and Postgraduate Studied Student Teachers

The Table 4.2.3.1 gives a clear picture of the level of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical and content knowledge of undergraduate and postgraduate studied student teachers.

Table 4.2.3.1
LEVEL OF TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF UNDERGRADUATE AND POSTGRADUATE STUDIED STUDENT TEACHERS

Variables	Qualifications	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Technological Knowledge	Undergraduate	123	22.9	313	58.3	101	18.8
	postgraduate	23	12.8	93	51.9	63	35.3
Pedagogical Knowledge	Undergraduate	108	20.1	300	55.9	129	24
	postgraduate	40	22.3	100	55.9	39	21.8
Content Knowledge	Undergraduate	110	20.5	278	51.8	149	27.7
	postgraduate	35	19.5	95	53.1	49	27.4
Technological pedagogical knowledge	Undergraduate	100	18.6	292	54.4	145	27
	postgraduate	35	19.5	100	55.9	44	24.6
Technological content knowledge	Undergraduate	127	23.6	262	48.8	148	27.6
	postgraduate	23	12.8	109	60.9	47	26.3
Pedagogical content knowledge	Undergraduate	109	20.3	262	48.8	166	30.9
	postgraduate	21	11.7	122	68.2	36	20.1
Technological pedagogical content knowledge	Undergraduate	120	22.3	293	54.6	124	23.1
	postgraduate	29	16.2	97	54.2	53	29.6

It is inferred from the Table 4.2.3.1 that 22.9% of undergraduate student teachers reported low, 58.3% of them moderate and 18.8% of them high level of technological

knowledge. Whereas 12.8% of postgraduate student teachers reported low, 51.9% of them moderate and 35.3% of them high level of technological knowledge.

It is understood that 20.1% of undergraduate student teachers reported low, 55.9% of them moderate and 24% of them high level of pedagogical knowledge. Whereas 22.3% of postgraduate student teachers reported low, 55.9% of them moderate and 21.8% of them high level of pedagogical knowledge.

It is clear that 20.5% of undergraduate student teachers reported low, 51.8% of them moderate and 27.7% of them high level of content knowledge. Whereas 19.5% of postgraduate student teachers reported low, 53.1% of them moderate and 27.4% of them high level of content knowledge.

The Table indicates that 18.6% of undergraduate student teachers reported low, 54.4% of them moderate and 27% of them high level of technological pedagogical knowledge. Whereas 19.5% of postgraduate student teachers reported low, 55.9% of them moderate and 24.6% of them high level of technological pedagogical knowledge.

It is shown that 23.6% of undergraduate student teachers reported low, 48.8% of them moderate and 27.6% of them high level of technological content knowledge. Whereas 12.8% of postgraduate student teachers reported low, 60.9% of them moderate and 26.3% of them high level of technological content knowledge.

The Table displays that 20.3% of undergraduate student teachers reported low, 48.8% of them moderate and 30.9% of them high level of pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas 11.7% of postgraduate student teachers reported low, 68.2% of them moderate and 20.1% of them high level of pedagogical content knowledge.

It is inferred from the Table that 22.3% of undergraduate student teachers reported low, 54.6% of them moderate and 23.1% of them high level of technological pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas 16.2% of postgraduate student teachers reported low, 54.2% of them moderate and 29.6% of them high level of technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 3

There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical and content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 3.1a

There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate student teachers in their technological knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 3.1b

There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 3.1c

There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate student teachers in their content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 3.1d

There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 3.1e

There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate student teachers in their technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 3.1f

There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate student teachers in their pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 3.1g

There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.2.3.2
DIFFERENCE BETWEEN UNDERGRADUATE AND POSTGRADUATE STUDIED
STUDENT TEACHERS IN THEIR TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE,
PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL
PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE,
PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL
PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE

Variable	Qualifications	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Remarks at 5% level
Technological Knowledge	Undergraduate	26.354	4.795	0.690	NS
	Postgraduate	26.637	4.632		
Pedagogical Knowledge	Undergraduate	32.138	4.537	0.323	NS
	Postgraduate	32.011	4.566		
Content Knowledge	Undergraduate	24.281	3.655	0.081	NS
	Postgraduate	24.307	3.893		
Technological pedagogical knowledge	Undergraduate	31.277	4.887	0.184	NS
	Postgraduate	31.201	4.585		
Technological content knowledge	Undergraduate	24.052	3.959	0.185	NS
	Postgraduate	24.117	4.449		
Pedagogical content knowledge	Undergraduate	31.566	5.091	0.100	NS
	Postgraduate	31.609	4.609		
Technological pedagogical content knowledge	Undergraduate	31.980	4.555	0.146	NS
	Postgraduate	31.922	4.714		

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the Table 4.2.3.2 that there was no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical and content knowledge, as the calculated 't' values of 0.690, 0.323, 0.081, 0.184, 0.185, 0.100 and 0.146 was less than the table value of 1.96 at 5% level of significance. *Hence the null hypothesis 3.1a, 3.1b, 3.1c, 3.1d, 3.1e, 3.1f and 3.1g was accepted.*

4.2.4 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Tamil and English Medium Studying Student Teachers

The Table 4.2.4.1 gives a clear picture of the level of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical and content knowledge of Tamil and English medium studying student teachers.

Table 4.2.4.1
LEVEL OF TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF TAMIL AND ENGLISH MEDIUM STUDYING STUDENT TEACHERS

Variables	Medium of Instruction	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Technological Knowledge	Tamil	57	15.4	201	54.5	111	30.6
	English	71	20.5	194	55.9	82	23.6
Pedagogical Knowledge	Tamil	48	13	238	64.5	83	22.5
	English	70	20.2	192	55.3	85	24.5
Content Knowledge	Tamil	80	21.7	183	49.6	106	28.7
	English	65	18.7	190	54.8	92	26.5
Technological pedagogical knowledge	Tamil	69	18.7	196	53.1	104	28.2
	English	66	19	196	56.5	85	24.5
Technological content knowledge	Tamil	74	20.1	179	48.5	116	31.4
	English	67	19.3	228	65.7	52	15
Pedagogical content knowledge	Tamil	53	14.4	233	63.1	83	22.5
	English	75	21.6	173	49.9	99	28.5
Technological pedagogical content knowledge	Tamil	49	13.3	197	53.4	123	33.3
	English	60	17.3	184	53	103	29.7

It is inferred from the Table 4.2.4.1 that 15.4% of Tamil medium studying student teachers reported low, 54.5% of them moderate and 30.6% of them high level of technological

knowledge. Whereas 20.5% of English medium studying student teachers reported low, 55.9% of them moderate and 23.6% of them high level of technological knowledge.

It is understood that 13% of Tamil medium studying student teachers reported low, 64.5% of them moderate and 22.5% of them high level of pedagogical knowledge. Whereas 20.2% of English medium studying student teachers reported low, 55.3% of them moderate and 24.5% of them high level of pedagogical knowledge.

It is clear that 21.7% of Tamil medium studying student teachers reported low, 49.6% of them moderate and 28.7% of them high level of content knowledge. Whereas 18.7% of English medium studying student teachers reported low, 54.8% of them moderate and 26.5% of them high level of content knowledge.

The Table indicates that 18.7% of Tamil medium studying student teachers reported low, 53.1% of them moderate and 28.2% of them high level of technological pedagogical knowledge. Whereas 19% of English medium studying student teachers reported low, 56.5% of them moderate and 24.5% of them high level of technological pedagogical knowledge.

It is shown that 20.1% of Tamil medium studying student teachers reported low, 48.5% of them moderate and 31.4% of them high level of technological content knowledge. Whereas 19.3% of English medium studying student teachers reported low, 65.7% of them moderate and 15% of them high level of technological content knowledge.

The Table displays that 14.4% of Tamil medium studying student teachers reported low, 63.1% of them moderate and 22.5% of them high level of pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas 21.6% of English medium studying student teachers reported low, 49.9% of them moderate and 28.5% of them high level of pedagogical content knowledge.

It is inferred from the Table that 13.3% of Tamil medium studying student teachers reported low, 53.4% of them moderate and 33.3% of them high level of technological pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas 17.3% of English medium studying student teachers reported low, 53% of them moderate and 29.7% of them high level of technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 4

There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge,

technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical and content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 4.1a

There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their technological knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 4.1b

There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 4.1c

There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 4.1d

There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 4.1e

There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 4.1f

There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 4.1g

There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.2.4.2
DIFFERENCE BETWEEN TAMIL AND ENGLISH MEDIUM STUDYING STUDENT
TEACHERS IN THEIR TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL
KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL
KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL
CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL AND
CONTENT KNOWLEDGE

Variable	Medium of Instruction	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Remarks at 5% level
Technological Knowledge	Tamil	27.000	4.629	3.364	S
	English	25.813	4.813		
Pedagogical Knowledge	Tamil	32.054	4.574	0.315	NS
	English	32.161	4.513		
Content Knowledge	Tamil	24.325	3.707	0.278	NS
	English	24.248	3.724		
Technological pedagogical knowledge	Tamil	31.472	4.722	1.223	NS
	English	31.032	4.899		
Technological content knowledge	Tamil	24.469	3.949	2.717	S
	English	23.643	4.187		
Pedagogical content knowledge	Tamil	31.943	4.907	2.037	S
	English	31.187	5.017		
Technological pedagogical content knowledge	Tamil	32.249	4.582	1.710	NS
	English	31.663	4.589		

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the Table 4.2.4.2 that there was significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their technological knowledge, technological content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge as the calculated 't' values of 3.364, 2.717 and 2.037 was greater than the table value of 1.96 at 5% level of significance. **Hence the null hypothesis 4.1a, 4.1e and 4.1f was rejected.**

Further, there was no significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical

knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge, as the calculated ‘t’ values of 0.315, 0.278, 1.223 and 1.710 was less than the table value of 1.96 at 5% level of significance.

Hence the null hypothesis 4.1b, 4.1c, 4.1d and 4.1g was accepted.

4.2.5 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Rural and Urban Student Teachers

The Table 4.2.5.1 gives a clear picture of the level of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical and content knowledge of rural and urban student teachers.

Table 4.2.5.1
LEVEL OF TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF RURAL AND URBAN STUDENT TEACHERS

Variables	Locality	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Technological Knowledge	Rural	75	16.7	259	57.6	116	25.7
	Urban	53	19.9	136	51.2	77	28.9
Pedagogical Knowledge	Rural	98	21.8	260	57.8	92	20.4
	Urban	50	18.8	140	52.6	76	28.6
Content Knowledge	Rural	92	20.4	239	53.2	119	26.4
	Urban	53	19.9	134	50.4	79	29.7
Technological pedagogical knowledge	Rural	83	18.4	292	64.9	75	16.7
	Urban	41	15.4	166	62.4	59	22.2
Technological content knowledge	Rural	72	16	228	50.7	150	33.3
	Urban	48	18	109	41	109	41
Pedagogical content knowledge	Rural	87	19.3	223	49.6	140	31.1
	Urban	51	19.2	138	51.9	77	28.9
Technological pedagogical content knowledge	Rural	66	14.7	242	53.8	142	31.5
	Urban	43	16.2	139	52.3	84	31.5

It is inferred from the Table 4.2.5.1 that 16.7% of rural student teachers reported low, 57.6% of them moderate and 25.7% of them high level of technological knowledge. Whereas 19.9% of urban student teachers reported low, 51.2% of them moderate and 28.9% of them high level of technological knowledge.

It is understood that 21.8% of rural student teachers reported low, 57.8% of them moderate and 20.4% of them high level of pedagogical knowledge. Whereas 18.8% of urban student teachers reported low, 52.6% of them moderate and 28.6% of them high level of pedagogical knowledge.

It is clear that 20.4% of rural student teachers reported low, 53.2% of them moderate and 26.4% of them high level of content knowledge. Whereas 19.9% of urban student teachers reported low, 50.4% of them moderate and 29.7% of them high level of content knowledge.

The Table indicates that 18.4% of rural student teachers reported low, 64.9% of them moderate and 16.7% of them high level of technological pedagogical knowledge. Whereas 15.4% of urban student teachers reported low, 62.4% of them moderate and 22.2% of them high level of technological pedagogical knowledge.

It is shown that 16% of rural student teachers reported low, 50.7% of them moderate and 33.3% of them high level of technological content knowledge. Whereas 18% of urban student teachers reported low, 41% of them moderate and 41% of them high level of technological content knowledge.

The Table displays that 19.3% of rural student teachers reported low, 49.6% of them moderate and 31.1% of them high level of pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas 19.2% of urban student teachers reported low, 51.9% of them moderate and 28.9% of them high level of pedagogical content knowledge.

It is inferred from the Table that 14.7% of rural student teachers reported low, 53.8% of them moderate and 31.5% of them high level of technological pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas 16.2% of urban student teachers reported low, 52.3% of them moderate and 31.5% of them high level of technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 5

There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological

pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical and content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 5.1a

There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their technological knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 5.1b

There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 5.1c

There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 5.1d

There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 5.1e

There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 5.1f

There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 5.1g

There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.2.5.2
DIFFERENCE BETWEEN RURAL AND URBAN STUDENT TEACHERS IN THEIR TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE

Variable	Locality	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Remarks at 5% level
Technological Knowledge	Rural	26.382	4.625	0.310	NS
	Urban	26.496	4.971		
Pedagogical Knowledge	Rural	32.016	4.374	0.694	NS
	Urban	32.259	4.817		
Content Knowledge	Rural	24.224	3.529	0.593	NS
	Urban	24.395	4.010		
Technological pedagogical knowledge	Rural	31.187	4.656	0.519	NS
	Urban	31.380	5.067		
Technological content knowledge	Rural	23.900	3.809	1.436	NS
	Urban	24.353	4.504		
Pedagogical content knowledge	Rural	31.680	4.963	0.722	NS
	Urban	31.402	4.992		
Technological pedagogical content knowledge	Rural	31.953	4.682	0.089	NS
	Urban	31.985	4.443		

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the Table 4.2.5.2 that there was no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge as the calculated 't' values of 0.310, 0.694, 0.593, 0.519, 1.436, 0.722 and 0.089 was less than the table value of 1.96 at 5% level of significance. *Hence the null hypothesis 5.1a, 5.1b, 5.1c, 5.1d, 5.1e, 5.1f and 5.1g was accepted.*

4.2.6 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Student Teachers having Age Group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above

NULL HYPOTHESIS 6

There is any significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 6.1a

There is no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their technological knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 6.1b

There is no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 6.1c

There is no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 6.1d

There is no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 6.1e

There is no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 6.1f

There is no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 6.1g

There is no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.2.6.1
DIFFERENCE AMONG STUDENT TEACHERS HAVING 25 YEARS AND BELOW, 26-30 YEARS AND 31 YEARS AND ABOVE OF AGE GROUPS IN THEIR TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE

Variable	Source of Variation	Sum of Square	Mean Square	Calculated 'F' Value	Remarks at 5% level
Technological Knowledge	Between	6.789	3.395	0.150	NS
	Within	16148.13	22.648		
Pedagogical Knowledge	Between	84.082	42.041	2.044	NS
	Within	14667.85	20.572		
Content Knowledge	Between	28.598	14.299	1.037	NS
	Within	9832.13	13.790		
Technological pedagogical knowledge	Between	6.247	3.213	0.139	NS
	Within	16540.77	23.199		
Technological content knowledge	Between	43.807	21.904	1.314	NS
	Within	11883.83	16.667		
Pedagogical content knowledge	Between	77.097	38.549	1.562	NS
	Within	17599.67	24.684		
Technological pedagogical content knowledge	Between	29.414	14.707	0.697	NS
	Within	15048.71	21.106		

(At 5% level of significance for 2, 934 df, the table value of 'F' is 3.00)

It is inferred from the Table 4.2.6.1 that there was no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and

technological pedagogical content knowledge as the calculated 'F' values of 0.150, 0.044, 1.037, 0.139, 1.314, 1.562 and 0.697 was less than the table value of 3.00 at 5% level of significance. *Hence the null hypothesis 6.1a, 6.1b, 6.1c, 6.1d, 6.1e, 6.1f and 6.1g was accepted.*

4.2.7 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Student Teachers Studying Languages, Arts and Science Subjects

NULL HYPOTHESIS 7

There is no significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 7.1a

There is no significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their technological knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 7.1b

There is no significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 7.1c

There is no significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 7.1d

There is no significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 7.1e

There is no significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 7.1f

There is no significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 7.1g

There is no significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.2.7.1
DIFFERENCE AMONG STUDENT TEACHERS STUDYING LANGUAGES, ARTS
AND SCIENCE SUBJECTS IN THEIR TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE,
PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL
PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE,
PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL
PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE

Variable	Source of Variation	Sum of Square	Mean Square	Calculated 'F' Value	Remarks at 5% level
Technological Knowledge	Between	127.945	63.973	2.846	NS
	Within	16026.98	22.478		
Pedagogical Knowledge	Between	302.948	151.474	7.475	S
	Within	14448.98	20.265		
Content Knowledge	Between	60.913	30.457	2.216	NS
	Within	9799.81	13.744		
Technological pedagogical knowledge	Between	19.331	9.666	0.417	NS
	Within	16527.86	23.181		
Technological content knowledge	Between	12.522	6.261	0.375	NS
	Within	11915.12	16.711		
Pedagogical content knowledge	Between	170.638	85.319	3.475	S
	Within	17506.13	24.553		
Technological pedagogical content knowledge	Between	38.772	19.386	0.919	NS
	Within	15039.35	21.093		

(At 5% level of significance for 2, 934 df, the table value of 'F' is 3.00)

It is inferred from the Table 4.2.7.1 that there was significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, as the calculated 'F' values of 7.475 and 3.475 was greater than the table value of 3.00 at 5% level of significance. *Hence the null hypothesis 7.1b and 7.1f was rejected.*

Further, there was no significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their technological knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge, as the calculated 'F' values of 2.846, 2.216, 0.417, 0.375 and 0.919 was less than the table value of 3.00 at 5% level of significance. *Hence the null hypothesis 7.1a, 7.1c, 7.1d, 7.1e and 7.1g was accepted.*

4.2.8 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Parental Education of Student Teachers with regards to School Education, Undergraduate and Postgraduate

NULL HYPOTHESIS 8

There is no significant association among parental education of student teachers with regards to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 8.1a

There is no significant association among parental education of student teachers with regard to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their technological knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 8.1b

There is no significant association among parental education of student teachers with regard to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 8.1c

There is no significant association among parental education of student teachers with regard to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 8.1d

There is no significant association among parental education of student teachers with regard to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 9.1e

There is no significant association among parental education of student teachers with regard to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 8.1f

There is no significant association among parental education of student teachers with regard to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 8.1g

There is no significant association among parental education of student teachers with regard to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.2.8.1

ASSOCIATION AMONG PARENTAL EDUCATION OF STUDENT TEACHERS WITH REGARD TO SCHOOL EDUCATION, UNDERGRADUATE AND POSTGRADUATE IN THEIR TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE

Variable	Calculated χ^2 Value	Remarks at 5% level
Technological Knowledge	73.03	S
Pedagogical Knowledge	74.68	S
Content Knowledge	51.85	S
Technological pedagogical knowledge	43.55	S
Technological content knowledge	67.32	S
Pedagogical content knowledge	69.52	S
Technological pedagogical content knowledge	61.53	S

(At 5% level of significance, for 4 df, the table value of ' χ^2 ' is 9.488)

It is inferred from the Table 4.2.8.1 that there was significant association among parental education of student teachers with regard school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge, as the calculated ' χ^2 ' values of 73.03, 74.68, 51.85, 43.55, 67.37, 69.52 and 61.53 was greater than the table value of 9.488 at 5% level of significance. *Hence the null hypothesis 8.1a, 8.1b, 8.1c, 8.1d, 8.1e, 8.1f and 8.1g was rejected.*

4.2.9 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Parental Occupation of Student Teachers with regard to Daily Wages, Private and Government

NULL HYPOTHESIS 9

There is no significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard to daily wages, private and government in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 9.1a

There is no significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard to daily wages, private and government in their technological knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 9.1b

There is no significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard to daily wages, private and government in their pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 9.1c

There is no significant association among parental education of student teachers with regard to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 9.1d

There is no significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard to daily wages, private and government in their technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 9.1e

There is no significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard to daily wages, private and government in their technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 9.1f

There is no significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard to daily wages, private and government in their pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 9.1g

There is no significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard to daily wages, private and government in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.2.9.1
ASSOCIATION AMONG PARENTAL OCCUPATION OF STUDENT TEACHERS WITH REGARD TO DAILY WAGES, PRIVATE AND GOVERNMENT IN THEIR TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE

Variable	Calculated χ^2 Value	Remarks at 5% level
Technological Knowledge	59.90	S
Pedagogical Knowledge	71.20	S
Content Knowledge	53.37	S
Technological pedagogical knowledge	62.18	S
Technological content knowledge	72.29	S
Pedagogical content knowledge	57.02	S
Technological pedagogical content knowledge	46.20	S

(At 5% level of significance, for 4 df, the table value of ' χ^2 ' is 9.488)

It is inferred from the Table 4.2.9.1 that there was significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard daily wages, private and government in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge, as the calculated ' χ^2 ' values of 59.90, 71.20, 53.37, 62.18, 72.29, 57.02 and 46.20 was greater than the table value of 9.488 at 5% level of significance. *Hence the null hypothesis 9.1a, 9.1b, 9.1c, 9.1d, 9.1e, 9.1f and 9.1g was rejected.*

4.3 CORRELATIONAL ANALYSIS

NULL HYPOTHESIS 10

There is no significant relationship between male and female student teachers in their technological knowledge and pedagogical knowledge, technological knowledge and content knowledge, technological knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, technological knowledge and technological content knowledge, technological knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 10.1a

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological knowledge and pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 10.1b

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological knowledge and content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 10.1c

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 10.1d

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 10.1e

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 10.1f

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.3.1

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE,

**TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL
CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF MALE STUDENT TEACHERS**

Sub Dimensions	Technological Knowledge	Remarks at 5% Level
Pedagogical Knowledge	0.334**	S
Content Knowledge	0.365**	S
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	0.454**	S
Technological Content Knowledge	0.403**	S
Pedagogical content Knowledge	0.267**	S
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.309**	S

**** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)**

From the table 4.3.1 it is inferred that there is significant relationship between technological knowledge and pedagogical knowledge, Technological knowledge and content knowledge, technological knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, technological knowledge and technological content knowledge, technological knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of male student teachers, as the calculated ‘ γ ’ values 0.334, 0.365, 0.454, 0.403, 0.267 and 0.309 was significant at 1% level. **Hence the null hypothesis 10.1a, 10.1b, 10.1c, 10.1d, 10.1e and 10.1f was rejected.**

NULL HYPOTHESIS 10.2a

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological knowledge and pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 10.2b

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological knowledge and content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 10.2c

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 10.2d

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 10.2e

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 10.2f

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.3.2

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF FEMALE STUDENT TEACHERS

Sub Dimensions	Technological Knowledge	Remarks at 5% Level
Pedagogical Knowledge	0.344**	S
Content Knowledge	0.377**	S
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	0.424**	S
Technological Content Knowledge	0.368**	S
Pedagogical content Knowledge	0.347**	S
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.329**	S

**** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)**

From the table 4.3.2 it is inferred that there is significant relationship between technological knowledge and pedagogical knowledge, Technological knowledge and content knowledge, technological knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, technological

knowledge and technological content knowledge, technological knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of female student teachers, as the calculated ' γ ' values 0.344, 0.377, 0.424, 0.368, 0.347 and 0.329 was significant at 1% level. *Hence the null hypothesis 10.2a, 10.2b, 10.2c, 10.2d, 10.2e and 10.2f was rejected.*

NULL HYPOTHESIS 11

There is no significant relationship between male and female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 11.1a

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 11.1b

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 11.1c

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 11.1d

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 11.1e

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.3.3

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND

TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF MALE STUDENT TEACHERS

Sub Dimensions	Pedagogical Knowledge	Remarks at 5% Level
Content Knowledge	0.475**	S
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	0.477**	S
Technological Content Knowledge	0.310**	S
Pedagogical content Knowledge	0.397**	S
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.429**	S

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

From the table 4.3.3 it is inferred that there is significant relationship between pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of male student teachers, as the calculated ‘ γ ’ values 0.475, 0.477, 0.310, 0.397 and 0.429 was significant at 1% level. **Hence the null hypothesis 11.1a, 11.1b, 11.1c, 11.1d and 11.1e was rejected.**

NULL HYPOTHESIS 11.2a

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 11.2b

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 11.2c

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 11.2d

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 11.2e

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.3.4

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF FEMALE STUDENT TEACHERS

Sub Dimensions	Technological Knowledge	Remarks at 5% Level
Content Knowledge	0.502**	S
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	0.532**	S
Technological Content Knowledge	0.407**	S
Pedagogical content Knowledge	0.419**	S
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.381**	S

**** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)**

From the table 4.3.4 it is inferred that there is significant relationship between pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of female student teachers, as the calculated ' γ ' 0.502, 0.532, 0.407, 0.419 and 0.381 was significant at 1% level. **Hence the null hypothesis 11.2a, 11.2b, 11.2c, 11.2d and 11.2e was rejected.**

NULL HYPOTHESIS 12

There is no significant relationship between male and female student teachers in their content knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge and technological content knowledge, content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 12.1a

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their content knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 12.1b

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their content knowledge and technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 12.1c

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 12.1d

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.3.5

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF MALE STUDENT TEACHERS

Sub Dimensions	Content Knowledge	Remarks at 5% Level
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	0.461**	S
Technological Content Knowledge	0.470**	S
Pedagogical content Knowledge	0.369**	S
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.563**	S

**** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)**

From the table 4.3.5 it is inferred that there is significant relationship between content knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge and technological content knowledge, content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of male student teachers, as the calculated ‘ γ ’ values 0.461, 0.470, 0.369 and 0.563 was significant at 1% level. **Hence the null hypothesis 12.1a, 12.1b, 12.1c and 12.1d was rejected.**

NULL HYPOTHESIS 12.2a

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their content knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 12.2b

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their content knowledge and technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 12.2c

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 12.2d

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.3.6

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF FEMALE STUDENT TEACHERS

Sub Dimensions	Content Knowledge	Remarks at 5% Level
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	0.458**	S
Technological Content Knowledge	0.438**	S
Pedagogical content Knowledge	0.456**	S
Technological Pedagogical	0.390**	S

Content Knowledge		
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**** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)**

From the table 4.3.6 it is inferred that there is significant relationship between content knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge and technological content knowledge, content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of female student teachers, as the calculated ‘ γ ’ values 0.458, 0.438, 0.456 and 0.390 was significant at 1% level. ***Hence the null hypothesis 12.2a, 12.2b, 12.2c and 12.2d was rejected.***

NULL HYPOTHESIS 13

There is no significant relationship between male and female student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 13.1a

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 13.1b

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 13.1c

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.3.7
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF MALE STUDENT TEACHERS

Sub Dimensions	Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	Remarks at 5% Level
Technological Content Knowledge	0.407**	S
Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.469**	S
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.563**	S

** *Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)* **Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

From the table 4.3.7 it is inferred that there is significant relationship between technological pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of male student teachers, as the calculated ‘ γ ’ values 0.407, 0.469 and 0.563 was significant at 1% level. ***Hence the null hypothesis 13.1a, 13.1b and 13.1c was rejected.***

NULL HYPOTHESIS 13.2a

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 13.2b

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 13.2c

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.3.8
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF FEMALE STUDENT TEACHERS

Sub Dimensions	Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	Remarks at 5% Level
Technological Content Knowledge	0.439**	S
Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.421**	S
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.440**	S

** *Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)* **Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

From the table 4.3.8 it is inferred that there is significant relationship between technological pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of female student teachers, as the calculated ‘ γ ’ values 0.439, 0.421 and 0.440 was significant at 1% level. ***Hence the null hypothesis 13.2a, 13.2b and 13.2c was rejected.***

NULL HYPOTHESIS 14

There is no significant relationship between male and female student teachers in their technological content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 14.1a

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 14.1b

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.3.9
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND
PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT
KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE
OF MALE STUDENT TEACHERS

Sub Dimensions	Technological Content Knowledge	Remarks at 5% Level
Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.388**	S
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.452**	S

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

From the table 4.3.9 it is inferred that there is significant relationship between technological content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of male student teachers, as the calculated ‘ γ ’ values 0.388 and 0.452 are significant at 5% level. *Hence the null hypothesis 14.1a and 14.1b was rejected.*

NULL HYPOTHESIS 14.2a

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 14.2b

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.3.10
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AND
PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF FEMALE STUDENT
TEACHERS

Sub Dimensions	Technological Content Knowledge	Remarks at 5% Level
Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.374**	S
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.437**	S

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

From the table 4.3.10 it is inferred that there is significant relationship technological content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of female student teachers, as the calculated ‘ γ ’ values 0.374 and 0.437 are significant at 5% level. *Hence the null hypothesis 14.2a and 14.2b was rejected.*

NULL HYPOTHESIS 15

There is no significant relationship between male and female student teachers in their pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 15.1a

There is no significant relationship between male student teachers in their pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.3.11
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND
TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF MALE
STUDENT TEACHERS

Sub dimensions of TPACK	Pedagogical Content Knowledge	Remarks at 5% Level
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.643**	S

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

From the table 4.3.11 it is inferred that there is significant relationship between pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of male student teachers, as the calculated ‘ γ ’ value 0.643 are significant at 1% level. *Hence the null hypothesis 15.1a was rejected.*

NULL HYPOTHESIS 15.2a

There is no significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Table 4.3.12
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND
TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF FEMALE
STUDENT TEACHERS

Sub dimensions of TPACK	Pedagogical Content Knowledge	Remarks at 5% Level
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.575**	S

** *Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)* **Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

From the table 4.3.12 it is inferred that there is significant relationship between pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of female student teachers, as the calculated ‘ γ ’ value 0.575 are significant at 1% level. *Hence the null hypothesis 15.2a was rejected.*

4.4 MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

4.4.1 Influence of Technological Knowledge, Pedagogical Knowledge, Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Knowledge, Technological Content Knowledge, Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge on Academic Achievement Score of Male and Female Student Teachers

NULL HYPOTHESIS 16

There is no significant influence of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge on academic achievement score of male and female student teachers.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 16.1a

There is no significant influence of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge on academic achievement score of male student teachers.

Table 4.4.1.1a

INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT SCORE OF MALE STUDENT TEACHERS - MODEL SUMMARY

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error
1	0.098	0.010	0.017	31.574

Table 4.4.1.1b

INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT SCORE OF MALE STUDENT TEACHERS – ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Significance
1	Regression	2524.98	360.71	0.362	NS
	Residual	260209.77	996.97		
	Total	262734.75			

Table 4.4.1.1c

INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT SCORE OF MALE STUDENT TEACHERS – COEFFICIENTS

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	‘t’	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	514.53	17.341			
Technological Knowledge	0.007	0.475	0.001	0.014	NS
Pedagogical Knowledge	0.628	0.515	0.093	1.219	NS
Content Knowledge	0.024	0.703	0.003	0.034	NS
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	0.023	0.562	0.003	0.041	NS
Technological Content Knowledge	0.192	0.590	0.025	0.326	NS
Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.103	0.510	0.017	0.201	NS

Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.536	0.574	0.084	0.933	NS
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From the above table 4.4.1.1a is observed that the adjusted R Square value 0.010 indicates that 0.17% of the variance could be predicted that technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge on academic achievement score of male student teachers.

It is also inferred from the above table 4.4.1.1a that the multiple correlation co-efficient (0.098) shows that there is a low correlation found among technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge and academic achievement score of male student teachers.

It is learnt from the above table 4.4.1.1b that the significant 'P' value 0.924 for ANOVA ('F' value = 0.362) indicates that technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge was differ in their influence on academic achievement score of male student teachers.

It is understood from the above table 4.4.1.1c that the technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge not significantly influences the academic achievement score of male student teachers. *Hence the null hypothesis 16.1a is rejected.*

NULL HYPOTHESIS 16.1b

There is no significant influence of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge on academic achievement score of female student teachers.

Table 4.4.1.2a

INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT SCORE OF FEMALE STUDENT TEACHERS - MODEL SUMMARY

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error
1	0.129	0.017	0.001	33.2212

Table 4.4.1.2b

INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT SCORE OF FEMALE STUDENT TEACHERS – ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Significance
1	Regression	8151.565	1164.509	1.055	NS
	Residual	484502.851	1103.651		
	Total	492654.416			

Table 4.4.1.2c

INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE, PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT SCORE OF FEMALE STUDENT TEACHERS – COEFFICIENTS

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	‘t’	Sig. ‘p’
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	541.614	14.887			
Technological Knowledge	0.250	0.385	0.036	0.648	
Pedagogical Knowledge	0.087	0.454	0.012	0.191	
Content Knowledge	0.084	0.529	0.010	0.160	
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	0.149	0.423	0.022	0.353	
Technological Content Knowledge	0.654	0.469	0.081	1.393	
Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.328	0.426	0.048	0.769	
Technological Pedagogical	0.863	0.473	0.113	1.825	

Content Knowledge					
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From the above table 4.4.1.2a is observed that the adjusted R Square value 0.001 indicates that 0.01% of the variance could be predicted that technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge on academic achievement score of female student teachers.

It is also inferred from the above table 4.4.1.2a that the multiple correlation co-efficient (0.129) shows that there is a low correlation found among technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge and academic achievement score of female student teachers.

It is learnt from the above table 4.4.1.2b that the significant 'P' value 0.392 for ANOVA ('F' value=1.055) indicates that technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge and academic achievement score of female student teachers.

It is understood from the above table 4.4.1.2c that the technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge not significantly influences academic achievement score of female student teachers. ***Hence the null hypothesis 16.1b was accepted.***

4.5 CONCLUSION

Through the analyses of data, the investigator has arrived at a set of findings regarding technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge. The succeeding chapter deals with the major findings of the study, the interpretations of the findings, recommendations and suggestions for the further researchers.

CHAPTER V

FINDINGS, INTERPRETATIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

5.1 INTRODUCTION

The Investigator studied the technological pedagogical content knowledge of student teachers. The findings of the study are based on the analysis of data collected through the administration of questionnaires on the selected sample of student teachers studying their bachelor of education from Tamilnadu Teachers Education University affiliated colleges of education at Tiruchirappalli district. Findings of the present study are given below.

5.2 MAJOR FINDINGS

5.2.1 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student Teachers

- I. With regard to male student teachers reported 56.1 percent of them were gathered moderate level of technological knowledge. Whereas female student teachers reported 54.6 percent of them were gathered moderate level of technological knowledge.
- ii. With regard to male student teachers reported 70.2 percent of them were achieved moderate level of pedagogical knowledge. Whereas female student teachers reported 50.8 percent of them were achieved moderate level of pedagogical knowledge.
- iii. With regard to male student teachers reported 50.5 percent of them were moderate level of content knowledge. Whereas female student teachers reported 62 percent of them were moderate level of content knowledge.
- iv. With regard to male student teachers reported 53.2 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical knowledge. Whereas female student teachers reported 53.7 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical knowledge.
- v. With regard to male student teachers reported 65.1 percent of them were moderate level of technological content knowledge. Whereas female student teachers reported 63.5 percent of them were moderate level of technological content knowledge.
- vi. With regard to male student teachers reported 60.6 percent of them were moderate level of pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas female student teachers reported 53.7 percent of them were moderate level of pedagogical content knowledge.

- vii. With regard to male student teachers reported 54.3 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas female student teachers reported 61.3 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical content knowledge.
- 1.1a There is no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their technological knowledge.
- 1.1b There is significant difference between male and female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge.
- 1.1c There is significant difference between male and female student teachers in their content knowledge.
- 1.1d There is no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge.
- 1.1e There is significant difference between male and female student teachers in their technological content knowledge.
- 1.1f There is significant difference between male and female student teachers in their pedagogical content knowledge.
- 1.1g There is significant difference between male and female student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.2.2 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Married and Unmarried Student Teachers

- I. With regard to married student teachers reported 60.9 percent of them were gathered moderate level of technological knowledge. Whereas unmarried student teachers reported 56.1 percent of them were gathered moderate level of technological knowledge.
- ii. With regard to married student teachers reported 58.4 percent of them were achieved moderate level of pedagogical knowledge. Whereas unmarried student teachers reported 55.7 percent of them were achieved moderate level of pedagogical knowledge.
- iii. With regard to married student teachers reported 52.8 percent of them were moderate level of content knowledge. Whereas unmarried student teachers reported 67.5 percent of them were moderate level of content knowledge.

- iv. With regard to married student teachers reported 56.2 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical knowledge. Whereas unmarried student teachers reported 54 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical knowledge.
 - v. With regard to married student teachers reported 67.8 percent of them were moderate level of technological content knowledge. Whereas unmarried student teachers reported 62.3 percent of them were moderate level of technological content knowledge.
 - vi. With regard to married student teachers reported 45.5 percent of them were moderate level of pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas unmarried student teachers reported 52.8 percent of them were moderate level of pedagogical content knowledge.
 - vii. With regard to married student teachers reported 51.9 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas unmarried student teachers reported 57.4 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical content knowledge.
- 2.1a There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their technological knowledge.
 - 2.1b There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge.
 - 2.1c There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their content knowledge.
 - 2.1d There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge.
 - 2.1e There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their technological content knowledge.
 - 2.1f There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their pedagogical content knowledge.
 - 2.1g There is no significant difference between married and unmarried student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.2.3 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Undergraduate and Postgraduate studied Student Teachers

- I. With regard to undergraduate student teachers reported 58.3 percent of them were gathered moderate level of technological knowledge. Whereas postgraduate student teachers reported 51.9 percent of them were gathered moderate level of technological knowledge.
 - ii. With regard to undergraduate student teachers reported 55.9 percent of them were achieved moderate level of pedagogical knowledge. Whereas postgraduate student teachers reported 55.9 percent of them were achieved moderate level of pedagogical knowledge.
 - iii. With regard to undergraduate student teachers reported 51.8 percent of them were moderate level of content knowledge. Whereas postgraduate student teachers reported 53.1 percent of them were moderate level of content knowledge.
 - iv. With regard to undergraduate student teachers reported 54.4 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical knowledge. Whereas postgraduate student teachers reported 55.9 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical knowledge.
 - v. With regard to undergraduate student teachers reported 48.8 percent of them were moderate level of technological content knowledge. Whereas postgraduate student teachers reported 60.9 percent of them were moderate level of technological content knowledge.
 - vi. With regard to undergraduate student teachers reported 48.8 percent of them were moderate level of pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas postgraduate student teachers reported 68.2 percent of them were moderate level of pedagogical content knowledge.
 - vii. With regard to undergraduate student teachers reported 54.6 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas postgraduate student teachers reported 54.2 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical content knowledge.
- 3.1a There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate studied student teachers in their technological knowledge.

- 3.1b There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate studied student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge.
- 3.1c There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate studied student teachers in their content knowledge.
- 3.1d There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate studied student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge.
- 3.1e There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate studied student teachers in their technological content knowledge.
- 3.1f There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate studied student teachers in their pedagogical content knowledge.
- 3.1g There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate studied student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.2.4 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Tamil and English Medium Studying Student Teachers

- I. With regard to Tamil medium studying student teachers reported 54.5 percent of them were gathered moderate level of technological knowledge. Whereas English medium studying student teachers reported 55.9 percent of them were gathered moderate level of technological knowledge.
- ii. With regard to Tamil medium studying student teachers reported 64.5 percent of them were achieved moderate level of pedagogical knowledge. Whereas English medium studying student teachers reported 55.3 percent of them were achieved moderate level of pedagogical knowledge.
- iii. With regard to Tamil medium studying student teachers reported 49.6 percent of them were moderate level of content knowledge. Whereas English medium studying student teachers reported 54.8 percent of them were moderate level of content knowledge.
- iv. With regard to Tamil medium studying student teachers reported 53.1 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical knowledge. Whereas English medium studying student teachers reported 56.5 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical knowledge.

- v. With regard to Tamil medium studying student teachers reported 48.5 percent of them were moderate level of technological content knowledge. Whereas English medium studying student teachers reported 65.7 percent of them were moderate level of technological content knowledge.
 - vi. With regard to Tamil medium studying student teachers reported 63.1 percent of them were moderate level of pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas English medium studying student teachers reported 49.9 percent of them were moderate level of pedagogical content knowledge.
 - vii. With regard to Tamil medium studying student teachers reported 53.4 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas English medium studying student teachers reported 53 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical content knowledge.
- 4.1a There is significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their technological knowledge.
 - 4.1b There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge.
 - 4.1c There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their content knowledge.
 - 4.1d There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge.
 - 4.1e There is significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their technological content knowledge.
 - 4.1f There is significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their pedagogical content knowledge.
 - 4.1g There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium studying student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.2.5 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Rural and Urban Student Teachers

- I. With regard to rural student teachers reported 57.6 percent of them were gathered moderate level of technological knowledge. Whereas urban student teachers reported 51.2 percent of them were gathered moderate level of technological knowledge.

- ii. With regard to rural student teachers reported 57.8 percent of them were achieved moderate level of pedagogical knowledge. Whereas urban student teachers reported 52.6 percent of them were achieved moderate level of pedagogical knowledge.
 - iii. With regard to rural student teachers reported 53.2 percent of them were moderate level of content knowledge. Whereas urban student teachers reported 50.4 percent of them were moderate level of content knowledge.
 - iv. With regard to rural student teachers reported 64.9 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical knowledge. Whereas urban student teachers reported 62.4 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical knowledge.
 - v. With regard to rural student teachers reported 50.7 percent of them were moderate level of technological content knowledge. Whereas urban student teachers reported 41 percent of them were moderate level of technological content knowledge.
 - vi. With regard to rural student teachers reported 49.6 percent of them were moderate level of pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas urban student teachers reported 51.9 percent of them were moderate level of pedagogical content knowledge.
 - vii. With regard to rural student teachers reported 53.8 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical content knowledge. Whereas urban student teachers reported 52.3 percent of them were moderate level of technological pedagogical content knowledge.
- 5.1a There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their technological knowledge.
 - 5.1b There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge.
 - 5.1c There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their content knowledge.
 - 5.1d There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge.
 - 5.1e There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their technological content knowledge.

5.1f There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their pedagogical content knowledge.

5.1g There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.2.6 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Student Teachers having Age Group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above

6.1a There is no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their technological knowledge.

6.1b There is no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their pedagogical knowledge.

6.1c There is no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their content knowledge.

6.1d There is no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their technological pedagogical knowledge.

6.1e There is no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their technological content knowledge.

6.1f There is no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their pedagogical content knowledge.

6.1g There is no significant difference among student teachers having age group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.2.7 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Student Teachers Studying Languages, Arts and Science Subjects

7.1a There is no significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their technological knowledge.

7.1b There is significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their pedagogical knowledge.

- 7.1c There is no significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their content knowledge.
- 7.1d There is no significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their technological pedagogical knowledge.
- 7.1e There is no significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their technological content knowledge.
- 7.1f There is significant difference among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their pedagogical content knowledge.
- 7.1g There is no significant among student teachers studying languages, arts and science subjects in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.2.8 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Parental Education of Student Teachers with regards to School Education, Undergraduate and Postgraduate

- 8.1a There is significant association among parental education of student teachers with regards to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their technological knowledge.
- 8.1b There is significant association among parental education of student teachers with regards to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their pedagogical knowledge.
- 8.1c There is significant association among parental education of student teachers with regards to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their content knowledge.
- 8.1d There is significant association among parental education of student teachers with regards to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their technological pedagogical knowledge.
- 8.1e There is significant association among parental education of student teachers with regards to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their technological content knowledge.
- 8.1f There is significant association among parental education of student teachers with regards to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their pedagogical content knowledge.

8.1g There is significant association among parental education of student teachers with regards to school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.2.9 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Parental Occupation of Student Teachers with regard to Daily Wages, Private and Government

9.1a There is significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard to daily wages, private and government in their technological knowledge.

9.1b There is significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard to daily wages, private and government in their pedagogical knowledge.

9.1c There is significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard to daily wages, private and government in their content knowledge.

9.1d There is significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard to daily wages, private and government in their technologic pedagogical knowledge.

9.1e There is significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard to daily wages, private and government in their technologica content knowledge.

9.1f There is significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard to daily wages, private and government in their pedagogical content knowledge.

9.1g There is significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard to daily wages, private and government in their technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.3.1 Relationship between Technological Knowledge and Pedagogical Knowledge, Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Knowledge, Technological Content Knowledge, Pedagogical Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student Teachers

10.1a There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological knowledge and pedagogical knowledge.

10.1b There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological knowledge and content knowledge.

10.1c There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge.

- 10.1d There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological content knowledge.
- 10.1e There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.
- 10.1f There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
- 10.2a There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological knowledge and pedagogical knowledge.
- 10.2b There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological knowledge and content knowledge.
- 10.2c There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge.
- 10.2d There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological content knowledge.
- 10.2e There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.
- 10.2f There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.3.2 Relationship between Pedagogical Knowledge and Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Knowledge, Technological Content Knowledge, Pedagogical Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student Teachers

- 11.1a There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge.
- 11.1b There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge.
- 11.1c There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge.
- 11.1d There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

- 11.1e There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
- 11.2a There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge.
- 11.2b There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge.
- 11.2c There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge.
- 11.2d There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.
- 11.2e There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.3.3 Relationship between Content Knowledge and Technological Pedagogical Knowledge, Technological Content Knowledge, Pedagogical Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student Teachers

- 12.1a There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their content knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge.
- 12.1b There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their content knowledge and technological content knowledge.
- 12.1c There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.
- 12.1d There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
- 12.2a There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their content knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge.
- 12.2b There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their content knowledge and technological content knowledge.
- 12.2c There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

12.2d There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.3.4 Relationship between Technological Pedagogical Knowledge and Technological Content Knowledge, Pedagogical Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student Teachers

13.1a There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge.

13.1b There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

13.1c There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

13.2a There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge.

13.2b There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

13.2c There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.3.5 Relationship between Technological Content Knowledge and Pedagogical Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student Teachers

14.1a There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

14.1b There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their technological content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

14.2a There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

14.2b There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.3.6 Relationship between Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student Teachers

- 15.1 There is significant relationship between male student teachers in their pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.
- 15.2 There is significant relationship between female student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.4 MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

5.4.1 Influence of Technological Knowledge, Pedagogical Knowledge, Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Knowledge, Technological Content Knowledge, Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge on Academic Achievement Score of Male and Female Student Teachers

- 16.1a There is no significant influence of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge on academic achievement score of male student teachers.
- 16.1b There is no significant influence of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge on academic achievement score of female student teachers.

5.5 INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION

The Investigator with her observations and field experience has come out with the following interpretations derived from the present study.

5.5.1 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student Teachers

The percentage analysis of the study revealed that majority of the male and female student teachers experienced moderate level of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge as shown in the Table 4.2.1.1. The pervasiveness of technological pedagogical content knowledge at moderate level among male and female student teachers may be because that they were born in

the era of millennial. Further, they might have been availed with ample opportunities to understand the concept and the significance of the techno pedagogy in their teaching learning process.

The 't' test results with regard to gender, demonstrated that there was no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their technological knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, whereas there was significant difference between male and female student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge and experienced female student teachers higher levels than their male counterparts. It implied that female student teachers of colleges of education are interested in techno pedagogical practices than their men counterparts. The reason may be that female student teachers of colleges of education could observe the modern trends of techno pedagogical contents and their scope. They also executed their academic activities assigned to them by their heads with more diligence and care with the help of technological platform. This habit of doing the academic activities with sincerity and care might have helped them in understanding their needs and gaining better knowledge than men teachers.

5.5.2 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Married and Unmarried Student Teachers

The percentage analysis of the study revealed that majority of the married and unmarried student teachers expertise moderate level of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge as shown in the Table 4.2.2.1. The reason behind that today technology enhancement is to be occupy toddler to senior citizen in their day to day activities like games, shopping, alarm, calendar, astrology, kitchen utilities and methods to preparation of dishes, exercise etc.

The 't' test results with respect to marital status of the student teachers found that there was no significant difference in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of student teachers of colleges of education.

5.5.3 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Undergraduate and Postgraduate Student Teachers

The percentage analysis of the study revealed that majority of the undergraduate and postgraduate student teachers enhanced moderate level of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge as shown in the Table 4.2.3.1. The reason behind that technology has become an increasingly important part of students' lives beyond school, and even within the classroom it can also help increase their understanding of complex concepts or encourage collaboration among peers. Because of these benefits, current educational practice suggests that teachers implement some form of technology in their classrooms.

The 't' test results with regard to qualification, demonstrated that there was no significant difference between undergraduate and post graduate student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of student teachers of colleges of education.

5.5.4 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Tamil and English medium Student Teachers

The percentage analysis of the study revealed that majority of the Tamil and English medium studied student teachers fluent moderate level of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge as shown in the Table 4.2.4.1. The reason behind that technology is apart from that the languages. In studying language and technology, we look at how the technology influences the language use, but we should not assume that the use of technology to mediate the language necessarily changes everything. Generally speaking, English is the universal language on the Internet, but it has no official status, and it will never have. Linguistically, English is extremely unsuitable for international communication, and the actual wide use of English tends to polarize the world into Internet users and Internet illiterates. The position of English can only be altered by major world-scale political and economic changes.

The 't' test results with regard to qualification, demonstrated that there was no significant difference between Tamil and English medium studied student teachers in their pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, and technological pedagogical content knowledge of student teachers of colleges of education, whereas there was significant difference between Tamil and English medium studied student teachers in their technological knowledge, technological content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.

5.5.5 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Rural and Urban Student Teachers

The percentage analysis of the study revealed that majority of the rural and urban student teachers enriched moderate level of technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge as shown in the Table 4.2.5.1. The reason behind that

The 't' test results with regard to qualification, demonstrated that there was no significant difference between undergraduate and post graduate student teachers in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of student teachers of colleges of education.

5.5.6 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Student Teachers having Age Group of 25 years and below, 26-30 years and 31 years and above

The 'F' test results with respect to the student teachers having age group revealed that there was no significant difference among student teachers of colleges of education based on their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge. The reason behind that age does not influence any significant change for technology integration of daily life. The use technology such as computers or the Internet puts older adults at a disadvantage in terms of their ability to live and function independently and successfully perform everyday tasks. Further, older populations may not realize the full benefits of available technologies. Technology has the potential of increasing the quality of life for older people. The Internet can help mitigate problems with social isolation, foster linkages to family and friends, and facilitate the performance of essential activities such as

banking and shopping. The Internet can also enhance educational opportunities for older adults and enable them to take a more active role in their own health care.

5.5.7 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Student Teachers Studying Languages, Arts and Science Subjects

The 'F' test results with respect to the languages, arts and science subject studying student teachers revealed that there was no significant difference among student teachers of colleges of education based on their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge. The reason behind that age does not influence any significant change for technology integration of daily life.

5.5.8 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Parental Education of Student Teachers with regards to School Education, Undergraduate and Postgraduate

The ' χ^2 ' test results revealed that there was significant association among parental education of student teachers with regard school education, undergraduate and postgraduate in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.5.9 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Parental Occupation of Student Teachers with regard to Daily Wages, Private and Government

The ' χ^2 ' test results revealed that there was significant association among parental occupation of student teachers with regard daily wages, private and government in their technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge.

5.5.10 Relationship between Technological Knowledge and Pedagogical Knowledge, Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Knowledge, Technological Content Knowledge, Pedagogical Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student teachers

The ' γ ' test results revealed that there is significant relationship between technological knowledge and pedagogical knowledge, Technological knowledge and content knowledge, technological knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, technological knowledge

and technological content knowledge, technological knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of male student teachers.

Similarly, the ‘ γ ’ test results revealed that there is significant relationship between technological knowledge and pedagogical knowledge, Technological knowledge and content knowledge, technological knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, technological knowledge and technological content knowledge, technological knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of female student teachers.

5.5.11 Relationship between Pedagogical Knowledge and Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Knowledge, Technological Content Knowledge, Pedagogical Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student teachers

The ‘ γ ’ test results revealed that there is significant relationship between pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of male student teachers.

Similarly, the ‘ γ ’ test results revealed that there is significant relationship between pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of female student teachers.

5.5.12 Relationship between Content Knowledge and Technological Pedagogical Knowledge, Technological Content Knowledge, Pedagogical Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student teachers

The ‘ γ ’ test results revealed that there is significant relationship between content knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge and technological content knowledge, content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of male student teachers.

Similarly, the ‘ γ ’ test results revealed that there is significant relationship between content knowledge and technological pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge and technological content knowledge, content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of female student teachers.

5.5.13 Relationship between Technological Pedagogical Knowledge and Technological Content Knowledge, Pedagogical Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student teachers

The ‘ γ ’ test results revealed that there is significant relationship between technological pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of male student teachers.

Similarly, the ‘ γ ’ test results revealed that there is significant relationship between technological pedagogical knowledge and technological content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of female student teachers.

5.5.14 Relationship between Technological Content Knowledge and Pedagogical Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student teachers

The ‘ γ ’ test results revealed that there is significant relationship between technological content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of male student teachers.

Similarly, the ‘ γ ’ test results revealed that there is significant relationship between technological content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge, technological content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of female student teachers.

5.5.15 Relationship between Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Male and Female Student teachers

The ‘ γ ’ test results revealed that there is significant relationship between pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of male student teachers.

Similarly, the ‘ γ ’ test results revealed that there is significant relationship between pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge of male student teachers.

5.5.16 Influence of Technological Knowledge, Pedagogical Knowledge, Content Knowledge, Technological Pedagogical Knowledge, Technological Content Knowledge, Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge on Academic Achievement Score of Male and Female Student Teachers

The technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge not significantly influences the academic achievement score of male student teachers.

Similarly, The technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and technological pedagogical content knowledge not significantly influences the academic achievement score of female student teachers.

5.4 RECOMMENDATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

Based on the findings of the present study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The present study indicates that technological pedagogical content knowledge play a prominent role in influencing the academic achievement of student teachers and therefore, students with good technological pedagogical content knowledge may be encouraged to enter the teaching profession.
2. Quality of any educational institution is determined by the role played by its teachers. Therefore, it is a must for the authorities concerned to be impartial in recruiting qualified teachers and select only those individuals who satisfied the criteria of good technological knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge.
3. The existing training programme is not adequate to provide adequate opportunities to teachers to develop pedagogical knowledge, to face the varied situations in their real teaching life. It seems that the entire teacher education programme in our country lack professionalization, which is extremely essential for a sound teacher education programme.
4. Teaching is considered to be a noble profession. It is one of those professions, which confers special privileges as well as obligations on those who practice it. Hence, the teachers should understand the importance of pedagogical content knowledge and the ways to achieve satisfaction in their job.

5. The quality of any educational institution is determined by the technological pedagogical content knowledge of its teachers. Therefore, it is a must for the school or college management and concerned authorities to be impartial in selecting quality faculties and recruiting only those individuals who have appropriate pedagogical content knowledge and passion for teaching.
6. Pedagogical content knowledge of the teachers should be measured from time to time with the help of self-administrated questionnaire and on the basis of the test reports, immediate intervention must be made.
7. Workshops may be organized for increasing teachers' abilities to deal effectively with the demands of educational challenges. In such workshops, teachers should be equipped with latest technologies for enhancing their technological knowledge and reducing their stress due to work overload.
8. The Board of Education and school managements should provide more equipment's, teaching aids and resources for the various subjects so that teachers and students can keep themselves updated and competent.
9. The Board of Education and school managements must help teachers and students to participate in various programmes like seminars, conferences and workshops at national and international levels to make them updated and more effective.
10. Techno pedagogy based monitoring system needs to be evolved for quality improvement at school and college levels, because techno pedagogy is an essential aspect for qualitative improvement in education. Well planned in-service training and orientation programmes may be organized to enrich pedagogical content knowledge in school teachers.

5.5 SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Research studies may be conducted under the following headings:

1. Similar type of studies may be extended to other colleges and universities exploring the same field of investigation.
2. Influence of pedagogy content on technological pedagogical content knowledge of arts and science college teachers may be studied.
3. Job satisfaction and mental health on technological pedagogical content knowledge of school teachers may be analysed.

4. Technological pedagogical content knowledge of higher secondary teachers in relation to their ICT awareness may be studied.
5. Attitude towards teaching and pedagogical content knowledge of higher secondary education teachers may be studied.
6. Relationship between technological pedagogical content knowledge and emotional maturity of higher secondary teachers may be studied.
7. Influence of self-regulated learning behaviour and pedagogical content knowledge of secondary education teachers may be studied.
8. Metacognition, ICT awareness on pedagogical content knowledge of higher secondary teachers may be studied.
9. Influence of job involvement and adjustment on technological pedagogical content knowledge of university professors may be examined.

5.6 CONCLUSION

As educators know, teaching is a complicated practice that requires an interweaving of many kinds of specialized knowledge. In this way, teaching is an example of an ill-structured discipline, requiring teachers to apply complex knowledge structures across different cases and contexts (Mishra, Spiro, & Feltovich, 1996; Spiro & Jehng, 1990). Teachers practice their craft in highly complex, dynamic classroom contexts (Leinhardt & Greeno, 1986) that require them constantly to shift and evolve their understanding. Thus, effective teaching depends on flexible access to rich, well-organized and integrated knowledge from different domains (Glaser, 1984; Putnam & Borko, 2000; Shulman, 1986, 1987), including knowledge of student thinking and learning, knowledge of subject matter, and increasingly, knowledge of technology.

Teaching with technology is complicated further considering the challenges newer technologies present to teachers. In our work, the word technology applies equally to analog and digital, as well as new and old, technologies. As a matter of practical significance, however, most of the technologies under consideration in current literature are newer and digital and have some inherent properties that make applying them in straightforward ways difficult.

Most traditional pedagogical technologies are characterized by specificity (a pencil is for writing, while a microscope is for viewing small objects); stability (pencils, pendulums, and chalkboards have not changed a great deal over time); and transparency of function (the inner workings of the pencil or the pendulum are simple and directly related to their function) (Simon,

1969). Over time, these technologies achieve a transparency of perception (Bruce & Hogan, 1998); they become commonplace and, in most cases, are not even considered to be technologies. Digital technologies such as computers, handheld devices, and software applications by contrast, are protean (usable in many different ways; Papert, 1980); unstable (rapidly changing); and opaque (the inner workings are hidden from users; Turkle, 1995). On an academic level, it is easy to argue that a pencil and a software simulation are both technologies. The latter, however, is qualitatively different in that its functioning is more opaque to teachers and offers fundamentally less stability than more traditional technologies. By their very nature, newer digital technologies, which are protean, unstable, and opaque, present new challenges to teachers who are struggling to use more technology in their teaching.

Also complicating teaching with technology is an understanding that technologies are neither neutral nor unbiased. Rather, particular technologies have their own propensities, potentials, affordances, and constraints that make them more suitable for certain tasks than others (Bromley, 1998; Bruce, 1993; Koehler & Mishra, 2008). Using email to communicate, for example, affords (makes possible and supports) asynchronous communication and easy storage of exchanges. Email does not afford synchronous communication in the way that a phone call, a face-to-face conversation, or instant messaging does. Nor does email afford the conveyance of subtleties of tone, intent, or mood possible with face-to-face communication. Understanding how these affordances and constraints of specific technologies influence what teachers do in their classrooms is not straightforward and may require rethinking teacher education and teacher professional development.

Social and contextual factors also complicate the relationships between teaching and technology. Social and institutional contexts are often unsupportive of teachers' efforts to integrate technology use into their work. Teachers often have inadequate (or inappropriate) experience with using digital technologies for teaching and learning. Many teachers earned degrees at a time when educational technology was at a very different stage of development than it is today. It is, thus, not surprising that they do not consider themselves sufficiently prepared to use technology in the classroom and often do not appreciate its value or relevance to teaching and learning. Acquiring a new knowledge base and skill set can be challenging, particularly if it is a time-intensive activity that must fit into a busy schedule. Moreover, this knowledge is unlikely to be used unless teachers can conceive of technology uses that are consistent with their

existing pedagogical beliefs (Ertmer, 2005). Furthermore, teachers have often been provided with inadequate training for this task. Many approaches to teachers' professional development offer a one-size-fits-all approach to technology integration when, in fact, teachers operate in diverse contexts of teaching and learning.

REFERENCES

- Abbitt J. T., (2011), An investigation of the relationship between self-efficacy beliefs about technology integration and technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) among preservice teachers, *J. Digital Learn. Teach. Educ.*, 27(4), 134–143.
- Angeli C. and Valanides N., (2009), Epistemological and methodological issues for the conceptualization, development, and assessment of ICT-TPCK: advances in technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPCK), *Comput. Educ.*, 52, 154–168.
- Archambault L, Crippen K. (2009) Examining TPACK among K-12 online distance educators in the United States. *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 9(1), 71-88
- Archambault L. M., and Barnett J. H., (2010), Revisiting technological pedagogical content knowledge: exploring the TPACK framework, *Comput. Educ.*, 55(4), 1656–1662.
- Bang E. and Luft J., (2013), Secondary science teachers' use of technology in the classroom during their first 5 years, *J. Digital Learn. Teach. Educ.*, 29(4), 118–126.
- Bang E., (2013), Hybrid mentoring programs for beginning elementary science teachers, *Int. J. Math. Educ. Sci. Technol.*, 1(1), 1–15.
- Blonder R. and Rap S., (2015), I like Facebook: exploring Israeli high school chemistry teachers' TPACK and self-efficacy beliefs, *Education and Information Technologies*, 1–29.
- Bruce, B. C., & Hogan, M. C. (1998). The disappearance of technology: Toward an ecological model of literacy. In D. Reinking, M. McKenna, L. Labbo, & R. Kieffer (Eds.), *Handbook of literacy and technology: Transformations in a post-typographic world* (pp. 269-281). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Canbazoglu Bilici S., Yamak H., Kavak N. and Guzey S. S., (2013), Technological pedagogical content knowledge self-efficacy scale (TPACK-SeS) for pre-service science teachers: construction, validation and reliability, *Eurasian J. Educ. Res.*, 52, 37–60.
- Chai C. S., Koh J. H. L. and Tsai C. C., (2013), A review of technological pedagogical content knowledge, *Educ. Technol. Soc.*, 16(2), 31–51.
- Crocker L. and Algina J., (1986), *Introduction to classical and modern test theory*, Holt, Rinehart and Winston, Inc.

- Dalal M., Archambault L. and Shelton C., (2017), Professional Development for International Teachers: Examining TPACK and Technology Integration Decision Making, *J. Res. Technol. Educ.*, 1–17.
- Dori Y. J. and Belcher J., (2005), How does technology-enabled active learning affect undergraduate students' understanding of electromagnetism concepts? *J. Learn. Sci.*, 14(2), 243–279.
- Erdogan A. and Şahin İ., (2010), Relationship between math teacher candidates' Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) and achievement levels, *Procedia Soc. Behav. Sci.*, 2, 2707–2711.
- Ertmer, P. A. (2005). Teacher pedagogical beliefs: The final frontier in our quest for technology integration. *Educational Technology, Research and Development*, 53(4), 25-39.
- Fraenkel J. R., Wallen N. E. and Hyun H., (2011), *How to design and evaluate research in education*, 8th edn, The McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc.
- Graham C. R., (2011), Theoretical considerations for understanding technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK), *Comput. Educ.*, 57, 1953–1960.
- Guzey S. S. and Roehrig G. H., (2009), Teaching science with technology: case studies of science teachers' development of technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge, *Contemp. Issues Technol. Teach. Educ.*, 9(1), 25–45.
- Harris J, Mishra P, Koehler M. (2009) Teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge and learning activity types: Curriculum-based technology integration reframed. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 41(4), 393-416
- Hew K. F. and Brush T., (2007), Integrating technology into K-12 teaching and learning: current knowledge gaps and recommendations for future research, *Educ. Technol. Res. Dev.*, 55, 223–252.
- Hoffer M. and Grandgenett N., (2012), TPACK Development in Teacher Education: A Longitudinal Study of Pre-service Teachers in a Secondary M.A.Ed. Program, *J. Res. Technol. Educ.*, 45(1), 83–106.
- Horzum B. M., (2013), An investigation of the technological pedagogical content knowledge of pre-service teachers, *Technol., Pedagog. Educ.*, 22(3), 303–317.
- Hu C. and Fyfe V., (2010), Impact of a new curriculum on pre-service teachers' Technical, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK). *Proceedings Ascilite Sydney 2010*, Australia, 184–189.

- Keating T. and Evans E., (2001), Three computers in the back of the classroom: pre-service teachers' conceptions of technology integration, in Carlsen R., Davis N., Price J., Weber R. and Willis D. (ed.), *Society for Information Technology and Teacher Education Annual*, Norfolk, VA: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education, pp. 1671–1676.
- Kim M. C. and Hannafin M. J., (2011), Scaffolding problem solving in technology-enhanced learning environments (TELEs): bridging research and theory with practice, *Comput. Educ.*, 56(2), 403–417. .
- Klisch Y., Miller L. M. and Wang S., (2012), The impact of a science education game on students' learning and perception of inhalants as body pollutants, *J. Sci. Educ. Technol.*, 21, 295–303.
- Koehler M. J. and Mishra P., (2005), What happens when teachers design educational technology? The development of technological pedagogical content knowledge, *J. Educ. Comput. Res.*, 32(2), 131–152.
- Koehler M. J. and Mishra P., (2009), What is technological pedagogical content knowledge? *Contemp. Issues Technol. Teach. Educ.*, 9(1), 60–70.
- Koehler M. J., Mishra P. and Yahya K., (2007), Tracing the development of teacher knowledge in a design seminar: integrating content, pedagogy and technology, *Comput. Educ.*, 49(3), 740–762.
- Koehler M. J., Mishra P., Kereluik K., Shin T. S. and Graham C. R., (2014), Technological pedagogical content knowledge framework, in Spector J. M. et al. (ed.), *Handbook of Research on Educational Communications and Technology*, New York: Springer Science + Business Media, pp. 101–111.
- Koh J. H. L. and Chai C. S., (2014), Teacher clusters and their perceptions of technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) development through ICT lesson design, *Comput. Educ.*, 70, 222–232.
- Koh J. H. L. and Divaharan S., (2011), Towards a TPACK-fostering ICT instructional process for teachers: lessons from the implementation of interactive whiteboard instruction, *Australas. J. Educ. Technol.*, 29(2), 233–247.
- Koh J. H. L., Chai C. S. and Tsai C. C., (2010), Examining the technology pedagogical content knowledge of Singapore pre-service teachers with a large-scale survey, *J. Comput. Assist. Learn.*, 26(6), 563–573.

- Kramarski B. and Michalsky T., (2010), Preparing preservice teachers for self-regulated learning in the context of technological pedagogical content knowledge, *Learn. Instr.*, 20, 434–447.
- Kurt, S. "Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework," in Educational Technology, May 12, 2018.
- Kushner Benson S. N., Ward C. L. and Liang X., (2015), The essential role of pedagogical knowledge in technology integration for transformative teaching and learning, in Angeli C. and Valanides N. (ed.), *Technological pedagogical content knowledge exploring, developing, and assessing TPCK*, New York: Springer Science + Business Media, pp. 3–18.
- Lee M. H. and Tsai C. C., (2010), Exploring teachers' perceived self-efficacy and technological pedagogical content knowledge with respect to educational use of the World Wide Web, *Instr. Sci.*, 38(1), 1–21.
- Li M. C. and Tsai C. C., (2013), Game-based learning in science education: a review of relevant research, *J. Sci. Educ. Technol.*, 22, 877–898.
- Maeng J. L., Mulvey B. K., Smetana L. K. and Bell R. L., (2013), Preservice teachers' TPACK: using technology to support inquiry instruction, *J. Sci. Educ. Technol.*, 22(6), 838–857.
- McCrory R., (2008), Science, technology, and teaching: the topic-specific challenges of TPCK in science, in AACTE (ed.), *The handbook of technological pedagogical content knowledge for educators*, New York, NY: Routledge/Taylor & Francis Group for the American Association of Colleges of Teacher Education, pp. 193–206.
- Merriam S. B., (2009), *Qualitative research: a guide to design and implementation*, San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Mishra P. and Koehler M. J., (2006), Technological pedagogical content knowledge: a framework for integrating technology in teacher knowledge, *Teach. Coll. Rec.*, 108(6), 1017–1054.
- Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. (2007). Technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPCK): Confronting the wicked problems of teaching with technology. In C. Crawford et al. (Eds.), *Proceedings of Society for Information Technology and Teacher Education International Conference 2007* (pp. 2214-2226). Chesapeake, VA: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education.
- Moore E. B., Herzog T. A. and Perkins K. K., (2013), Interactive simulations as implicit support for guided-inquiry, *Chem. Educ. Res. Pract.*, 14, 257–268.

- Mouza C., (2011), Promoting urban teachers' understanding of technology, content, and pedagogy in the context of case development, *J. Res. Technol. Educ.*, 44(1), 1–29.
- Mouza C., Karchmer-Klein R., Nansakumar R., Ozden S. Y. and Hu L., (2014), Investigating the impact of an integrated approach to the development of preservice teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK), *Comput. Educ.*, 71, 206–221.
- Niess M. L., (2005), Preparing teachers to teach science and mathematics with technology: development of a technology pedagogical content knowledge, *Teach. Teach. Educ.*, 21(5), 509–523.
- Pallant J., (2007), *SPSS Survival Manual: a step by step guide to data analysis using SPSS for windows*, 3rd edn, New York: McGraw Hill, Open University Press.
- Patton M. Q., (2002), *Qualitative Research and Evaluation Methods*, 3rd edn, Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Ryan B. J., (2013), Line up, line up: using technology to align and enhance peer learning and assessment in a student centered foundation organic chemistry module, *Chem. Educ. Res. Pract.*, 14, 229–238.
- Schmidt DA, Baran E, Thompson AD, Mishra P, Koehler MJ, Shin TS. (2009) Technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK): The development and validation of an assessment instrument for preservice teachers. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 42(2), 123-149.
- Shulman L. S., (1986), Those who understand: knowledge growth in teaching, *Educ. Res.*, 15(4), 4–14.
- So H. J. and Kim B., (2009), Learning about problem based learning: Student teachers integrating technology, pedagogy and content knowledge, *Australas. J. Educ. Technol.*, 25(1), 101–116.
- Srisawasdi N., (2012), The role of TPACK in physics classroom: case studies of preservice physics teachers, *Procd. Soc. Behv. Sci.*, 46, 3235–3243.
- Taber K. S., (2017), The Use of Cronbach's Alpha When Developing and Reporting Research Instruments in Science Education, *Res. Sci. Educ.*, 1–24.
- Thompson A. D. and Mishra P., (2007), Breaking news: TPCK becomes TPACK! *J. Comput. Teach. Educ.*, 24(2), 38–64.
- Thompson A. D., (2005), Scientifically based research: establishing a research agenda for the technology in teacher education community, *J. Res. Technol. Educ.*, 37(4), 331–337.

- Yurdakul I. K., Odabasi H. F., Kilicer K., Coklar A. N., Birinci G. and Kurt A. A., (2012), The development, validity and reliability of TPACK-deep: a technological pedagogical content knowledge scale, *Comput. Educ.*, 58(3), 964–977.
- Zhao Y., (2003), *What teachers should know about technology: perspectives and practices*, Greenwich, CT: Information Age Publishing.

DRAFT TOOL
TPACK Questionnaire for Student Teachers

S.N	Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Sometimes	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I	Technological Knowledge (TK)					
1	I know how to solve my own technical problems in the classroom.					
2	I can learn technology easily.					
3	I keep up with important new technologies.					
4	I frequently play around with the technology.					
5	I know about a lot of different technologies.					
6	I have the technical skills I need to use technology.					
7	I have sufficient knowledge to solving a technical problem with the computer.					
8	I know about basic computer hardware (ex., CD-ROM, mother-board, RAM) and their functions.					
9	I know about basic computer software (ex., Windows, Media Player) and their functions.					
II	Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)					
10	I know how to assess student performance in a classroom.					
11	I can adapt my teaching based upon what students currently understand or do not understand.					
12	I can adapt my teaching style to different learners.					
13	I can assess student learning in multiple ways.					
14	I can use a wide range of teaching approaches in a classroom setting.					

15	I am familiar with common student understandings and misconceptions.					
16	I know how to organize and maintain classroom management.					
17	I have had formal pedagogical education or training.					
18	I use different evaluation methods and techniques.					
19	I apply different learning theories and approaches (ex, Constructivist Learning, Multiple Intelligence Theory, Project-based Teaching).					
20	I can aware of possible student learning difficulties and misconceptions in managing class.					
III	Content Knowledge (CK)					
21	I have sufficient knowledge about my subject matter.					
22	I have various ways and strategies of developing my understanding of my subject matter.					
23	I have sufficient knowledge of my subject to design a rubric that evaluates my teaching.					
24	I have sufficient knowledge to select technology that matches my subject matter.					
25	I can develop class activities and projects.					
26	I follow recent developments and applications in my content area.					
27	I recognize leaders in my content area.					
28	I follow up-to-date resources (books, and journals) in my content area.					
29	I follow conferences and activities in my content area.					
IV	Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK)					
30	I can choose technologies that enhance the teaching approaches for a lesson.					
31	I can choose technologies that enhance students' learning for a lesson.					
32	I think deeply about how technology could influence the teaching approaches I use in my classroom.					
33	I am thinking critically about how to use technology in my classroom.					

34	I can adapt the use of the technologies to different teaching activities.					
35	I can choose appropriate technologies for my teaching/learning approaches and strategies.					
36	I am using computer applications supporting student learning.					
37	I am able to select technologies useful for my teaching career.					
38	I can evaluate appropriateness of a new technology for teaching and learning.					
V	Technological Content Knowledge (TCK)					
39	I know about technologies that I can use for understanding my subject matter.					
40	I know how to match course objectives to technology.					
41	I know how to match technology to course objectives.					
42	I know how to create a lesson or unit that incorporates web based tools as an integral part of the course.					
43	I use technologies to reach course objectives easily in my lesson plan.					
44	I am preparing a lesson plan requiring use of instructional technologies.					
45	I can develop class activities and projects involving use of instructional technologies.					
VI	Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK)					
46	I can select effective teaching approaches to guide student thinking and learning within my subject area.					
47	I can use technology to collaborate with others who are distant from my classroom.					
48	I can create appropriate lesson plans that scaffold to student learning.					
49	I can select appropriate and effective teaching strategies for my content area.					
50	I am developing evaluation tests and surveys in my content area.					
51	I am preparing a lesson plan including class/school-wide activities.					
52	I can make connections among related subjects in my content area.					

53	I am collaborating in my content area with outside (out-of-school) activities.					
VII	Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK)					
54	I can teach lessons that appropriately combine my subject matter, technologies, and teaching approaches.					
55	I can select technologies to use in my classroom that enhance what I teach, how I teach, and what students learn.					
56	I can use strategies that combine content, technologies, and teaching approaches in my classroom.					
57	I can provide leadership in helping others to coordinate using content, technologies, and teaching approaches at my university.					
58	I can choose technologies that enhance the content for a lesson.					
59	I am integrating appropriate instructional methods and technologies into my content area.					
60	I can select contemporary strategies and technologies helping to teach my content effective.					
61	I can teach successfully by combining my content, pedagogy, and technology knowledge.					
62	I am taking a leadership role among my colleagues in the integration of content, pedagogy, and technology knowledge.					
63	I can teach a subject with different instructional strategies and computer applications.					

TPACK QUESTIONNAIRE
Item Total Correlation Value

S.N	Items	Item-Total Correlation	Selected Item (≥ 0.35)/ Eliminated Item (≤ 0.35)
1	I know how to solve my own technical problems in the classroom.	.340	Eliminated Item
2	I can learn technology easily.	.362	Selected Item
3	I keep up with important new technologies.	.376	Selected Item
4	I frequently play around with the technology.	.136	Eliminated Item
5	I know about a lot of different technologies.	.438	Selected Item
6	I have the technical skills I need to use technology.	.507	Selected Item
7	I have sufficient knowledge to solving a technical problem with the computer.	.460	Selected Item
8	I know about basic computer hardware (ex., CD-ROM, mother-board, RAM) and their functions.	.393	Selected Item
9	I know about basic computer software (ex., Windows, Media Player) and their functions.	.386	Selected Item
10	I know how to assess student performance in a classroom.	.262	Eliminated Item
11	I can adapt my teaching based upon what students currently understand or do not understand.	.374	Selected Item
12	I can adapt my teaching style to different learners.	.457	Selected Item
13	I can assess student learning in multiple ways.	.395	Selected Item
14	I can use a wide range of teaching approaches in a classroom setting.	.389	Selected Item
15	I am familiar with common student understandings and misconceptions.	.506	Selected Item
16	I know how to organize and maintain classroom management.	.349	Eliminated Item
17	I have had formal pedagogical	.373	Selected Item

	education or training.		
18	I use different evaluation methods and techniques.	.481	Selected Item
19	I apply different learning theories and approaches (ex, Constructivist Learning, Multiple Intelligence Theory, Project-based Teaching).	.336	Eliminated Item
20	I can aware of possible student learning difficulties and misconceptions in managing class.	.407	Selected Item
21	I have sufficient knowledge about my subject matter.	.120	Eliminated Item
22	I have various ways and strategies of developing my understanding of my subject matter.	.389	Selected Item
23	I have sufficient knowledge of my subject to design a rubric that evaluates my teaching.	.396	Selected Item
24	I have sufficient knowledge to select technology that matches my subject matter.	.443	Selected Item
25	I can develop class activities and projects.	.460	Selected Item
26	I follow recent developments and applications in my content area.	.337	Eliminated Item
27	I recognize leaders in my content area.	.526	Selected Item
28	I follow up-to-date resources (books, and journals) in my content area.	.138	Eliminated Item
29	I follow conferences and activities in my content area.	.534	Selected Item
30	I can choose technologies that enhance the teaching approaches for a lesson.	.374	Selected Item
31	I can choose technologies that enhance students' learning for a lesson.	.473	Selected Item
32	I think deeply about how technology could influence the teaching approaches I use in my classroom.	.404	Selected Item
33	I am thinking critically about how to use technology in my classroom.	.482	Selected Item
34	I can adapt the use of the technologies	.571	Selected Item

	to different teaching activities.		
35	I can choose appropriate technologies for my teaching/learning approaches and strategies.	.389	Selected Item
36	I am using computer applications supporting student learning.	.380	Selected Item
37	I am able to select technologies useful for my teaching career.	.284	Eliminated Item
38	I can evaluate appropriateness of a new technology for teaching and learning.	.604	Selected Item
39	I know about technologies that I can use for understanding my subject matter.	.315	Eliminated Item
40	I know how to match course objectives to technology.	.460	Selected Item
41	I know how to match technology to course objectives.	.458	Selected Item
42	I know how to create a lesson or unit that incorporates web based tools as an integral part of the course.	.416	Selected Item
43	I use technologies to reach course objectives easily in my lesson plan.	.394	Selected Item
44	I am preparing a lesson plan requiring use of instructional technologies.	.552	Selected Item
45	I can develop class activities and projects involving use of instructional technologies.	.383	Selected Item
46	I can select effective teaching approaches to guide student thinking and learning within my subject area.	.441	Selected Item
47	I can use technology to collaborate with others who are distant from my classroom.	.525	Selected Item
48	I can create appropriate lesson plans that scaffold to student learning.	.586	Selected Item
49	I can select appropriate and effective teaching strategies for my content area.	.577	Selected Item
50	I am developing evaluation tests and	.415	Selected Item

	surveys in my content area.		
51	I am preparing a lesson plan including class/school-wide activities.	.484	Selected Item
52	I can make connections among related subjects in my content area.	.482	Selected Item
53	I am collaborating in my content area with outside (out-of-school) activities.	.519	Selected Item
54	I can teach lessons that appropriately combine my subject matter, technologies, and teaching approaches.	.520	Selected Item
55	I can select technologies to use in my classroom that enhance what I teach, how I teach, and what students learn.	.416	Selected Item
56	I can use strategies that combine content, technologies, and teaching approaches in my classroom.	.311	Eliminated Item
57	I can provide leadership in helping others to coordinate using content, technologies, and teaching approaches at my university.	.406	Selected Item
58	I can choose technologies that enhance the content for a lesson.	.322	Eliminated Item
59	I am integrating appropriate instructional methods and technologies into my content area.	.475	Selected Item
60	I can select contemporary strategies and technologies helping to teach my content effective.	.530	Selected Item
61	I can teach successfully by combining my content, pedagogy, and technology knowledge.	.634	Selected Item
62	I am taking a leadership role among my colleagues in the integration of content, pedagogy, and technology knowledge.	.471	Selected Item
63	I can teach a subject with different instructional strategies and computer applications.	.404	Selected Item

FINAL TOOL

TPACK Questionnaire for Student Teachers

S.N	Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Sometimes	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I	Technological Knowledge (TK)					
1	I can learn technology easily.					
2	I keep up with important new technologies.					
3	I know about a lot of different technologies.					
4	I have the technical skills I need to use technology.					
5	I have sufficient knowledge to solving a technical problem with the computer.					
6	I know about basic computer hardware (ex., CD-ROM, mother-board, RAM) and their functions.					
7	I know about basic computer software (ex., Windows, Media Player) and their functions.					
II	Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)					
8	I can adapt my teaching based upon what students currently understand or do not understand.					
9	I can adapt my teaching style to different learners.					
10	I can assess student learning in multiple ways.					
11	I can use a wide range of teaching approaches in a classroom setting.					
12	I am familiar with common student understandings and misconceptions.					
13	I have had formal pedagogical education or training.					
14	I use different evaluation methods and techniques.					

15	I can aware of possible student learning difficulties and misconceptions in managing class.					
III	Content Knowledge (CK)					
16	I have various ways and strategies of developing my understanding of my subject matter.					
17	I have sufficient knowledge of my subject to design a rubric that evaluates my teaching.					
18	I have sufficient knowledge to select technology that matches my subject matter.					
19	I can develop class activities and projects.					
20	I recognize leaders in my content area.					
21	I follow conferences and activities in my content area.					
IV	Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK)					
22	I can choose technologies that enhance the teaching approaches for a lesson.					
23	I can choose technologies that enhance students' learning for a lesson.					
24	I think deeply about how technology could influence the teaching approaches I use in my classroom.					
25	I am thinking critically about how to use technology in my classroom.					
26	I can adapt the use of the technologies to different teaching activities.					
27	I can choose appropriate technologies for my teaching/learning approaches and strategies.					
28	I am using computer applications supporting student learning.					
29	I can evaluate appropriateness of a new technology for teaching and learning.					
V	Technological Content Knowledge (TCK)					
30	I know how to match course objectives to technology.					
31	I know how to match technology to course objectives.					
32	I know how to create a lesson or unit that incorporates web based tools as an integral part of the course.					

33	I use technologies to reach course objectives easily in my lesson plan.					
34	I am preparing a lesson plan requiring use of instructional technologies.					
35	I can develop class activities and projects involving use of instructional technologies.					
VI	Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK)					
36	I can select effective teaching approaches to guide student thinking and learning within my subject area.					
37	I can use technology to collaborate with others who are distant from my classroom.					
38	I can create appropriate lesson plans that scaffold to student learning.					
39	I can select appropriate and effective teaching strategies for my content area.					
40	I am developing evaluation tests and surveys in my content area.					
41	I am preparing a lesson plan including class/school-wide activities.					
42	I can make connections among related subjects in my content area.					
43	I am collaborating in my content area with outside (out-of-school) activities.					
VII	Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK)					
44	I can teach lessons that appropriately combine my subject matter, technologies, and teaching approaches.					
45	I can select technologies to use in my classroom that enhance what I teach, how I teach, and what students learn.					
46	I can provide leadership in helping others to coordinate using content, technologies, and teaching approaches at my university.					
47	I am integrating appropriate instructional methods and technologies into my content area.					
48	I can select contemporary strategies and technologies helping to teach my content effective.					
49	I can teach successfully by combining my content, pedagogy, and technology knowledge.					
50	I am taking a leadership role among my colleagues in the integration of content, pedagogy, and					

	technology knowledge.					
51	I can teach a subject with different instructional strategies and computer applications.					